

Energy-efficient AI-ready Data Spaces

D3.1: First Version of Energy-Efficient Large-Scale Data Analytics Services

Abstract:

Deliverable D3.1 provides the first version of the energy-efficient large-scale data analytics services tailored to six distinct Use Cases spanning four industries. Specifically, this report discusses related work, introduces each developed service, presents preliminary results, and outlines future plans. The report emphasises the 'green' dimension of the developed services reinforcing GREEN.DAT.AI's commitment to sustainability. Additionally, it includes six workflows that utilise the developed services, showcasing how these services align with GREEN.DAT.AI and how they can be interconnected to effectively address the objectives and meet the requirements of the GREEN.DAT.AI Use Cases.

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	14
1.1	Purpose of the document	14
1.2	Relationship to other Work Packages and Deliverables	20
1.3	Contribution to WP3 and Project Objectives.....	21
1.4	Document Structure.....	21
2	Energy-Efficient Large-Scale Data Analytics Services	22
2.1	AI-enabled data enrichment	23
2.1.1	Description of Data enrichment service	23
2.1.2	Evaluation of Data enrichment service.....	27
2.1.3	Next steps	28
2.2	Incentive mechanisms for Data Anonymisation and Sharing	28
2.2.1	Description of data monetization mechanisms for data sharing service	28
2.2.2	Evaluation of data monetization mechanisms for data sharing service.....	30
2.2.3	Description of data marketplaces using blockchain service.....	31
2.2.4	Evaluation of data marketplaces using blockchain service	39
2.2.5	Next steps	41
2.3	Synthetic Data Generators.....	41
2.3.1	Description of Mobility trajectory data generation (IMN-cloning Car Trajectory Synthesis) service	42
2.3.2	Evaluation of Mobility trajectory data generation (IMN-cloning Car Trajectory Synthesis) service	44
2.3.3	Next steps	47
2.4	Large-scale time series analytics.....	48
2.4.1	Trajectory-based battery consumption estimation (ThunderFlow)	48
2.4.2	Evaluation of Trajectory-based battery consumption estimation (ThunderFlow)	52
2.4.3	Description of EV Transaction Data Forecasting service	55
2.4.4	Evaluation of EV Transaction Data Forecasting service.....	56
2.4.5	Next steps	59
2.5	Federated & Auto ML at the edge/fog.....	60
2.5.1	Description of Privacy-preserving FL service	60
2.5.2	Evaluation of Privacy-preserving FL service.....	64
2.5.3	Description of Algorithm Selection & Hyperparameter Tuning/AutoML service.....	65
2.5.4	Evaluation of Algorithm Selection & Hyperparameter Tuning/AutoML service	67

2.5.5	Next steps	70
2.6	Explainable AI/Feature Learning with Privacy Preservation	70
2.6.1	Description of Explainable feature learning service	70
2.6.2	Description of Interpretable Clustering (ParTree Clustering Algorithm) service.....	72
2.6.3	Evaluation of Interpretable Clustering (ParTree Clustering Algorithm) service	76
2.6.4	Next steps	80
2.7	Federated & Automatic Transfer Learning	81
2.7.1	Description of weighted FL (FL for timeseries forecasting) service.....	81
2.7.2	Evaluation of weighted FL service	82
2.7.3	Next steps	84
2.8	Adaptive FL for Digital Twin Applications	84
2.8.1	Description of Orchestration Framework for Derivation Geospatial Data Products service	86
2.8.2	Description of Behaviour Modelling Pipelines service	87
2.8.3	Description of Event Detection on Fused Datasets service	88
2.8.4	Next steps	89
2.9	Automated IoT event-based change detection/ forecasting.....	89
2.9.1	Description of Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox.....	90
2.9.2	Evaluation of Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox	93
2.9.3	Description of Accelerated Event Processing Engine	93
2.9.4	Evaluation of Accelerated Event Processing Engine.....	95
2.9.5	Next steps	97
3	Discussion of the Green Dimension of the WP3 Services	98
4	WP3 Toolbox in GREEN.DAT.AI & UC Workflows.....	101
4.1	UC#1 Workflow	101
4.2	UC#2 Workflow	102
4.3	UC#3 Workflow	104
4.4	UC#4 Workflow	106
4.5	UC#5 Workflow	107
4.6	UC#6 Workflow	109
5	Conclusion	110
6	References.....	111
Appendix I – AI-based Tools Background		114
Appendix II – Ethics Checklist		143

List of Tables

Table 1.1: Relevance of the deliverable D3.1 in context of GREEN.DAT.AI Grant Agreement	15
Table 2.1: List of services developed within WP3.	22
Table 2.2: Illustration of the results for a simple synthetic dataset (social welfare mechanism).....	31
Table 2.3: Overview of the model’s parameters	49
Table 2.4: Overview of the model’s parameters	51
Table 2.5: Execution results.....	52
Table 2.6: Overview of charging transactions data from semi-public charging stations in Portugal.....	57
Table 2.7: Experimental results. For each algorithm and dataset, we report the performance of the best parameter configuration w.r.t. SIL. The overall highest value per measure is in bold while the highest among tree-based methods is in italic and blue.	77
Table 2.8: List of implemented earth observation indices on top of the Sentinel 2 data products.	86
Table 2.9: Results of predictions of water quality behaviour parameters.	88
Table 2.10: Performance achieved by the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ under different processing conditions (i.e., number of patterns, input size, and workload).....	96
Table 2.11: Performance achieved by the GNU grep tool under different processing conditions (i.e., number of patterns and workload).....	96

List of Figures

Figure 2.1: RDF-Gen architecture overview.	24
Figure 2.2: The Global Administrative Areas (GADM) of Slovenia at level 2 and location of sensors in the data sample evaluated (green dots).....	27
Figure 2.3: Social welfare auction mechanism: an overview.	30
Figure 2.4: Illustration of the results for a simple synthetic dataset (data-by-data mechanism).....	31
Figure 2.5. Architecture of the Predico data marketplace.....	32
Figure 2.6. Data Market Platform - components and interactions.	33
Figure 2.7. Available interactions with the Data Market for the transfer of data.	33
Figure 2.8: Home dashboard of the application.....	34
Figure 2.9: Forecasts computed by the Data Market.....	35
Figure 2.10: Data upload preferences and measurements home section (a).....	35
Figure 2.11: Data upload preferences and measurements home section (b).....	36
Figure 2.12: Agent wallet.....	36
Figure 2.13: Bid validation process.....	37
Figure 2.14: Overview architecture and available interactions for the transfer of data.	40
Figure 2.15: Overview of the process IMN	42
Figure 2.16: Illustration of the locations of a sample user in the two areas (original one on the left, located in Tuscany; remapped one on the right, in Porto).	45
Figure 2.17: Illustration of the distribution of RMSE obtained over 1'000 IMNs mapped. The left plot represents the global RMSE, while the right one is limited to the 10 most frequent locations of each IMN.	46
Figure 2.18: On the left plot, the road network of Porto is presented, highlighting frequency of visit of road segments through their width. On the right plot, a map showing the distribution of roads in the area.	46
Figure 2.19: Distribution of computation times (in seconds) required to generate the trajectory history of a user over a window of two weeks (as in the previous tests).	47
Figure 2.20: ThunderFlow's core architecture composed of four principal modules.	48
Figure 2.21: Overview of all the flows considered in the estimation of the consumptions.	50
Figure 2.22: Execution results.	52
Figure 2.23: Dataset overview.....	53
Figure 2.24: Estimation of battery consumption.....	53
Figure 2.25: Overview of the day-of-week distribution of consumption (left plot); Overview of the hourly distribution of battery consumptions (right plot).	54
Figure 2.26: Overview of average consumption per km for each road in cities of Florence and Bologna.	54
Figure 2.27: Framework of EV Transaction Data Forecasting	55
Figure 2.28: Comparison of MAE (duration) for T3 (low variability) achieved by proposed method (xgb) and reference naïve models.	57
Figure 2.29: Comparison of MAE (duration) for T5 (low variability) achieved by proposed method (xgb) and reference naïve models.	58
Figure 2.30: Comparison of MAE (Charged Energy) for T3 (low variability) achieved by proposed method (xgb) and reference naïve models.	58
Figure 2.31: Comparison of MAE (Charged Energy) for T5 (high variability) achieved by proposed method (xgb) and reference naïve models.	59
Figure 2.32: VAR model representation (1 timestamp ahead, using p lags on power time series).....	60
Figure 2.33: Performance of the models for 3 of the 10 zones in terms of RMSE.....	65
Figure 2.34: Service application in both offline and online phase.	67

Figure 2.35: Example of redistribution output after minimum cost flow optimisation. 68

Figure 2.36: Results’ box plots regarding MAE. 69

Figure 2.37: Best Trials per algorithm: x-axis: Frequency of the optimization procedures (one for each bike station) according to required iterations, y-axis : Number of iterations for the optimization algorithm to find the optimal configuration. (Upper) MLP Search and (Lower) XGBoost Search 69

Figure 2.38: Probability distributions agreement of classes c_0 and c_1 in case of an arbitrary feature with the range [0,12]. 71

Figure 2.39: Features selection on (a) the initial graph G, where in steps (b) – (e) features of the highest quality (red) are selected and their neighbours (blue) are removed. 72

Figure 2.40: ParTree application on the iris dataset. Partitioning logic as rules (1st plot, number within parenthesis are absolute and relative number of records in a cluster); partitioning logic as scatter plot (2nd), iris classes (3rd). 73

Figure 2.41: Critical Difference plots with Nemenyi at 95% confidence among all datasets. 78

Figure 2.42: Clustering visualisations for home. Top: ParTree; bottom, from left to right: k-Means, AHC. 79

Figure 2.43: User study results. (left) success rate, (center) cognitive effort, (right) usability. 80

Figure 2.44 - FedEDF Architecture Overview 82

Figure 2.45 - Snapshot of INESC TEC dataset; Illustrating EV chargers’ demand in terms of power (W) 82

Figure 2.46 - FedEDF Training Workflow 83

Figure 2.47 - FedEDF Preliminary Demonstration 83

Figure 2.48: Overall service architecture for derivation digital twin applications. 84

Figure 2.49: Architecture of GREEN.DAT.AI services for Digital Twin applications. 86

Figure 2.50: Data processing flow loading two different geospatial products and producing derived spatial map. 87

Figure 2.51: ConvLSTM architecture for predicting spectral indices of raster type. 87

Figure 2.52: Prediction of crop behaviour on raster data using NDVI. 88

Figure 2.53: Predicted crop development map (left), actually observed crop development (centre), and accordingly generated spraying map. 89

Figure 2.54. Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox, high-level architecture (final) 91

Figure 2.55. Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox, high-level architecture (current). 91

Figure 2.56. Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox, GraphQL ontology (current) 92

Figure 2.57: High-level overview of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ in GREEN.DAT.AI 93

Figure 2.58: Example execution of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ 94

Figure 2.59: Input used for the execution of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’. 94

Figure 2.60: Pattern file used for the execution of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’. 94

Figure 2.61: Output of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ using as input the annual user surveys that SERVEO receives from their customers. 95

Figure 2.62: Patterns used to extract negative reviews from the annual user survey. 95

Figure 2.63: OpenCL devices present in the testing environment. 96

Figure 4.1: UC#1 workflow utilising WP3 services. 102

Figure 4.2: UC#2 workflow utilising WP3 services. 104

Figure 4.3: UC#3 workflow utilising WP3 services. 105

Figure 4.4: UC#4 workflow utilising WP3 services. 107

Figure 4.5: UC#5 workflow utilising WP3 services. 108

Figure 4.6: UC#6 workflow utilising WP3 services. 109

List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
ADMM	Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AHC	Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
ARIMA	AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average
AutoML	Automated Machine Learning
BDA	Big Data Analytics
BIC	Bayesian Information Criterion
BIRCH	Balanced Iterative Reducing and Clustering using Hierarchies
CDRs	Call Detail Records
CI/CD	Continuous Integration and Deployment
CLTree	Clustering Through Decision Tree
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
ConvLSTM	Convolutional Long Short-Term Memory
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CPT	Center-based ParTree
CSMS	Charging Station Management System
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DBSCAN	Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise
DFA	Deterministic Finite Automaton
DFT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DML	Distributed Machine Learning
DoA	Description of Action
ESRI	Environmental Systems Research Institute
EV	Electric Vehicle
EVPRE	Electric Vehicle Path and Range Estimator
FedAvg	FEDerated AVeraging
FedEDF	FEDerated learning approach for Energy/power Demand Forecasting
FL	Federated Learning
FLS	Federated Learning Services
GA	Grant Agreement
GFS	GeMMA Fusion Suite
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit

ICE	Internal Combustion Engine
IMM	Iterative Mistake Minimisation
IMN	Individual Mobility Network
IO-HMM	Input-Output Hidden Markov Model
IoT(A)	Internet of Things (Application)
IPT	Impurity-based ParTree
JDL/DFIG	Joint Directors of Laboratories/Data Fusion Information Group
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LASSO	Least Absolute Shrinkage
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MA(P)E	Mean Absolute (Percentage) Error
MCA	Multiple Correspondence Analysis
MFA	Multi-Factor Authentication
MKR	Meta-Knowledge Repository
ML	Machine Learning
(R)MSE	(Root) Mean Squared Error
NASA-TLX	NASA Task Load Index
OpenCL	Open Computing Language
OPTICS	Ordering Points To Identify the Clustering Structure
OSRM	Open Source Routing Machine
ParTree	Partitioning Tree
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
POI	Point of Interest
PPT	Principal-based ParTree
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SCS	System Causability Scale
SGD	Stochastic Gradient Descent
SIMD	Single Instruction, Multiple Data
SotA	State-of-the-Art
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
SVM	Support Vector Machine
TIFF	Tagged Image File Format
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TTL	Terse RDF Triple Language
UC	Use Case
VAE	Variational AutoEncoder
VAR	Vector AutoRegressive
VPT	Feature-Values to Use for Partitioning

WM5	Geometric Tools and Wild Magic
XAI	eXplainable Artificial Intelligence
XGBoost	eXtreme Gradient Boosting
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides the first version of the energy-efficient large-scale data analytics services tailored to six distinct Use Cases (UCs) spanning across four industries: Smart Energy, Smart Agriculture/Agri-food, Smart Mobility, and Smart Banking. Specifically, D3.1 comprises a software library accessible at the GREEN.DAT.AI GitHub Repository¹, accompanied by a comprehensive report. The report offers an overview of the services devised within WP3, discussing related work, presenting preliminary results, and outlining future plans.

These services cover various crucial areas including Artificial Intelligence (AI)-enabled data enrichment, Incentive mechanisms for Data Sharing, Synthetic Data Generation, Large-scale learning at the edge/fog, Federated & Automated Machine Learning (AutoML) at the edge/fog, Explainable AI/Feature Learning with Privacy Preservation, Federated & Automatic Transfer Learning, Adaptive Federated Learning (FL) for Digital Twin Applications, and Automated Internet of Things (IoT) event-based change detection/forecasting.

A significant aspect of this deliverable is the incorporation of technical expertise and insights gained from the analysis in WP1, along with the specific needs and requirements of the GREEN.DAT.AI UCs identified within WP4. As such, presently, 16 services are being developed within WP3, either already customised or currently undergoing customisation to facilitate the UCs and their envisioned workflows. These developments align closely with the overarching ambition of GREEN.DAT.AI, which prioritises addressing environmental concerns associated with the management and processing of large data volumes. Specifically, the following services are being developed:

- ‘Data enrichment’: enriching UCs data with external data sources, e.g., mobility data with weather.
- ‘Data monetisation mechanisms for data sharing’: mathematical algorithms designed to facilitate interaction between data owners aiming to create two primary incentives for data sharing.
- ‘Data marketplaces using blockchain’: orchestrating all the processes including the interactions between data owners and application of the incentive mechanisms.
- ‘Mobility trajectory data generation’: generating synthetic trajectory data.
- ‘Trajectory-based battery consumption estimation’: estimating battery consumption of Electric Vehicles (EVs) along with their input trajectories.
- ‘EV Transaction Data Forecasting’: forecasting parking duration and charged energy per transaction of an EV owner.
- ‘Privacy-preserving FL’: algorithms allowing to combine and predict multiple time series, owned by multiple owners, with a unique model; ensuring data privacy without affecting the accuracy of the collaborative model.
- ‘Algorithm Selection & Hyperparameter Tuning/AutoML’: meta-feature model for algorithm selection prior to hyperparameter tuning to optimise bikes’ redistribution among stations.
- ‘Explainable feature learning’: improving classifiers and regressions performance through a set of data transformations.
- ‘Interpretable Clustering’: clustering over mixed-type tabular data yielding tree-structure and human-readable outputs.
- ‘(weighted) FL’: exploiting neural networks and cross-device FL to predict the energy demand of EV chargers.

¹ <https://github.com/greendataai-eu>

- ‘Orchestration framework for derivation geospatial data products’: a basic instantiation of the developed data fusion architecture, applied on raster data for assessing the state of agricultural fields and water bodies with spectral indices derived from the satellite images.
- ‘Behaviour modelling pipelines’: predicting various attributes related to the observed geospatial entities.
- ‘Event detection on fused datasets’: implementing abnormality detection on raster or sensory data.
- ‘Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox’: configurable data ingestion service, event-based change detection, summary statistics, and forecasting.
- ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’: core operation based on pattern matching inspired by the Aho-Corasick algorithm.

Based on these services, six workflows are provided combining the developed services, demonstrating their alignment with GREEN.DAT.AI and their potential to effectively address the objectives of the UCs. Notably, this deliverable underscores the importance of the green dimension of the most developed services, which contribute to reducing the energy footprint, in alignment with GREEN.DAT.AI's commitment to sustainability.

In summary, this deliverable sets the foundation for further advancements in data analytics, as it provides the first version of the energy-efficient large-scale data analytics services, serving as the innovations to be demonstrated within the UCs.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

Deliverable D3.1 – First Version of Energy-Efficient Large-Scale Data Analytics Services, comprises a software library and a report consolidating the services development and the results of the technical work carried out within WP3, in Tasks T3.1-T3.5. D3.1 represents a pivotal milestone within the GREEN.DAT.AI project, presenting the first iteration of the work employed towards the design and development of 16 different services that aspire to provide energy-efficient large-scale data analytics tailored to six distinct UCs (*Energy Marketplaces - Data sharing across the renewable energy sector, Energy - Smart electric vehicle charging, Agriculture - Smart farming optimisation through Digital Twins, Agrifood - Smart water management, smart green mobility - Energy demand response in e-bikes & infrastructure planning, and Banking - Fraud detection and efficient explainable AI with privacy preservation*) spanning four industries (*Smart Energy, Smart Agriculture/Agri-food, Smart Mobility, and Smart Banking*). These services cover key areas including AI-enabled data enrichment, Incentive mechanisms for Data Sharing, Synthetic Data Generation, Large-scale learning at the edge/fog, Federated & AutoML at the edge/fog, Explainable AI/Feature Learning with Privacy Preservation, Federated & Automatic Transfer Learning, Adaptive FL for Digital Twin Applications, and Automated IoT event-based change detection/forecasting, therefore playing a pivotal role in addressing the project's objectives of innovation and sustainability.

As FL assumes a central role across multiple services, it is important to highlight its key role in training Machine Learning (ML) models across decentralised data sources without exchanging raw data. FL provides several benefits across these services, particularly in terms of data privacy preservation, energy efficiency enhancement, system efficiency, and improvement of algorithm performance. Specifically, FL enables local model training without central data sharing, ensuring the preservation of sensitive information. Moreover, FL reduces the computational burden on individual devices, leading to enhanced energy efficiency. Additionally, by distributing model training across multiple devices or servers, FL minimises data transfers to a central server, thus reducing network usage and improving system efficiency. Furthermore, FL facilitates the development of robust ML algorithms for large-scale time series analytics leading to improved accuracy by capturing patterns and insights from heterogeneous data sources.

Developed within WP3, these services signify a crucial advancement towards the project's overarching objectives. Comprising both a software library and a comprehensive report, D3.1 offers a multifaceted approach to developing solutions guided by UC needs addressed in T1.1 and WP4, along with tools to support the deployment of operational solutions using the facilities developed in WP2. The software library, accessible through the GREEN.DAT.AI GitHub Repository² (detailed in Table 2.1), serves as a tangible demonstration of the project's progress in developing cutting-edge solutions for data analytics. The accompanying report provides a detailed overview of the services devised within WP3. Each service is meticulously evaluated, with preliminary results presented alongside discussions on the State-of-Art (SotA) and future plans.

Significantly, the services developed within GREEN.DAT.AI contribute to the Europe's ambitious sustainability goals, outlined in the EU Green Deal, by targeting the minimisation of the energy footprint of data management. By emphasising the energy efficiency of the developed services, the project addresses a key aspect of sustainability. Moreover, the adaptability of these services to different user needs ensures their

² <https://github.com/greendatai-eu>

widespread applicability across various UCs and industries. Therefore, this deliverable emphasises the energy efficiency of the developed services, highlighting their ‘green’ dimension and underscoring GREEN.DAT.AI's commitment to sustainability and environmental stewardship.

A second version of this deliverable (D3.2) will be provided on M24 to outline updates and the final version of the energy-efficient large-scale data analytics services developed, consolidating them into a toolbox, which will be integrated in the GREEN.DAT.AI infrastructure and tested in the UCs. The final version of the services will demonstrate improved energy efficiency by at least 10% measured against baseline scenarios and metrics identified in D1.1.

The following table provides the relevance of the contents of this deliverable with the Grant Agreement (GA).

Table 1.1: Relevance of the deliverable D3.1 in context of GREEN.DAT.AI Grant Agreement

GREEN.DAT.AI GA Component Title	GREEN.DAT.AI GA Component Outline	Respective Document Section(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D3.1. First Version of Energy-Efficient Large-Scale Data Analytics Services	D3.1 presents the first iteration of the work employed towards the design and development of nine different services that aspire to provide energy-efficient large-scale data analytics.	Sections 2, and 3	All sections reflect the work performed within WP3 tasks and subtasks. Particularly, section 2 describes the services developed, and section 3 discusses services’ energy efficient dimension. Appendix I provides an overview of SotA.
	The software library and report will cover AI-enabled data enrichment, Incentive mechanisms for Data Sharing, Synthetic Data Generation, Large-scale learning at the Edge/ Fog, Federated & AutoML at the edge/fog, Explainable AI, Feature Learning with Privacy Preservation, Federated & Automatic Transfer Learning, Adaptive FL for Digital Twin Applications, Automated IoT event-based change detection/ forecasting.	Section 2	The software library is accessible through the GREEN.DAT.AI GitHub Repository, whereas the developed services, included in section 2, cover the following nine key areas: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ AI-enabled data enrichment, ▪ Incentive mechanisms for Data Sharing, ▪ Synthetic Data Generation, ▪ Large-scale learning at the Edge/ Fog, ▪ Federated & AutoML at the edge/fog, ▪ Explainable AI, Feature Learning with Privacy Preservation, ▪ Federated & Automatic Transfer Learning, ▪ Adaptive FL for Digital Twin Applications, ▪ Automated IoT event-based change detection/ forecasting.
	GREEN.DAT.AI will develop analytics services being adaptable to user needs, as demonstrated in different UC context.	Sections 2 & 4	The services described in section 2 were developed by considering the following:

	Efficient solutions will be developed, guided by pilot needs addressed in T1.1 and WP4.		<p>a) Technical expertise and insights gained from the analysis in WP1, including the technical requirements and specifications identified therein, and specifically the envisaged technical offerings presented in D1.1.</p> <p>b) UCs and their needs specified within WP4 and the respective workflows presented in D4.7.</p> <p>To ensure that the specific needs and requirements of GREEN.DAT.AI UCs are met, 16 services were developed. These services have been appropriately customised to facilitate the envisioned UC workflows described in section 4. Most services are provided as open-source tools to accelerate upscaling and commercialisation.</p>
	WP3 will (1) advance SotA solutions for large-scale data analytics including learning (FL, AutoML, etc.) methods at the edge/fog, transfer learning, digital twins, (2) embed privacy-preservation and explainability mechanisms in the services.	Section 2	Section 2 describes the services that advance SotA (presented in Appendix I) for large-scale data analytics including learning at the edge/fog, FL, digital twins and AutoML methods, while special focus is given into embedding privacy-preservation and explainability mechanisms in the services.
	Technical requirements set in WP1-2 will be studied. Develop novel Energy-Efficient Large-Scale Data Analytics Services including Federated Learning Services (FLS) and tools, supporting deployment of operational solutions using the facilities developed in WP2.	Section 2 and 3	The novel Energy-Efficient Large-Scale Data Analytics Services take into account the technical specifications of the reference architecture for AI-ready Data Spaces.
	GREEN.DAT.AI will develop analytics services contributing to the energy footprint minimisation.	Section 4	Most of the developed services are energy-efficient. Section 4 describes the energy-efficient part of the services.
TASKS			
Task 3.1 AI-enabled data enrichment and sharing – Synthetic data generation	Effective use of datasets assumes a series of data pre-processing actions including cleansing, semantic annotation, and augmentation. In order to be able to handle datasets containing sensitive information, this task will also perform anonymisation on the data ingestion process to protect this information as well as incentive mechanisms for data sharing. It consists of subtasks ST3.1.1, ST3.1.2, and ST3.1.3.	Sections: 2.1-2.3	These sections reflect the work performed in T3.1 of the project. Particularly, the services that were developed cover the key areas of data enrichment, incentive mechanisms and synthetic data generation.

<p>ST3.1.1 Efficient tools for data enrichment</p>	<p>Effective use of datasets assumes a series of data pre- processing actions including cleansing, semantic annotation, and augmentation. In order to be able to handle datasets containing sensitive information, this task will also perform anonymisation on the data ingestion process to protect this information. Due to the need for huge volumes of data for testing and validation purposes, this task will also develop synthetic data generation tools based on pilot specifications. The result of the task will be a toolset for data enrichment and synthetic data generation.</p>	<p>Section: 2.1</p>	<p>This section reflects the work performed in ST3.1.1. Particularly, the service called ‘Data enrichment’ was developed, which conducts enrichment of UCs data with external data sources, e.g., mobility data with weather.</p>
<p>ST3.1.2 Incentive mechanisms for data anonymisation and sharing</p>	<p>Since data privacy enabled by FL variants may not be enough to incentivize data sharing, this subtask will design a set of incentive mechanisms for data sharing, having in mind that these mechanisms should be helpful to attract data consumers and increase data sellers’ revenue. Two main types of mechanisms will be considered: (a) data monetisation departing from data auction solutions of past projects such as H2020 Smart4RES, namely game theory and social welfare maximisation; (b) barter trading, in particular data-by-data (processed as raw material) and data-by-service (processed as an information product) exchange schemes leveraged by distributed ledger technology (IOTA).</p>	<p>Section: 2.2</p>	<p>This section reflects the work performed in ST3.1.2. Particularly, two services were developed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The ‘Data monetisation mechanisms for data sharing’ comprises a collection of mathematical algorithms designed to facilitate interaction between data owners aiming to create two primary incentives for data sharing. ▪ The ‘Data marketplaces using blockchain’ orchestrates all the processes including the interactions between data owners and application of the incentive mechanisms.
<p>ST3.1.3 Synthetic data generators</p>	<p>Due to the need for huge volumes of data for testing and validation purposes, this task will also develop synthetic data generation tools based on pilot specifications. The result of the task will be a toolset for data enrichment – anonymisation – sharing as well as a library of synthetic data generators (D3.1).</p>	<p>Section: 2.3</p>	<p>This section reflects the work performed in ST3.1.3, and in particular a service called ‘Mobility trajectory data generation (IMN-cloning Car Trajectory Synthesis)’ was developed providing synthetic trajectory data generation functionalities. This service will be adopted in UC#2.2, and integrated in the project infrastructure.</p>
<p>Task 3.2 Large-scale learning at the edge/fog</p>	<p>This task will develop analytics modules that can be seamlessly integrated with the GREEN.DAT.AI infrastructure developed in WP2. Modelling of data will be based on the time series paradigm. It consists of subtasks ST3.2.1, ST3.2.2, and ST3.2.3.</p>	<p>Sections: 2.4-2.6</p>	<p>These sections reflect the work performed in T3.2 of the project. Particularly, the services that were developed cover the key areas of Large-scale time series analytics, Federated & AutoML at the edge/fog, and Explainable AI /Feature Learning with Privacy Preservation.</p>
<p>ST3.2.1 Large-scale time series analytics</p>	<p>Efficient similarity search, classification, and forecasting methods. The result of the subtask will be a suite of (mainly</p>	<p>Section: 2.4</p>	<p>This section reflects the work performed in ST3.2.1 of the project.</p>

	edge/fog- based) large-scale analytics methods.		<p>Particularly, two services were developed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The ‘Trajectory-based battery consumption estimation (ThunderFlow)’ estimates the battery consumption of Electric Vehicles (EVs) along with their input trajectories. ▪ The ‘EV Transaction Data Forecasting’ forecasts parking duration and charged energy per transaction of an EV owner.
ST3.2.2 Federated & AutoML at the edge/fog	<p>This subtask will implement privacy-preserving horizontal and vertical FL for time series forecasting and modelling. The FL method from Smart4RES (European Patent Application EP20215836) consisted in combining an algebraic cryptography protocol, alternating direction method of multipliers (ADMM) and vector autoregressive models (with different LASSO variants). In this subtask, kernel least squares framework will be explored to model non-linear relations between multiple inputs and outputs, and guarantee data privacy at the same time. The result of the task will be a toolset for learning, including FL and AutoML, methods efficiently performing at the fog/edge.</p>	Section: 2.5	<p>This section reflects the work performed in ST3.2.2 of the project. Particularly, two services were developed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The ‘Privacy-preserving FL’ is a set of algorithms that allows to combine and predict multiple time series, owned by multiple owners, with a unique model; this service ensures data privacy without affecting the accuracy of the collaborative model. ▪ The ‘Algorithm Selection & Hyperparameter Tuning/AutoML’ employs a meta-feature model for algorithm selection prior to hyperparameter tuning to optimise bikes’ redistribution among the stations.
ST3.2.3 Explainable AI /Feature Learning with Privacy Preservation	<p>This subtask will develop extensions to previous work so that data privacy can be preserved for complex AI models, deliver explainability of the models to the human decision-maker in the context of vertical FL and applying them to the banking sector.</p>	Section: 2.6	<p>This section reflects the work performed in ST3.2.3. There were two services developed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The ‘Explainable feature learning’ learns a set of data transformations that improves the performances of classifiers and regressions. ▪ The ‘Interpretable Clustering’ performs clustering over mixed-type tabular data yielding tree-structure and human-readable outputs.
Task 3.3 Federated & Automatic Transfer Learning	<p>Complex application scenarios require new distributed learning solutions where nodes might know different (only partially overlapping) subsets of features and different data samples. The result of this task will be a set of Federated Transfer Learning methods that take into account the knowledge transformations needed to let different node exchange information and converge towards a collective ML model. The specific FTL</p>	Section: 2.7	<p>This section reflects the work performed in Task 3.3. Particularly, one service was developed called ‘(weighted) FL’ service, which exploits on neural networks and cross-device FL to predict the energy demand of EV chargers.</p> <p>Note: Services related to transfer learning are currently under</p>

	tasks will follow the needs of pilot applications in WP4.		development and will be described in deliverable D3.2.
Task 3.4 Adaptive FL for Digital Twin Applications	Within this task, (near) real-time map generation framework (GeMMA Fusion Suit) will be extended with the GREEN.DAT.AI analytics modules from T3.2, to fulfil key functional requirements for building Digital Twins. While structuring the analytics technology stack will follow the JDL/DFIG reference data-fusion model, management of subscribed edge devices (i.e. satellites, UAVs, and IoT Hubs) and internal communication protocols will be developed, so that they can in turn be utilised in FL. Accordingly, existing map generation tools will be adapted for rendering the behaviour of the learned models, thus, providing the basis for implementation of smart farming and water management tools in T4.4 and T4.5.	Section: 2.8	This section reflects the work performed in T3.4 of the project. Particularly, three services were developed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The ‘Orchestration framework for derivation geospatial data products’ provides a basic instantiation of the developed data fusion architecture, applied on raster data, while it provides core functionalities for assessment of the state of the agricultural fields and water bodies with spectral indices derived from the satellite images. ▪ The ‘Behaviour modelling pipelines’ addresses predictions of a various sets of different attributes related to the observed geospatial entities. ▪ The ‘Event detection on fused datasets’ is implemented as abnormality detection raster or sensory data.
Task 3.5 Automated IoT event-based change detection & forecasting	T3.5 will develop a service for event detection over large data sets from a network of IoT devices. Each device will be producing a stream of data stored locally in timeseries optimised databases and handled using an adapted version of the Accelerated Event-Processing Engine. Using this data, plug-in widgets will provide (in real-time) summary statistics and issue warnings when thresholds are met, as well as provide (in near real-time) the output of pre-trained neural network models. On top of this and building on work of the INSPECTr H2020 project, a graph network will be developed that will represent each IoT device by a node in a storage graph database (e.g., Neo4j), and embed edges between each pair of nodes with distance metrics (e.g., ‘straight line’ distance, traffic-dependent traveling distance), thus encompassing the geospatial dimension of the deployed IoT devices. At the federal level, the graph network will be used to access and handle data collected (by IoT devices) and produced (by widgets and pre-trained NN) at the edge, allowing for a database-natural and efficient way (compared to	Section: 2.9	This section reflects the work performed in T3.5 of the project. Particularly, two services were developed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The ‘Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox’ is a fully configurable data ingestion service, event-based change detection, summary statistics, and forecasting, developed by KNT and supported by INLE. ▪ The ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ core operation is pattern matching and its implementation is inspired by the Aho-Corasick algorithm.

	<p>‘traditional’ SQL and non- graph NoSQL databases) to collect and use for evaluation, training, or as input for digital twin models, data that takes into consideration the geospatial dimension. Forecasting will take place both at the edge via computationally cheap pre-trained NN, and at the federal level using data summarized at the edge (e.g., via Dense NN) and retrieved via the graph network. This service will be applied in several pilots. For instance, in Pilot 5, each bike rental station can measure the number of available bikes and their type (electric or mechanical), providing summaries of usage, etc. Each bike can provide current position, speed, user, battery status if electric, etc. All rental stations and bikes are represented by nodes in the graph network, with the edge connecting each pair of nodes also providing the travelling-by-car time between the 2 points (i.e., traffic dependant). Similarly, on Pilot 4 a graph network could fuse all data received (meteorological sources, air/ground pollution maps, water quality, IoT devices) so that it can all be instantly retrievable from one service, with all queries able to consider the geospatial dimension in an efficient manner (e.g., water quality of corn plants being more than 10m away of nearest irrigation with a ground pollution level of X). Finally, concerning Pilot 6 graph databases have been used to tackle banking frauds (first-party bank fraud, insurance fraud, and e-commerce fraud), showcasing that graph databases can be very efficient in quickly detecting cases of fraud and elaborate fraud rings.</p>		
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1.2 Relationship to other Work Packages and Deliverables

WP3 is the innovation ‘backbone’ of the project, as the innovations within the pilots are organised in this package. WP3 services use the GREEN.DAT.AI infrastructure, including the Big Data Analytics (BDA) infrastructure and the Federated Data Sovereignty services, which is implemented within WP2. The efficiency of the WP3 services will be demonstrated by the WP4 taking into account the Macro Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) introduced in D1.1. D3.1 elaborates on technical requirements set in WP1-2, while also developing solutions guided by UC needs addressed in T1.1 and D4.7.

The present deliverable is related to D3.2, which will include the updated and final version of the WP3 services. Also, results of the first testing cycle that will consolidate feedback for fixes on the WP3 services will be reported on D4.8. Furthermore, D2.2 will deliver the integrated platform that unifies the different services developed in WP3, along with the Energy Efficiency Testing Framework, which will be utilised by WP3 services for energy demand measurement purposes, aiming to achieve a minimum 10% improvement in energy efficiency compared to baseline scenarios and metrics identified in D1.1.

1.3 Contribution to WP3 and Project Objectives

The present deliverable marks a significant milestone within WP3 of the GREEN.DAT.AI project, representing the culmination of efforts to develop innovative solutions for large-scale data analytics. This deliverable serves as the initial version of D3.2, outlining a pathway towards achieving MS2.

D3.1 emphasises MS2 within the GREEN.DAT.AI project, marking the preliminary integration of technical components as well as addressing GREEN.DAT.AI Objective 3 (O3) that is to develop novel Energy-Efficient Large-Scale Data Analytics Services including Federated Learning Services (FLS) and tools to support the deployment of operational solutions using the facilities developed in Objective 2 (O2). O2, closely aligned with WP2, provides the BDA infrastructure and tools to support dynamic data sharing in industrial ecosystems through the federation of services and the execution of distributed large scale data pipelines.

Moreover, D3.1 represents the first attempt to incorporate green-efficient dimensions into the developed services, underscoring the project's commitment to sustainability and environmental responsibility. Additionally, D3.1 marks the initial step towards addressing the Macro KPIs listed in D1.1, which encompass reducing energy consumption, minimising model size, optimising the ratio of model accuracy per power used for computation model, and enhancing overall model accuracy. By offering a comprehensive overview of the preliminary solutions developed within WP3, this deliverable lays the groundwork for further advancements and refinements in subsequent iterations, ultimately contributing to the overarching objectives of the GREEN.DAT.AI project.

1.4 Document Structure

This deliverable is organised into five sections, structured as follows:

- Section 1 serves as an introduction to the deliverable, documenting how the results of the deliverable and the related tasks (T3.1-T3.5) align with the project's Description of Action (DoA) and GA. It also provides an overview of the deliverable and its structure.
- Section 2 introduces each service developed, preliminary results, and future plans.
- Section 3 discusses the green dimension of the services.
- Section 4 demonstrates how the developed services align with GREEN.DAT.AI and presents how they can be interconnected to effectively address the objectives and meet the requirements of the GREEN.DAT.AI UCs.
- Section 5 concludes the deliverable and discusses future extensions.

2 Energy-Efficient Large-Scale Data Analytics Services

Within the context of WP3, this section unveils the services developed or currently under development to tackle the challenges of Energy-efficient Large-Scale Data Analytics. With the widespread integration of AI across various domains, successfully addressing the challenges posed by large-scale data analytics, it becomes imperative to innovate new AI solutions that effectively manage computational demands. By synthesising recent advancements and methodologies, the objective is to illuminate promising pathways towards achieving both analytical efficacy and energy efficiency.

Table 2.1 presents a comprehensive overview of all developed services, as well as those currently under development, categorised by task/subtask. Also, it includes links to both open and private repositories.

Table 2.1: List of services developed within WP3.

Task-Service	Repository-Link
Task 3.1 AI-enabled data enrichment and sharing - Synthetic data generation	
ST3.1.1 Efficient tools for data enrichment	
Data enrichment	https://github.com/greendatai-eu/ST3.1.1-data-enrichment
ST3.1.2 Incentive mechanisms for data anonymisation and sharing	
Data monetisation mechanisms for data sharing	https://github.com/greendatai-eu/ST3.1.2-data-monetization-mechanisms-for-data-sharing_
Data marketplaces using blockchain	https://github.com/greendatai-eu/ST3.1.2-data-marketplaces-using-blockchain_client https://github.com/greendatai-eu/ST3.1.2-data-marketplaces-using-blockchain_rest-api
ST3.1.3 Synthetic data generators	
Mobility trajectory data generation	https://github.com/greendatai-eu/ST3.1.3-mobility-trajectory-data-generation
Data generation - based on images	<i>*Under development/exploration</i>
Task 3.2 Large-scale learning at the edge/fog	
ST3.2.1 Large-scale time series analytics	
Trajectory-based battery consumption estimation	https://github.com/greendatai-eu/ST3.2.1-trajectory-based-battery-consumption-estimation
EV Transaction Data Forecasting	https://github.com/greendatai-eu/ST3.2.1-EV-transaction-data-forecast
Energy (demand/consumption) forecasting of charging stations using ANNs	<i>*Under development/exploration</i>
Charging station occupancy forecast	<i>*Under development/exploration</i>
ST3.2.2 Federated & Auto ML at the edge/fog	
Privacy-preserving FL	https://gitlab.inesc.tec.pt/cpes/european-projects/green-dat-ai/fl-wind-forecast <i>*Private GitLab repository, please contact INESC for access</i>
Algorithm Selection & Hyperparameter Tuning / AutoML	https://github.com/greendatai-eu/ST3.2.2-algorithm-selection-hyperparameter-tuning-autoML

Distributed optimisation at the edge	<i>*Under development/exploration</i>
ST3.2.3 Explainable AI /Feature Learning with Privacy Preservation	
Explainable feature learning	https://github.com/greendataai-eu/ST3.2.3-explainable-feature-learning
Interpretable Clustering	https://github.com/greendataai-eu/ST3.2.3-interpretable-clustering
Knowledge discovery tools on learned features	<i>*Under development/exploration</i>
T3.3 Federated & Automatic Transfer Learning	
(weighted) FL	https://github.com/greendataai-eu/T3.3-weighted-federated-learning
Geographical transfer learning	<i>*Under development/exploration</i>
T3.4 Adaptive FL for Digital Twin Applications	
Orchestration framework for derivation geospatial data products	https://github.com/greendataai-eu/T3.4-orchestration-framework-for-derivation-geospatial-data-products
Behaviour modelling pipelines	https://github.com/greendataai-eu/T3.4-behaviour-modeling-pipelines
Event detection on fused datasets	https://github.com/greendataai-eu/T3.4-event-detection-on-fused-datasets
T3.5 Automated IoT event-based change detection & forecasting	
Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox	http://greendataai.konnecta.io:3000/ <i>*Private GitLab repository, please contact KNT for access</i>
Accelerated Event Processing Engine	https://github.com/greendataai-eu/T3.5-accelerated-event-processing-engine <i>*Private GitHub repository, please contact TUC for access</i>

In summary, this section is organized into nine sections, each covering key aspects of the Energy-Efficient Large-Scale Data Analytics domain. Specifically, these sections correspond to six subtasks that make up the first two tasks of WP3, along with the three last tasks of WP3. Each of these sections provides descriptions of the services, preliminary evaluation results, and future plans.

2.1 AI-enabled data enrichment

Transforming disparate and heterogeneous data sources into a common schema, enables integrated and enriched views on data and extends the opportunities to advance the effectiveness and accuracy of data analysis and prediction tasks. This section briefly presents the data enrichment service.

2.1.1 Description of Data enrichment service

The semantic enrichment of data requires the use of a semantic model that provides the conceptualisation of the domain. This semantic model is typically defined as an RDFS/OWL ontology that may also reuse existing, well-established, higher-level ontologies. Subsequently, the process of data enrichment is performed by means of data transformation from diverse data sources and formats into Resource Description Framework (RDF) triples (refer to Appendix I for more details).

The data enrichment service is exploited for semantic annotation of data under a common schema. Semantics enable data interoperability and interlinking, i.e. establishing relations between resources described in data from different sources, which further enrich the data. Thus, data enrichment provides further opportunities to advance the accuracy of data analysis and prediction tasks. In this service any

ontology expressed in RDFS up to OWL2 can be exploited as the common schema describing the data. The given ontology provides the terms and semantics for the construction of a template used by RDF-Gen (refer to Appendix I for more details) to transform the data to RDF triples. RDF-Gen has been experimentally evaluated and compared to SotA related work on both archival and streaming data sources [1]. In this section, the key components and features are briefly presented.

2.1.1.1 Data enrichment service overall architecture

Figure 2.1, illustrates the overall RDF-Gen architecture, which comprises the data connector and the triple generator component. For each data source type and format, an individual data connector has been implemented, to allow seamless data access. For example, a CSV data connector can access data stored in a CSV file, a Kafka connector can consume data provided in a specific topic, etc. A common ground for all data connectors, however, is that they have to push the data to the triple generator component in a 'record-by-record' fashion, to decouple the Triple Generator from any format-specific constraints, as it provides the data in a unified form, regardless their original format. From a technical point of view, the data connector implements the methods required to access and iterate over the data at the source. Data in each record are organised as a vector of values regardless of the original format at the source.

The triple generator component is responsible for consuming the records and generating the corresponding triples according to a predefined triple template, i.e. a pattern of triples using the vocabulary of the given ontology, such that the generated triples are consistent to the ontology. The triple generator assigns the values in each record received, to the corresponding variables of the triple template and process any functions used in the template. The result will be a set of triples that enrich the data at the source using the semantics of the ontology.

The overall good performance of RDF-Gen lies on the simplicity of the process, and the record-by-record approach. In addition, parallel processing is achieved by design due to the independent processing of each record, which allows partitioning records across nodes that host different triple generator instances. The triple generator is also responsible for storing the output to either a local file in Terse RDF Triple Language (TTL) or uploading the triples to a triple store specified in the configuration. Uploading a triple store can become a bottleneck in the long run, thereby RDF-Gen by default employs batch uploading, where each batch of triples is assigned to an individual worker of a multithread process. The size of batches in terms of number of triples, is also specified in the configuration.

Figure 2.1: RDF-Gen architecture overview.

2.1.1.2 Data enrichment service configuration

The configuration of data enrichment service comprises a part which provides the connection settings for accessing the data at a data source, the triple template (used in RDF-Gen) describing how the data should be transformed into triples, and the output settings, specifying where the generated triples should be stored.

The current version of RDF-Gen includes a wide range of data connectors to enable data access on a large set of data sources and formats. From a technical point of view, each data connector implies different configuration settings. For example, a DBMS data connector should be configured with user credentials, host address/port, and at least an SQL query to be used for accessing the data. A CSV data connector should be configured by different settings, such as which columns should be accessed, which value separator character should be used and range of records to be accessed.

The first part of the configuration therefore is highly dependent on the type and format of the data at the source, and the data connector to be used. A triple generator on the other hand is configured by a vector of variables \mathbf{V} , a triple template \mathbf{G} , and a set of functions. The variables in \mathbf{V} correspond to the attributes of a record provided by the data connector. Formally, let \mathbf{I} , \mathbf{B} , and \mathbf{L} the pairwise disjoint infinite sets of URIs, blank nodes and literals, respectively. A triple $(s, p, o) \in (\mathbf{I} \cup \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{I} \times (\mathbf{I} \cup \mathbf{B} \cup \mathbf{L})$ is called an RDF triple, where s is the subject, p is the predicate and o is the object of the triple. \mathbf{V} is the infinite set of variables that is disjoint from the above sets. For example, the triple:

```
:Svn11_1 :hasPlaceName "Bled" .
```

has subject (s): $Svn11_1 \in \mathbf{I}$, predicate (p): $:hasPlaceName \in \mathbf{I}$ and object (o) “Bled” $\in \mathbf{L}$.

A variable $?x \in \mathbf{V}$ is said to be bound to a value $q \in \mathbf{I} \cup \mathbf{L}$ if, and only if, $bound(?x) = q$. Let \mathbf{F} be an infinite set of function names disjoint with \mathbf{I} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{L} , and \mathbf{V} . The functions \mathbf{F} available in the triple templates are distinguished to the resource functions, generating a resource from a set of bound variables, the triples functions, generating a (possibly empty) set of triples, and the literal functions computing literals from the bound variables. For example, in the following segment of a triple template:

```
...
assertSensorLocation(?Longitude,?Latitude,?Name) a :Location ;
  :hasGeometry makePointURI(?Latitude,?Longitude) .
position2geoSPARQL(?Latitude,?Longitude) .
assertSensorObject(?Longitude,?Latitude,?Name) a :Object ;
  :hasName asString(?Name) ;
  sosa:isHostedBy    assertSensorLocation(?Longitude,?Latitude,?Name) .
...

```

The functions `assertSensorLocation/3`, `makePointURI/2`, `assertSensorObject/3` are resource functions (generating a resource for the bound variables provided as arguments), the function `asString/1` is a literal function (returns the value bound to the variable `?Name` as `xsd:string`), and the function `position2geoSPARQL/2` is a triples function, generating the triples describing the point referenced by the given arguments in GeoSPARQL.

RDF-Gen can store generated output in a local TTL file, or upload triples to a triple store. Uploading the generated output to a triple store or writing to a Kafka topic, can be proved to be important features for data enrichment at the edge (i.e. the triple store can be any remote endpoint). These settings comprise the third and last part of the configuration. For example, a data source may report readings of weather condition sensors as a JSON object:

```
{"2016":
  {"1":
    {"1":
```

```
[{
  "Id":0,"StationId":44,"Datum":"2016-01-01T00:00:00",
  "AvgTemp":0.6, "MaxTemp":8.5,"MinTemp":-2.5,"AvgWindSpeed":0.0,
  "Pressure":null,"PrecipitationQunatity":0.0,"Clouds":67,
  "Humidity":56.0,"Storm":false,"Rain":false,"Hail":false,
  "Fog":false,"Snow":false,"Wind":0,"Latitude":45.75495966282086,
  "Longitude":13.84390506261774,"Name":"GODNJE"
}, ...]...
}...
}...
}
```

The following fragment of a triple template transforms the input data to RDF triples:

```
...
assertSensorLocation(?Longitude,?Latitude,?Name) a :Location;
:hasGeometry makePointURI(?Latitude,?Longitude) .
position2geoSPARQL(?Latitude,?Longitude) .
assertSensorObject(?Longitude,?Latitude,?Name) a :Object ;
:hasName asString(?Name) ;
sosa:isHostedBy assertSensorLocation(?Longitude,?Latitude,?Name) .
assertSensorProperty("AvgTemp") a sosa:ObservableProperty ;
rdfs:label "AvgTemp" ; rdfs:comment "Average air temperature".
...
assertObservation(?Longitude,?Latitude,?Name,?Datum,"AvgTemp") a
:Observation ;
:ObservedTimeStamp asUnixTime(?Datum) ;
:location assertSensorLocation(?Longitude,?Latitude,?Name) ;
sosa:madeBySensor assertSensorObject(?Longitude,?Latitude,?Name) ;
sosa:observedProperty assertSensorProperty("AvgTemp") ;
qudt-1-1:numericValue asDouble(?AvgTemp) .
...
```

The following fragment of the generated RDF triples describes the average air temperature (:ObservationProperty_13), reported by :sensor_0 at location :location_0 (namely 'Godnje' with position of reference 'POINT(13.84390506261774 45.75495966282086)', CRS:4326) at the observed timestamp '1451606400':

```
...
:location_0 a :Location ;
:hasGeometry :Point_13.84390506261774_45.75495966282086 .
:Point_13.84390506261774_45.75495966282086 a ogc:Geometry ;
ogc:asWKT
  "<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326> POINT(13.84390506261774
45.75495966282086)"^^ogc:wktLiteral ;
ogc:coordinateDimension 1 ; ogc:dimension 1 ;
ogc:is3D "false"^^xsd:boolean ; ogc:isEmpty "false"^^xsd:boolean ;
ogc:isSimple "true"^^xsd:boolean ; ogc:spatialDimension 0 .
:sensor_0 a :Object ;
:hasName "GODNJE" ;
sosa:isHostedBy :location_0 .
```

```

:ObservationProperty_13 a sosa:ObservableProperty ;
  rdfs:label "AvgTemp" ;
  rdfs:comment "Average air temperature".
:observation_1 a :Observation ;
  :ObservedTimeStamp "1451606400" ;
  :location :location_0 ;
  sosa:madeBySensor :sensor_0 ;
  sosa:observedProperty :ObservationProperty_13 ;
  qudt-1-1:numericValue "0.6"^^xsd:double .
...

```

The triple template used in this example imports terms from GeoSPARQL [ogc³](http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#), Semantic Sensor Network Ontology [sosa⁴](http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/) and Quantities, Units, Dimensions and Types ontology [qudt-1-1⁵](http://qudt.org/1.1/schema/qudt#).

2.1.2 Evaluation of Data enrichment service

The current version of the service has been tested using data by UC#4, to enrich sensor readings with contextual information and semantics. In this version, data enrichment service transforms the data into RDF triples and combines sensor readings with the Global Administrative Areas (GADM) at level 2 (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2: The Global Administrative Areas (GADM) of Slovenia at level 2 and location of sensors in the data sample evaluated (green dots)

To evaluate the energy-efficiency of this service, the data transformation of the GADM areas into RDF triples in GeoSPARQL format, was tested. To this end, the focus was to investigate the potential benefit in terms of energy consumed when the service is deployed on the edge, instead of using cloud resources. The evaluated data transformation task is a preliminary step towards enriching the sensor data with contextual information. The service has been deployed and evaluated both on (a) an Intel i7-10750H at 2.6GHz system and (b) a RaspberryPi3 (model B, 1.2GHz quad core ARM Cortex-A53). The experimental results have shown that the system (a) transformed the data in less than a second utilising approximately 20% of the CPU, while system (b) processed the data for 5 seconds at approximately 50% of the CPU. As expected, the system (a) can process

³ <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>

⁴ <http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/>

⁵ <http://qudt.org/1.1/schema/qudt#>

the data in considerably less time compared to (b). However, it can be noted that the power consumed by system (a) is approximately 12.57W, while for system (b) it varies from 1.15W (being idle) to 3.6W (at 100% of the quad core CPU). A rough estimation of the power consumed by the system (b) using only the 50% of the CPU in this experiment, is $(3.6-1.15)*0.5+1.15W = 2.375W$. The total energy consumed for the 5 seconds is $2.375*5 J = 11.88J$ which is less than the energy (12.57J) consumed by system (a) even though it utilised only 20% of the CPU for this experiment. These preliminary experimental results show that the service can be optimised with respect to the energy consumed.

2.1.3 Next steps

The next steps for the upcoming months, will focus on:

- a) evaluating the energy consumption of the data enrichment service when using data sets provided by different UCs. Such an evaluation can indicate any differences to the energy demand per type of data set.
- b) implementing optimisations on the data enrichment service operating at the edge with respect to the energy consumed and the processing time,
- c) extending the data enrichment service with ML-based algorithms for the interlinking of resources from different data sources. The current version of the service interlinks resources only via topological relations.

2.2 Incentive mechanisms for Data Anonymisation and Sharing

This section focuses on the services developed under the context of Subtask 3.1.2, aiming to encourage and facilitate data sharing between multiple data owners. Since data privacy enabled by FL variants may not be enough to incentivise data sharing, this section along with Section 2.5 focuses on mechanisms that allow knowledge sharing without compromising user privacy.

Incentive Mechanisms for Data Anonymisation and Sharing revolves around designing effective strategies to motivate individuals and organisations to anonymise and share their data. These mechanisms strike a balance between data privacy and benefits of data sharing, leveraging incentives such as financial rewards, access to proprietary algorithms or insights, and enhanced reputation. Interactions between data owners are made through a data market platform (implemented in a distributed ledger technology, specifically Internet Of Things Application (IOTA)) that orchestrates all processes, integrating a set of mathematical algorithms to ensure fair data exchange and compensations (refer to Appendix I for more details).

2.2.1 Description of data monetization mechanisms for data sharing service

The service comprises a collection of mathematical algorithms designed to facilitate interaction between data owners. These algorithms aim to create two primary incentives for data sharing:

- **Monetary incentive:** Data owners share their data and receive compensation if their data contributes to solving regression tasks. Conversely, they pay for data from others when needed for their own tasks. GREEN.DAT.AI will demonstrate the data auction solutions and platform prototype of past projects such as H2020 Smart4RES with UC#1 data.
- **Non-monetary incentive:** Data owners exchange data without money involved, data owners agree to share and receive data of similar value.

Interactions between data owners are made through a data market platform using blockchain service that orchestrates all processes (refer to Appendix I for more details on data markets). A brief description of the main algorithms is provided next.

2.2.1.1 Monetary incentives

The initial algorithmic solution builds upon the solution outlined by Gonçalves et al. [2] and is called a zero-regret auction mechanism. In this mechanism, only data buyers express their preferences for data price. Suppose that N agents want to collaborate to generate predictions, at a certain time, to predict. Then, the following steps occur in sequence (for simplicity data owners are assumed buyers and sellers):

1. the market operator opens a session and inform about the market price (p), that reflects how much an agent should pay per 1% improvement (e.g., RMSE improvement) in point forecasting accuracy
2. data owners submit their data (covariates $\{\mathbf{X}_{n,t}\}_{t=1}^{T+H}$ and target $\{Y_{n,t}\}_{t=1}^T$) and inform the auto price they are willing to pay (b_n) per 1% improvement in forecasting accuracy of their target. A maximum payment \bar{b}_n is also submitted to avoid extremely high prices
3. the market operator closes the session
4. for each data buyer n , the market operator allocates all available features to $\{Y_{n,t}\}_{t=T+1}^{T+H}$:
 - a. if $b_n < p$, the market penalizes the buyer by adding random noise to the market data (proportionally to the deviation between b_n and p)
 - b. the allocated data is used to train a forecasting model (e.g., a Gradient Boosting Tree)
 - c. the data submitted by buyer is used to train a forecasting model (e.g., a Gradient Boosting Tree)
 - d. the accuracy of both methods is compared to estimate the gain attained by the buyer when using collaborative forecasting
 - e. if collaboration leads to an improvement (I) in forecasting accuracy, the data buyer should pay $I \times b_n$
 - f. if $I \times b_n > \bar{b}_n$ then data market operator repeats a.-f., adding random noise in step a., until $I \times b_n \leq \bar{b}_n$. (this means that maximum payment is not enough to buy the best model and therefore a worse model is considered that respects such restriction)
 - g. the buyer pays $I \times b_n$
 - h. the buyer receives the forecasts
 - i. the relevance of each feature in the forecasting model is estimated (Shapley values) and the payment $I \times b_n$ is divided by data owners proportionally
5. based on improvements and buyers' bids, the market operator updates the price for the next session.
6. repeat 1-5

While the previous solution represents a significant advancement for data markets in regression tasks, it suffers from the drawback that data sellers are not empowered to establish their preferences concerning data pricing. In the context of GREEN.DAT.AI other solutions will be developed. The proposal involves the estimation of collaborative forecasting models, considering that data owners define their value function for such models along with the minimum amount of compensation they expect (represented by \underline{p}_n) if their data contribute to enhancing others' forecasting models and the maximum price they are willing to pay (denoted by \bar{p}_n) if there are beneficial collaborative data available to them.

The formulation aims to maximise the sum of all value functions (**social welfare maximisation auction mechanism**) while ensuring the minimum and maximum acceptable prices, as depicted in Figure 2.3. Initial tests were conducted by assuming a linear collaborative forecasting model. The value function of the buyers is related to the relative error improvement of the collaborative model when compared to a model fed with

local data, while the value function of data sellers is related to the coefficients of the model (and the corresponding prices). In this way, while maximising social welfare, the linear collaborative forecasting model (data allocation and coefficients) and data prices are optimised.

Figure 2.3: Social welfare auction mechanism: an overview.

2.2.1.2 Non-monetary incentives

As in the previous incentive, suppose that N agents want to exchange data aiming to obtain, at a certain time T , data useful to $predict T + 1, T + 2, \dots, T + H$. Then, the following steps occur in sequence:

1. the market operator opens a session
2. data owners submit their data (covariates and target times series)
3. the market operator closes the session
4. the market operator performs feature engineering (e.g., lags of time series)
5. for each data owner, the market operator:
 - a. estimates the value of the data available in the market (e.g., mutual information between data owner's target and the features from the other data owners)
6. the market operator uses the estimated value to allocate data: a linear programming problem is solved that optimises the overall values allocation subject to the fact that each data owners should receive and share data of comparable value
7. agents receive the allocated data/ forecasts generated with allocated data
8. repeat 1-7

2.2.2 Evaluation of data monetization mechanisms for data sharing service

The algorithms under development are being initially validated, mainly using synthetic data to ensure the algorithms are correctly implemented and behave as expected.

Monetary incentives > Social Welfare Maximisation. Table 2.2 summarises the results for 3 synthetic case-studies, assuming 100 features are available in the market. The real model is:

$$y = -20.8x_1 - 2.8x_2 - 106.8x_3 + 82.0x_4 - 89.7x_5,$$

where features are generated from a Gaussian distribution with zero mean and unitary standard deviation. The collaborative model is a linear regression, the value function of data buyers is the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) of the collaborative model, and the value function for data sellers relates to the coefficients and prices. When faced with budget constraints (case #3) the algorithm correctly selects the most relevant information. For the cases where the maximum buyer budget is enough to buy

all relevant features (cases #1 and #2), the magnitude of their contribution to the collaborative forecasting model clearly affects the final revenues for data sellers.

Table 2.2: Illustration of the results for a simple synthetic dataset (social welfare mechanism).

	Case #1	Case #2	Case #3
Sellers: minimum acceptable price	0	0	2
Buyer: maximum acceptable price	10	40	5
Allocated model	$-20.8x_1 - 2.8x_2$ $- 106.8x_3 + 82.0x_4$ $- 89.7x_5$	$-20.8x_1 - 2.8x_2$ $- 106.8x_3 + 82.0x_4$ $- 89.7x_5$	$-96.26x_3$ $- 80x_5$
Revenue per feature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • x_1: 1.38 • x_2: 0.01 • x_3: 3.02 • x_4: 2.75 • x_5: 2.84 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • x_1: 5.72 • x_2: 3.63 • x_3: 7.36 • x_4: 7.10 • x_5: 7.19 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • x_3: 2.59 • x_5: 2.41

Non-monetary incentive > data-by-data exchange. 5 data owners are assumed to participate in the data-by-data market, each of them owns 100 covariates and 1 target feature. Figure 2.4 illustrates the results when relation between data is linear. The value of data is measured through the Spearman partial correlation, and the results emphasize the need to remove irrelevant relations before solving the allocation problem. Additionally, experiments were conducted under assumptions of nonlinearity, revealing suboptimal allocation outcomes. This underscores the necessity for employing more versatile metrics like conditional mutual information to enhance allocation accuracy.

Figure 2.4: Illustration of the results for a simple synthetic dataset (data-by-data mechanism).

2.2.3 Description of data marketplaces using blockchain service

The Predico data marketplace (architecture depicted in Figure 2.5) makes use in its core of a public Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) and a self-prorietary algorithmic solution to compute potential rewards from data provided by market participants for time series forecast computations. The DLT chosen for the Marketplace was Internet Of Things Application (IOTA). The current IOTA DLT technology excels in transaction speed and costs (feeless). Current and future developments are also desirable since they aim to offer data stream technology for IoT devices, which can be particularly useful for further automation in the energy sector along with smart contract developments.

When registering in the marketplace, a user account is created in the central Server, and a local encrypted wallet to manage the DLT native token is generated for the participant in its local computer (Desktop Application/Predico REST client). The wallet software available in the project is based on encrypted and

secure open-source software released by the DLT provider, which is compatible with the most known cryptocurrency exchanges worldwide.

Figure 2.5. Architecture of the Predico data marketplace.

Once registered, the market participant's unique wallet address is provided to the Server, and users can start uploading energy production data (e.g., time series) through structured CSV or JSON files in the data section of the Desktop application or by scheduling automatic uploads from querying local or remote sources through configurable FTP/SFTP/SCP or WebDAV protocols in the Desktop Application or by leveraging the Predico REST client⁶ automation capabilities for a more custom implementation.

Market sessions, when available, provide a solution for potential forecast buyers to bid for accurate forecasts with data supplied by sellers. The solution found to bind buyers was to provide a Market Wallet managed by the Data Market Platform where all the potential buyers will bind their bid with a max payment transfer of an amount they are prepared to spend. Once the Market Engine computes the forecasts, they will become available to each resource the user may have configured in his account.

Additionally, the platform empowers clients to design and develop personalised client applications to communicate with the Data Marketplace REST API. These tailor-made applications facilitate the automation of essential functions, including uploading and downloading data and submitting bids in sessions. The system aims to maximise operational efficiency by providing this possibility to clients. To further support the development, the platform provides a REST client API, that simplifies the management and transfer of data and tokens to the Data Marketplace, enhancing the overall developer and user experience. This includes a Sandbox environment allowing clients to experiment and refine their applications in a safe, controlled setting before interacting with the Data Marketplace in production.

The sessions, forecasts, and revenues to data providers are generated and computed by the Data Market Platform Backoffice, supported by a Cassandra Database Cluster for highly scalable data timeseries throughput and a Postgres Relational Database for market sessions and user account preferences management. Since the number of users and data to compute can scale to large numbers, a RabbitMQ message queue system is deployed to distribute computational jobs over multiple computers assigned to tasks that can be easily added to the overall effort if required.

The interactions between data owners and application of the incentive mechanisms developed are made through a data market platform (data marketplaces using blockchain service) that orchestrates all the

processes. The data market platform is implemented in distributed IOTA technology, IOTA, and the main components are illustrated in Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6. Data Market Platform - components and interactions.

Data owners have a client API that allows them to authenticate in the market, share data, make bids, and analyse the outcomes from each forecasting session. The market operator also has an API that integrates all the necessary functionalities, including data storage and the required mathematical algorithms to estimate models, generate forecasts, allocate fair prices, etc. The IOTA cryptocurrency serves as the payment infrastructure in this context. All value transactions use the native cryptocurrency MIOTA and are permanently documented and accessible to the public on the IOTA network.

The current prototype available on GitHub⁶ has integrated the monetary incentive described in Section 2.2.1.1 but it will be extended to support the other incentives as well. In what follows a summary of the functionalities and characteristics of each component illustrated in Figure 2.6 is provided.

2.2.3.1 Data flows and interactions

The data marketplace platform offers clients multiple methods for contributing data, enabling them to choose between manual input via a dedicated Desktop Application or automated data transfers (Figure 2.7) through tailored custom binaries and scripts publicly available, allowing agents to configure their data contribution and management preferences.

Figure 2.7. Available interactions with the Data Market for the transfer of data.

The Data Marketplace platform encompasses a diverse range of data types, specifically tailored to meet the needs of the energy domain. For example, energy production timeseries related datasets, which serve as the foundation for accurate and reliable forecasting and analysis. It is designed to accommodate future

⁶ <https://github.com/CPES-Power-and-Energy-Systems/data-sharing-barter-incentives-client>

expansion and integration of other relevant data types such as solar irradiance, wind speed, temperature, and potentially other environmental or operational factors that may impact energy production. The inclusion of these additional data types will further enhance the forecast platform's capabilities and enable users to access a comprehensive set of information for advanced forecasting and analysis.

2.2.3.2 Agent Market Interface

Registration. Users are required to provide essential information such as their email address, and password. This information serves as the foundation for authenticating and authorising users' access to the platform. In addition to the registration process, the Data Marketplace offers the instant creation of a blockchain cryptocurrency wallet. Such wallet provides users with a secure and decentralised storage for their digital tokens, essential to collect revenues or execute transactions within the Market.

Portfolio management. It involves the creation, organisation, and monitoring of data resources to optimise their value and effectiveness in the marketplace. Agents can dynamically manage their portfolio of resources, which may include energy production data, forecasts, and other relevant data sources. They can create and define their data resources, assign metadata (name and data upload instructions), and organise their resources based on different criteria, such as energy source, location, or market sector. Agents can also monitor the performance and usage of their resources within the marketplace. This includes tracking the number of data downloads, bids made, and revenue generated from their resources. Agents may also use the information to make informed decisions about their portfolio and optimise their participation in the marketplace.

Figure 2.8: Home dashboard of the application

Participation in market sessions. Agents can submit bids for forecasting services, and potentially engage in the buying and selling of data resources in further developments. For now, agents can only participate in market sessions, which are time-limited periods during which the biddings occur. These sessions provide agents with functionalities to submit their bids and explore potential opportunities to improve their forecasts. When participating in the marketplace, agents can submit bids for forecasting services. Bids involve specifying the value they are willing to pay for obtaining a potential more accurate and reliable forecast for their specific data resources. By participating in the bidding process, agents express

their interest and commitment which has links to smart contracts agreements. Agents market participation also encompasses sharing data production resources within the marketplace. Agents can contribute with their data, allowing other participants to access and use the valuable information they may provide for a Forecast result. Additionally, agents may explore and acquire in the future data resources from other participants to augment their own datasets and improve the forecasting capabilities of their own. By actively participating in the marketplace, agents contribute to the collaborative and dynamic nature of the platform, fostering knowledge sharing, innovation, and the development of more accurate and reliable energy forecasts.

Figure 2.9: Forecasts computed by the Data Market.

Figure 2.10: Data upload preferences and measurements home section (a).

Data upload. Agents can securely upload their measurements, (e.g.: solar or wind energy production data), to contribute to the collaborative forecasting and analysis within the platform and receiving a financial benefit from it. The uploaded measurements serve as valuable input for the forecasting algorithms and collaborative techniques used within the Data Marketplace forecast operations.

Figure 2.11: Data upload preferences and measurements home section (b).

Figure 2.12: Agent wallet.

Local Cryptocurrency Wallet. It is a built-in feature within the desktop app that allows market agents to securely store and manage their cryptocurrency assets. Cryptocurrency wallets are used to hold the digital tokens required for participating in financial transactions within the Data Marketplace, such as bidding, payment (revenue), or fund management. The Local Cryptocurrency Wallet provides a convenient and secure

solution for market agents to store their cryptocurrency assets locally on their devices, ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of their funds.

Forecasts’ download. The forecasts for the agent’ time series data can be downloaded in various formats, including CSV or JavaScript Object Notation (JSON), allowing an easy integration with different applications and analysis tools. Agents may also specify the desired forecast duration and granularity to align with their specific needs and requirements.

2.2.3.3 Market Engine

The Market Engine serves as the ‘brain’ that orchestrates and manages the various functions and processes within the Data Marketplace related to market sessions, bid validation, data validation, collaborative forecasting, and revenue distribution. It ensures the smooth operation of the marketplace, promotes fairness and transparency, and facilitates effective collaboration among agents to maximise the value and benefits derived from the marketplace ecosystem.

Market session management. The Market Engine is responsible for managing market sessions within the Data Marketplace. Market sessions refer to specific time periods during which users can participate in the marketplace by submitting their bids. The Market Engine handles the scheduling, initiation, and termination of market sessions, ensuring that they occur at predetermined intervals and provide users with the opportunity to engage in trading activities. It also enforces rules and regulations related to session duration, participant eligibility, and other parameters set by the marketplace administrators.

Agents’ bids validation. Agents are required to send funds to the market wallet (owned by the Market Operator) as a demonstration of their commitment and financial capability to participate in the bidding process. By sending funds to the Market Wallet, agents provide a unique transaction identifier that is stored in the intended session and later validated by the market engine, granting the agent’s bid valid if the unique transaction identifier is available in the Market Wallet and the fund amounts are correct.

Figure 2.13: Bid validation process.

Secure Fund Management. It leverages the inherent security features of the underlying technology, such as cryptographic encryption and distributed ledger technology, to safeguard the funds and maintain their integrity throughout the bidding process. This ensures that funds are protected from unauthorized access or tampering.

Bid Validation. By utilising the blockchain Market Wallet for bid validation, the Data Marketplace promotes transparency in the bidding process. Participants in the Data Marketplace can verify the existence of funds and transactions in the Market Wallet since the Blockchain technology is open to anyone to explore. This transparency enhances trust and accountability among users, as they can assess the financial commitment of other participants and make informed decisions during the bidding process.

Payment Function. In addition to bid validation, the Market Wallet facilitates the payment function within the Data Marketplace. Once a bid is successfully accepted, and a transaction is finalized, the funds held in the Market Wallet are used for payment disbursement to the relevant parties, such as data providers or forecasting service providers. The Market Wallet ensures a secure process for transferring funds between buyers and sellers, facilitating smooth financial transactions within the marketplace leveraging the public DLT infrastructure.

Collaborative forecasting. It involves leveraging the collective data contributions from multiple agents to generate accurate and reliable forecasts. The Market Engine combines the shared production data, applies advanced forecasting algorithms and techniques, and produces forecasts that reflect the aggregated knowledge and insights of the participating agents. Collaborative forecasting enables agents to benefit from a broader and more diverse dataset, leading to improved forecasting accuracy and enhanced decision-making in energy management.

Revenue definition and distribution. The Market Engine also plays a role in defining and distributing revenue within the Data Marketplace. It determines the pricing mechanisms, possible fee structures, and revenue sharing models that govern the collaborative data transactions and distribution of buyer's funds. The Market Engine ensures that revenue generated from bid acceptances, data sales, and other marketplace activities is allocated and distributed to the relevant parties, such as data providers and the marketplace operators. It enforces the defined revenue distribution rules, tracks financial transactions, and facilitates secure and transparent payment processes.

2.2.3.4 Running the Service

This section focuses on the operational aspects of running the data marketplace service. It covers the perspectives of different users involved in the process: regular users, developers, and system administrators (Market Operators).

Desktop application. from a regular user perspective, getting started with the data marketplace service involves signing up for an account on the Desktop Application. Once registered, agents can access the user-friendly Desktop Application to configure their personal settings, check their data contributions, forecasts and data revenues.

Developers. Deploying the PREDICO REST client⁶ serves as a step to facilitate the interaction with the Data Marketplace API server⁷. This tool equips developers with a versatile suite of functionalities, empowering them to execute a wide spectrum of operations programmatically. Moreover, the availability of binary executables (such as '.exe' or '.sh' files) further enhances efficiency by enabling automated tasks like data uploads and session bindings to less advanced users. This integration enables developers to design and implement custom data analysis workflows, optimise data retrieval processes, and facilitate collaborative forecasting efforts. As a result, the data marketplace becomes an integral component of their application ecosystem, driving innovation and enhancing productivity.

System administrator (Market Operator). For system administrators responsible for running the data marketplace platform, deployment is simplified using Docker containers. The platform can be set up following a series of steps to ensure smooth operation and scalability. These steps encompass containerising the necessary components, such as the backend infrastructure, database, and any additional services. By

⁷ <https://github.com/CPES-Power-and-Energy-Systems/data-sharing-barter-incentives-rest-api>

using Docker, system administrators can easily ensure a deploy consistency across different environments, facilitating efficient management and maintenance of the data marketplace platform.

The following steps outline the process:

1. **Docker Setup:** Docker must be installed and properly configured on the deployment environment. Docker provides containerisation technology, allowing for consistent and portable deployment across different environments.
2. **Containerisation:** Each component of the data marketplace service should be containerised using Docker. This involves creating Docker containers for the Django application, PostgreSQL database, and Cassandra database. Docker containers encapsulate the necessary dependencies and configurations, providing a standardized and isolated environment for each component.
3. **Docker Compose:** Docker Compose, a tool for defining and managing multi-container Docker applications, can be used to orchestrate the deployment of data marketplace service. A Docker Compose file must be created, specifying configuration of the containers, networks, and volumes.
4. **Service Configuration:** The Docker Compose file should be configured to include the necessary services and their dependencies as previously stated. Services should be defined for the Django application, PostgreSQL database, Cassandra database, and any other required components such as load balancers or reverse proxies that may be added.
5. **Networking:** The networking within the Docker Compose file should be configured to allow communication between the different containers. Network aliases or bridge networks can be specified to enable seamless connectivity between the Django application and the databases.
6. **Environment Variables:** Environment variables should be set up within the Docker Compose file or using an environment file to provide necessary configuration parameters such as database credentials, API keys, and other service-specific settings.
7. **Deployment:** The data marketplace service can be deployed using the Docker Compose command. This command creates and starts the containers based on the configuration specified in the Docker Compose file. Docker Compose handles the initialisation and networking of the containers, ensuring they are interconnected and operational.
8. **Monitoring and Logging:** Monitoring and logging solutions should be implemented to track the performance and health of the deployed containers. Tools such as Docker logs, container monitoring systems, or application performance monitoring (APM) platforms can be utilised to gather insights and diagnose any issues.
9. **Continuous Integration and Deployment (CI/CD):** Not required but highly advised setting up a CI/CD pipeline to automate the build, testing, and deployment of the data marketplace service using Docker. This ensures a consistent and reliable release cycle, streamlining the development and deployment process.

2.2.4 Evaluation of data marketplaces using blockchain service

All algorithms under development are being initially validated using synthetic data to ensure the market is correctly implemented and behaves as expected.

The current data marketplace is at a mature development stage, around TRL 5. The platform is undergoing extensive development, testing and refinement to ensure its functionality, reliability, and usability. The core features and functionalities have been implemented and validated through multiple iterations and in-house case studies. The platform is currently in an automated testing environment with a set of mocking agents - including energy providers and forecast buyers. For the near future, we anticipate reaching TRL 6. This will

involve further scalability improvements, performance optimisations and integration with additional data sources and partners. It is important to note that the current Data Marketplace operates in a traditional server-client architecture. However, our future development is focused on integrating the system with the GREEN.DAT.AI common Data Space, which will bring additional capabilities and improve the overall functionality and security of the platform.

Figure 2.14: Overview architecture and available interactions for the transfer of data.

The data marketplace is built on a robust and scalable software stack that uses a combination of third-party software and custom-built components. The key software details include:

1. **Programming language:** The platform is primarily developed using Python, a versatile and widely adopted programming language for data analysis and web development.
2. **Frontend framework:** The frontend application is developed using JavaScript and the React framework. JavaScript provides the foundation for dynamic and interactive web interfaces, while React offers a component-based approach for building reusable and responsive user interfaces.
3. **Electron:** The data marketplace frontend also uses Electron, a framework for building cross-platform desktop applications using web technologies. Electron enables the development of desktop client applications using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, allowing for seamless integration with the data marketplace's functionalities.
4. **Backend framework:** Django, a powerful web framework for Python, is utilised to develop the application's backend infrastructure and APIs. Django provides a comprehensive set of tools and features for building robust and scalable web applications. It offers a high-level of abstraction, facilitating rapid development and seamless integration with various components of the application.
5. **Database:** The platform employs a combination of databases to handle different types of data. PostgreSQL is used as a reliable and robust relational database management system for storing and managing various data, including user information, resources, and transaction records. Additionally, Cassandra, a highly scalable and distributed database, is used to handle large volumes of data coming from energy providers. Cassandra's distributed architecture allows efficient storage and retrieval of large volumes of data, making it suitable for handling high-volume data generated by RES.
6. **Docker:** The platform is containerised using Docker, which allows for easy deployment, scalability, and portability across different environments. Docker enables efficient management of dependencies and simplifies the deployment process for the platform.
7. **Job scheduling:** To automate various data-related tasks and ensure timely updates, the platform uses job scheduling tools like Celery, facilitating the scheduling and execution of periodic collaborative forecasting processes, and other background tasks such as user and email and logging notifications.

8. **Licensing:** The third-party software components used in the platform adhere to their respective licenses, including open-source licenses such as MIT, Apache, and GNU GPL. We ensure compliance with license requirements and promote the use of open-source software within our platform.

2.2.5 Next steps

Regarding market mechanisms, the next steps for each component are summarised as follows:

- **Monetary incentives:**
 - Extension of social welfare maximisation solution to deal with complex models such as NNs
 - Evaluation with synthetic and real data
 - Demonstration with data from Pilot 1
- **Non-monetary incentives:**
 - Improvement of the computational complexity and evaluation of different metrics to measure data value
 - Evaluation with synthetic and real data
 - Demonstration with data from Pilot 1
- **Data market platform:**
 - External library is no longer supported by the IOTA foundation and adaptations are required
 - Integration of the new incentive mechanisms in the server API
 - Demonstration with data from Pilot 1

For the data marketplace, the following steps will be taken:

- **Scalability and performance:**
 - Test scenarios with greater volumes of data and a higher number of agents
 - Implement strategies such as horizontal scaling, load balancing, and caching mechanisms
- **Privacy and security:**
 - Explore possibilities for data breach and employ preserving techniques
- **User interface:**
 - Include user feedback in the loop for an iterative refinement of the user experience
- **Data spaces:**
 - Work on data synchronization, advanced data sharing options, and collaborative forecasting features through the GREEN.DAT.AI data space connector

2.3 Synthetic Data Generators

Synthetic data can provide support for testing and tuning analytical algorithms as well as the performances of data management tools and communication infrastructures, allowing to simulate specific scenarios and different loads of data. In the context of GREEN.DAT.AI activities, the need for synthetic mobility data emerged clearly, especially within UC#2, where the mobility traces of EVs will be part of the recharge station management application. Synthetic mobility traces are requested as they capture the mobility history of a user, later to be used for helping the prediction of recharge times and energy demand at the recharge points. To this end, a service has been developed to reproduce the whole mobility history of a user within a given time period, trying to capture realistic mobility behaviours and daily mobility demand. Mobility data generation is typically addressed from three different perspectives, depending on the mobility component of interest: flows, trajectories, and individual mobility (refer to Appendix I for more details).

2.3.1 Description of Mobility trajectory data generation (IMN-cloning Car Trajectory Synthesis) service

The tool stems from the observation that presently a relative abundance of mobility data sources is available, also at the level of individual trajectories, both as private and open data. For the latter class, it is mentioned:

- Microsoft’s GeoLife dataset⁸
- Hunan University dataset⁹
- Wejo Connected Vehicle Trajectories¹⁰
- Milan 2007 semi-synthetic dataset¹¹

This availability of real data allows to rephrase the synthetic mobility data generation into a mobility transfer problem from a source geographical area (where real data are available) to a target one (where synthetic data needs to be generated).

2.3.1.1 Overview of the process

The generation process is composed of various steps: first, the input mobility data is processed to extract the Individual Mobility Network (IMN) of the user, thus identifying the locations visited and their timing; the locations are mapped to the road network of the target area, preserving the intra-location distances in an approximate way; at the same time, the original trips schedule is perturbed by changing the stay times at locations; each trip between locations is processed through routing functions to find the fastest path; the resulting path and the updated time schedule are combined to produce trajectory data, in the same format as the input. The process is summarised in the following figure.

Figure 2.15: Overview of the process IMN

2.3.1.2 Extraction of Individual Mobility Network (IMN) and trips schedule

An IMN describes the individual mobility of a user through a graph representation of her locations and movements, grasping the relevant properties and removing unnecessary details. Given a user u , we indicate with $G_u = (L_u, M_u)$ her IMN, where L_u is the set of nodes, each representing a spatial location where the user stopped in their history, and M_u is the set of edges, each representing the trips connecting two locations in the user’s history. For nodes and edges, we compute several aggregates: for each node (location) l in L_u we compute the number of trips in H_u reaching location l ; an aggregation (mean, variance etc.) of the durations

⁸ <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/download/details.aspx?id=52367>

⁹ <https://github.com/HunanUniversityZhuXiao/PrivateCarTrajectoryData>

¹⁰ <https://data.cdrc.ac.uk/dataset/wejo-connected-vehicle-trajectories>

¹¹ https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/ResourceCatalogue/gps_track_milan_italy

of stops in l ; an aggregation of arrival times of trips reaching l ; an aggregation of durations of trips reaching l ; an aggregation of lengths of trips reaching l . The same computations are also defined on edges (movements) in M_u in a similar way.

The nodes in L_u are locations that represent a group of stop points, and edges in M_u are movements that represent groups of similar trips between two locations. Given the user's individual mobility history, the IMN G_u is obtained by retrieving the locations L_u through a spatial clustering-based aggregation of stop points [3], and the movements M_u by grouping the trips between any pair of locations [4].

Once the locations of the IMN have been computed, the trips' schedule is obtained by simply associating each starting and ending point of trips with the corresponding locations, together with their start time.

2.3.1.3 Distance-preserving locations remapping

The objective of the mapping phase is to associate each location in the source IMN to a point in the target area, in such a way that the relations between locations existing in the first can still hold in the second. The main criteria adopted in doing that is to keep the mutual distances similar. To achieve that, each location L_i in the IMN is mapped into a node N_i of the road network in the target area, aiming to minimise the RMSE among the node-to-node distances:

$$\{N_i\}_i = \arg \min_{\{N_i\}_i} RMSE(\{N_i\}_i) = \arg \min_{\{N_i\}_i} \sqrt{\frac{1}{N^2} \sum_{L_i, L_j \in IMN} (d(L_i, L_j) - d(N_i, N_j))^2}$$

where $d(.,.)$ is computed as the geographical distance between locations using the Haversine function, and N is the number of locations in the source IMN. Computing the optimal mapping is an intractable problem, due to the exponential number of combinations to try, thus we developed a greedy approach that takes into consideration a number of UC requirements and commonsense properties of IMNs: first, locations of IMNs are sorted by visit frequency, and in the vast majority of cases that means that L_0 corresponds to the user's home location and L_1 to the workplace; second, we allow to fix a priori the target nodes corresponding to either L_0 (thus N_0) or L_1 (N_1) or both; finally, the impact of a mapping error on higher-frequency locations (corresponding to those with smaller index 'i') is likely to be much larger than an error on low-frequency ones. Thus, the following simple greedy procedure to map locations is applied:

1. Repeat for $j = 1, \dots, K$:
 - a. If N_0 is not fixed then randomly choose N_0
 - b. If N_1 is not fixed then randomly choose N_1
 - c. $d_j =$ Haversine distance between N_0 and N_1
2. $(N_0, N_1) = \operatorname{argmin} |d(L_0, L_1) - d_j|$
3. Repeat for $i = 2, \dots, n$:
 - a. Repeat for $j = 1, \dots, K$:
 - i. Randomly choose N^*_j
 - ii. $RMSE(N^*_j) = RMSE(\{N_0, \dots, N_{i-1}, N^*_j\})$
 - b. $N_i = \operatorname{argmin} RMSE(N^*_j)$

Basically, the procedure maps the source locations in (descending) order of frequency, each time aiming to only minimise the RMSE only of the locations mapped so far. While in principle all possible node assignments for each L_i could be assessed, this step was simplified by choosing K random nodes. That not only significantly speeds up the computation, but also implicitly introduces a perturbation in node-to-node distances that is beneficial to privacy preservation, since a perfect mapping would allow to re-identify the source IMN among those given as input.

2.3.1.4 Trip schedule generation

The original trips schedule is translated to a sequence of pairs of locations together with a stay time. The locations are those corresponding to the start and end points in the original mobility dataset, and the stay time is similarly inferred from the sequence of original trips as difference between the end of a trip and the start of another one. To introduce some variability in the output, the stay time is randomly perturbed by adding a value sampled from a uniform random distribution ranging between -20% and +20% of the original stay time (such percentage is an input parameter of the tool).

The schedule above is then used as basis to generate the trips that are passed to the next phase (the routing) which will provide the trajectory needed to move from one node to the other and, more importantly for the current step, the corresponding trip duration. The exact time of start/end of trips, then, is obtained summing up the stay times and the trip durations at each step of the process. Notice that the time of the very first trip of the sequence is directly taken from the input dataset.

2.3.1.5 Routing

Routing takes care of finding the optimal path over the target area that connects the starting node to the ending one. This is done choosing the fastest path computed over the OpenStreetMap road network exploiting information about the speed limits over each road (notice that such information is typically approximate). The result of the operation is a sequence of points corresponding to the nodes and edges traversed along the path. To produce a trajectory in a GPS-like format as the input dataset, the previous output is translated by (i) extracting the longitude and latitude of each node traversed, and (ii) estimating the travel time between each pair of nodes, and thus computing the timestamp to assign to each node in the sequence. Clearly, in the real-world travel times are subject to several factors that might reduce the actual speeds along road segments. Our tool allows to rescale estimate speeds at the granularity of the single trip, which might be used to adapt them to expected traffic conditions, e.g. reducing all speeds during peak hours. As mentioned above, the trip duration is used in the trips schedule generation and added to the stay times to reproduce the complete timeline of trip starts and arrivals.

2.3.2 Evaluation of Mobility trajectory data generation (IMN-cloning Car Trajectory Synthesis) service

Evaluating a synthetic data generator tool is a difficult task, since it requires a precise, mathematically defined notion of what is a good dataset. This notion is typically not available, and thus it is just approximated by a set of indicators and end-user subjective validations. Since in GREEN.DAT.AI the end-users are indeed part of the consortium, the human validation of the output was emphasised, generating various segments of data and asking an evaluation from them in terms of (i) realism of the data, exploiting their knowledge of the geographical area where data are generated, and (ii) data utility, making reference to the UC involved.

2.3.2.1 Experimental setup

The trajectory data generation was developed for the needs of UC#2, led by the INESC TEC partner, related to the management of EV charging facilities. The general objective is to predict what is the battery status (namely, the amount of charge left) of customers when they connect to the recharge station, since that is fundamental to better plan the usage of energy resources Task 2.2 involves the crowdsourcing of trajectory data of individuals (the customers) to be used to estimate their battery consumption. Synthetic data is aimed to simulate the mobility of such users, to help developing the prediction tools, tuning the models and stress-testing the overall system. This is particularly important, since crowdsourced data will be available later in the project, and thus synthetic data will provide a replacement to speed up the development till then.

The UC#2 scenario currently involves INESC TEC employees since the recharge facility under monitoring is accessible only internally by the institution staff. For this reason, the tests performed with our IMN-cloning data generation will fix the work location (L_1) to the INESC TEC campus in Porto, Portugal.

As source IMNs, those computed in Nanni et al. [5] are exploited, consisting of 1000 users in the Italian Tuscany region. IMNs are computed over periods of two months, yet in these experiments the mobility of two weeks (March 5th-19th, 2017) was reproduced.

2.3.2.2 Location mapping tests

Location mapping is the most critical phase of the whole process, as it must provide a reasonable spatial distribution of stops, and its output can heavily impact also on the temporal distribution, since very different distances can result in too long/short travel times and thus significantly shift all the schedules.

The validation was initiated by visually comparing the distribution of locations in the source and in the target area, to appreciate their similarity. The following figure shows the locations of a sample user in the two areas (original one on the left, located in Tuscany; remapped one on the right, in Porto). The maps are reproduced at the same scale. The blue spot represents the estimate home location (L_0) and the yellow one the work location (L_1). In particular, the work location on the right was manually fixed at the INESC TEC offices that host the EV recharge facilities. A direct comparison reveals (as expected) that the home-work distances are very similar. Also, in both cases the majority of locations are closer to the home than the workplace, their distribution being slightly skewed on the home side of the home location. It was observed that the source area has a more irregular distribution of roads and nodes, which led naturally to have locations more concentrated in some parts of the map, whereas this physical constraint is weaker in the target area, resulting in a more homogeneous distribution. Overall, the target remapping has been evaluated by the domain expert (INESC TEC) as both reasonable for the geographical area and compatible with the source IMNs.

The second validation of the mapping process consists in evaluating the RMSE between the original and the mapped distances among locations. The figures below show the distribution of RMSE obtained over 1'000 IMNs mapped. The left plot represents the global RMSE, while the right one is limited to the 10 most frequent locations of each IMN.

Figure 2.16: Illustration of the locations of a sample user in the two areas (original one on the left, located in Tuscany; remapped one on the right, in Porto).

Figure 2.17: Illustration of the distribution of RMSE obtained over 1'000 IMNs mapped. The left plot represents the global RMSE, while the right one is limited to the 10 most frequent locations of each IMN.

The results suggest that in most cases the RMSE remains below 6 km (RMSE can be interpreted as a sort of standard deviation and is expressed in the same unit of measure of the original quantities, in this case distances), which looks acceptable for a city of the scale of Porto. Focusing on the right plot, it can be inferred that most of the RMSE was due to less frequent locations, which are less impactful in describing the mobility of the user, thus confirming the quality of the mapping.

2.3.2.3 Traffic distribution test

Alternatively, an indirect way to validate the realism of the generated locations and trajectories consists in inspecting the resulting traffic on the map. While 1000 vehicles are not enough to produce stable statistics about the traffic distribution, a visual inspection can provide some preliminary feedback. In the following figure, on the left, the road network of Porto was plotted, highlighting the frequency of visit of road segments through their width. On the right, a map showing the distribution of roads in the area (map taken from Ibraeva et al. [6]).

Figure 2.18: On the left plot, the road network of Porto is presented, highlighting frequency of visit of road segments through their width. On the right plot, a map showing the distribution of roads in the area.

It is evident that simulated traffic generated seems to be concentrated along the main roads, with an extra hotspot around INESC TEC facilities, as expected given the bias introduced in the generation (all IMNs have that location as workplace). Similarly, the domain expert confirmed the realism of such distribution.

2.3.2.4 Runtimes

In the final testing task, the runtimes involved in data generation were evaluated. Indeed, while the computational costs are typically not as critical in data generation as in other services, since it is typically a

one-shot operation whose cost is easily amortised, it is useful to understand what is the scale of the population that can be simulated by our tool. To this purpose, the following plot shows the distribution of computation times (in seconds) required to generate the trajectory history of a user over a window of two weeks (as in the previous tests). Runtimes have been collected over a commodity machine using a single core. From the plot it can be observed that typical times range between 3 and 8 seconds, meaning that simulating the whole population of a typical medium-small European city of 100,000 inhabitants would require between 83 and 230 hours, a relatively large time, yet manageable, also considering the extreme size of the task. However, it can be noticed that the process is perfectly parallelisable, as each IMN can be relocated and simulate independently from the others, thus even a single multi-core machine would be sufficient to reduce runtimes by an order of magnitude, making the process doable in less than one day.

Figure 2.19: Distribution of computation times (in seconds) required to generate the trajectory history of a user over a window of two weeks (as in the previous tests).

2.3.3 Next steps

The synthetic trajectory generation tool will be used in the context of UC#2, and will be subject to at least the following activities:

- Adapting the tool to specific requirements emerging from first usages. Indeed, it is expected to make the generated data a better fit for the application, further constraints will be required, linked to the characteristics of the population to simulate (so far only their work location was considered, yet it is possible that other known behaviours will emerge, that are requested to be integrated as constraints), to geospatial features of the city that the domain expert might want to consider (roads typically avoided by locals, hours of work different from those in the source area, etc.), or to external data to be aligned, such as the energy demand at the recharge facilities.
- Improving the realism (in general terms, not for the specific UC) by considering various details that in this first version of the tool have not been implemented. On the spatial side, locations are randomly assigned to nodes in the target area, yet if more information are available about population distribution (in particular of the specific population involved in UC2) the location mapping might better try to align to it. Also, the mapping adopts as main criterion the (straight line) distance between locations, whereas the possibility to replace it with travel distance or travel time could be explored, evaluating the improvements are worth the obvious increase of computational cost. On the temporal side, currently stay times are perturbed without a tight consistency control, which might be put in place at regular intervals, for instance to check that the daily cycles all start within a reasonable time interval, with no cumulative time shifts.
- Improving efficiency and energy consumption. While not the primary focus of this tool, it is envisaged to improve various parts of the process, especially exploiting the redundancies present in personal mobility

routines, e.g. the routes between frequent origin-destination pairs might be computed only once and then reused, which would significantly reduce costs.

- Integrating the tool in the platform, and more specifically making it usable for the UC. Currently, the tool manages input and output data through simple CSV files (and JSON files, if precomputed IMNs are given as input). Next versions will include a more integrated data exchange following the communication channels provided by the project infrastructure.

2.4 Large-scale time series analytics

In this section, a comprehensive overview of the models developed within the domain of large-scale time series analytics under the context of Task 3.2, is presented. Time series data, characterised by sequential observations recorded over time, presents unique challenges in analysis and prediction, particularly when dealing with vast datasets (refer to Appendix I for more details on SotA in Large-scale time series analytics). The innovative models designed to address these challenges are presented, offering insights into their construction, functionality, and performance in handling temporal data at scale. This section focuses on two specific directions: trajectory-based battery consumption estimation and EV transaction data forecasting, representing significant areas of interest within the domain of EV charging time series analytics.

2.4.1 Trajectory-based battery consumption estimation (ThunderFlow)

In our era EVs have emerged as a crucial component in the pursuit of a greener and sustainable future. The analysis and management of EV energy consumption on a per-trip or per-user basis necessitates the development of sophisticated data-driven tools capable of providing detailed insights into EV energy dynamics. However, existing literature and tools often fall short in delivering comprehensive, efficient, and user-friendly solutions (refer to Appendix I for more details). For this reason, Thunder Flow, a tool that provides a full pipeline to pre-process, map-match (if requested) and elaborate trajectory data to infer the corresponding battery consumption, was developed.

2.4.1.1 Architecture

The system contains a suite of specialised modules for the battery consumption estimation for EVs, in particular: Elevation, Segmentation of Trajectories, Map-Matching, and Calculation of Consumption are designed to function cohesively, harnessing elevation data, trajectory segmentation, and map-matching integration to provide an accurate estimation. As depicted in the figure below, ThunderFlow's core architecture is composed of four principal modules, which form the foundation of the system. These modules are thoroughly described, as follows:

Figure 2.20: ThunderFlow's core architecture composed of four principal modules.

2.4.1.2 Elevation Data Retrieval

The system first verifies if there is elevation data in the inputs. If not, this module uses a function based on the GPS coordinates to determine the correct Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) data tile based on the provided longitude and latitude coordinates. The system proceeds to download the zip file containing the elevation data, and to extract the TIFF (Tagged Image File Format) file, and then uses it to retrieve the elevation information for the given coordinates. The elevation data is downloaded from the CGIAR-CSI GeoPortal that provides the SRTM 90m Digital Elevation Data covering the entire world.

2.4.1.3 Trajectory Segmentation

This module provides general trajectory pre-processing functionalities and specialises in segmenting trajectories. It utilises three critical parameters for trajectory segmentation: temporal threshold, spatial threshold, and the minimum number of points required in each trajectory segment. The temporal threshold, also known as the max time gap, is defined as the maximum allowable time period (in seconds) between two consecutive points in a trajectory. If the actual time interval between two points exceeds this predefined threshold, it triggers a segmentation of the trajectory, terminating the current trajectory and initiating a new one. This mechanism ensures that the data segmentation accurately reflects significant pauses or breaks in movement, which is essential for precise analysis and modelling in various applications. The spatial threshold represents the minimum permissible distance (measured in meters) between two consecutive points in a trajectory. If the distance between two points is found to be less than this predefined threshold, it implies minimal or no movement, suggesting that the vehicle is stationary. In such instances, the system will automatically remove the point from the trajectory analysis. This process is crucial for ensuring that only meaningful movement data is considered in the trajectory analysis.

If the number of points in a trajectory does not meet the required minimum, the system will not proceed with creating the segmentation. This criterion ensures that each segmented trajectory has a sufficient number of data points to be considered valid and reliable for further analysis. This module utilises the unique identifier of each vehicle to segment the trajectories accordingly. This is done with the objective of ensuring that the trajectories are distinctly differentiated. The parameters – max time gap, min space gap, and the minimum number of trajectories – are customisable, allowing users to tailor them according to their specific requirements. These settings come with default values, providing a convenient starting point for users who prefer not to modify the initial configurations:

Table 2.3: Overview of the model's parameters

Parameter	Unit	Value	Description
temporal_thr	seconds	1200	Maximum temporal distance between points
Spatial_thr	meters	50	Minimum distance between points
minpoints	-	4	Minimum number points required

2.4.1.4 Map-matching

In this section, the integration of map matching within the tool is described, highlighting its connection with two open-source route engine services: Open Source Routing Machine (OSRM) and Valhalla. By utilising OSRM and Valhalla, the tool gains access to comprehensive and accurate road data, crucial for a precise analysis, especially when the initial sampling rate of data is not very high. It should be noted that the utilisation of map matching is an optional feature. The decision to employ this tool rests solely with the user, offering flexibility based on individual requirements or preferences. In particular, ThunderFlow will be mainly applied in the crowdsourcing scenario of UC#2, where the input data is expected to be at high frequency, thus the map-matching functionality will not be exploited in this case.

The OSRM is a powerful tool that specializes in fast route calculations, utilising OpenStreetMap data. For each trajectory, the map matching function from OSRM is applied, then data are analysed, and points are matched to road segments obtained from Open Street Map data. The output from OSRM significantly enhances the accuracy of the vehicle's path representation by aligning it with the established road network. Additionally, OSRM provides valuable data such as the average speed limit of each road, as well as distance and time estimates between consecutive points. This additional information is instrumental for this system, as it allows for more precise calculations in estimating the battery consumption of EVs. By integrating these detailed insights from OSRM, varying speeds, distances, and travel times can be better accounted, all of which are critical factors in accurately assessing energy usage.

Valhalla, like OSRM, is an open-source routing service that offers sophisticated map matching capabilities. However, Valhalla is particularly known for its flexibility and support for various types of routing, such as multimodal and time-dependent routing. Like with OSRM once the trajectories are segmented, they are input into Valhalla's map matching service, one small difference with OSRM is that Valhalla takes into consideration timestamps to order the coordinates. In our system's context, a key distinction between Valhalla and OSRM is Valhalla's ability to provide a list of all the 'way_id' for each trajectory that has undergone map matching, representing a unique identifier used by Open Street Map. This feature makes it easier to compute road-based spatial aggregates, useful for various tasks.

2.4.1.5 EV Consumption

In this section, the mathematical model used for estimating the battery consumption will be outlined, based on the principle of tractive effort, a fundamental concept in vehicle dynamics. The model is based on Gaete-Morales et al. work [7]. The next figure describes the flows considered for consumption estimation.

Figure 2.21: Overview of all the flows considered in the estimation of the consumptions.

To determine a trip's energy consumption, calculations are conducted for power requirements for vehicle traction, heating and cooling. Additionally, assumptions on auxiliary power are included (customisable). Figure 2.21 above illustrates the power flows between the battery and the wheels, the heating/cooling devices, and the accessories.

Tractive effort is the force required to surpass the opposing forces to a vehicle's movement, which is the sum of *aerodynamic drag*, *rolling resistance force*, *climbing force*, and *linear acceleration and inertia forces* [8]. The aerodynamic drag force depends on the moist air density, the frontal area of the vehicle, the drag coefficient, and vehicle's velocity. *Power at wheels* (P_{wheel} in the Figure 2.21 above) is estimated at each time step when tractive effort is non-negative. Otherwise, P_{wheel} is zero and regenerative braking power takes the absolute value of the tractive effort. *Motor efficiency* depends on the motor's angular speed and torque. This

value can be determined experimentally for each vehicle model or can be provided by the manufacturer. A generalised approach has been implemented, where the efficiency function depends on the motor load fraction. Regenerative braking power occurs when the tractive effort is negative.

Heating, cooling, and accessories: power estimation is conducted to maintain a vehicle’s cabin temperature on a level of comfort for the passengers, employing a heat balance model [9]. The heating device may be either a resistor or a heat pump. Radiation heat transfer and latent heat by condensation and evaporation are features not considered in this model.

Positive or negative *energy consumption values* can be expected at the battery. Suppose the sum of motor input power, generator output power, auxiliary power, and power for heating/cooling is positive, the battery then provides energy to the vehicle as it discharges, and the discharging efficiency is used. Conversely, if the overall power required is negative, the battery charges via regenerative braking., with negative battery load employing charging efficiency.

The following table summarises the parameters required for estimating the driving electricity consumption, together with the values used for the consumption model.

Table 2.4: Overview of the model’s parameters

Parameter	Unit	Value	Description
η_{tr}	%	95	Transmission efficiency
η_{charge}	%	90	Efficiency for battery charging
$\eta_{discharge}$	%	95	Efficiency for battery discharging
h_{cabin}	W/(m ² K)	10	Cabin air convective heat transfer coefficient
	kg	75	Person mass
$Q_{sensible}$	W	70	Person sensible heat of a driver or passengers
	quantity	1	Number of passengers in the vehicle
T_{amb}	Celsius	-	Temperature from data coordinates
T_{cabin}	Celsius	17 (20)	Target cabin temperature for heating (cooling)
V_{cabin}	m ³	3.5	Air volume of vehicle's cabin
V_{in}, V_{out}	m ³ /s	0.02	Input (output) air flow at ambient (cabin) temperature for ventilation
P_{aux}	W	300	Auxiliary power for electronic accessories and battery heating
COP	-	2	Coefficient of performance. Values >1 imply the use of a heat pump; similar COP for heating and cooling assumed

2.4.1.6 Parallel Processing and Vectorisation

Two common techniques were employed to boost computational performances in the Python environment. Thunder Flow integrates key elements of vectorisation capabilities from NumPy, such as `numpy.select` and `numpy.where()` functions. By replacing conditional loops with `numpy.where()`, Thunder Flow can efficiently filter data based on specified conditions and apply various computations or transformations to array elements in a singular operation. For more complex scenarios involving multiple conditions, `numpy.select` proves to be invaluable, allowing for the definition of numerous conditions and choices in a straightforward manner. Implementing these vectorised functions marked a substantial improvement over traditional iterative method.

In the computational framework of our tool, parallel processing has been integrated to enhance efficiency and speed in estimations. In particular, the Pool class from the multiprocessing library was utilised to enhance

efficiency and speed in computational estimations. Applying the Pool class to our specific function, which estimates battery consumption, effectively facilitated tasks distribution across multiple cores.

2.4.2 Evaluation of Trajectory-based battery consumption estimation (ThunderFlow)

The tool is evaluated in terms of performances and providing a UC which shows some temporal and spatial statistics inferred from a very large dataset – a computation that would be impossible with most of previously existing tools.

2.4.2.1 Scalability

The dataset used in the scalability study comprises GPS coordinates around the city of Lucca region, Tuscany. The dataset encompasses a total of 220,632 entries, detailing the movements of 2,294 vehicles over a period of two months. Testing our Python project involved gradually increasing the volume of data, starting from a 10%, then increasing to 20% and so forth. This approach allowed us to observe how well ThunderFlow handles progressively larger datasets, providing important information about its capacity and efficiency. All experiments have been performed on a commodity machine having a single processor with 4 cores and 32 GB of RAM, also running the Valhalla map-matching server.

The results are summarised in the following table and plot, comparing a version of our tool considering parallel processing optimisation (right column of the table, colour red in the Figure 2.22) against a sequential one (right column, blue colour).

Table 2.5: Execution results

Data Percent (%)	Execution (Original Time)	Execution (New Time)
10	4.99	2.37
20	9.60	4.64
30	15.34	6.91
40	20.22	9.18
50	24.56	11.45
60	28.94	13.72
70	33.73	15.99
80	38.52	18.26
90	43.31	20.53
100	48.10	22.80

Figure 2.22: Execution results.

Runtimes show linear growth, and that the parallelisation has a significant effect, in spite of the limited specifics of the hardware adopted. Additionally, a major part of the computation time is attributed to map-matching, and the runtimes on high-frequency datasets (that do not require map-matching) are only a small fraction of those obtained on the full pipeline over low-frequency data.

2.4.2.2 Case of study

The dataset of our case study constitutes a collection of GPS location traces, charting movements throughout diverse regions of Italy over the course of the entire year of 2019. Overall, the dataset contains over 730 million points, corresponding to over 20 million trajectories. Below is a spatial visualisation of (a sample of) the dataset, covering a large portion of Central-Northern Italy. Noticeably, the vehicles involved are based on a combustion engine, while the simulation represents the battery consumption they would cause if exactly the same trips were performed with an electric motor.

Figure 2.23: Dataset overview.

The estimation of battery consumption for all the trips in the dataset allowed to compute several interesting aggregates. The first ones were temporal distributions of trip length and consumption, aimed at comparison and exploration of potential strong relations:

Users' consumption distribution

Users' travelled distances

Distances vs. Consumptions

Figure 2.24: Estimation of battery consumption.

As depicted in the plot above, the two distributions are quite similar, showing several short / low-consumption trips and a relatively long tail containing less vehicles traveling long distances / causing high battery consumptions. Battery consumptions, exhibit a slightly smoother distribution. Comparing distance

vs. Consumption for each trip (right plot), a clear linear relationship is visible, however the dispersion around the diagonal is rather strong, meaning that distance is not the only important factor in determining the trip consumption.

Another type of aggregation involves temporal analysis, aiming to identify periods (during the week or during the day) with higher electric energy consumption for travel.

Figure 2.25: Overview of the day-of-week distribution of consumption (left plot); Overview of the hourly distribution of battery consumptions (right plot).

The left plot shows the day-of-week distribution of consumption (aggregated over all weeks and all vehicles), revealing a surprising peak during Saturday, rather than working days – contrary to expectations, given typically higher trip frequency on weekends. An interpretation suggests that weekends involve usually more diverse trips and farther destinations, thus requiring more energy. The right plot shows the hourly distribution of battery consumptions, clearly displaying the standard three-peaks shape of urban traffic. The final aggregations pertain to spatial distribution of consumptions. The average consumption per km for each road in the cities of Florence and Bologna, is presented below.

(a) Florence

(b) Bologna

Figure 2.26: Overview of average consumption per km for each road in cities of Florence and Bologna.

This measure provides a way to identify areas where vehicles tend to consume more easily the battery. In both cities it is evident that very high consumption rates (red) appear mostly on external areas, whereas central roads are more often medium- (yellow) or low-consumption. Several of the external red lines correspond to mountain roads, where it is expected that the slope has a high impact on consumption. In the city centre, instead, red lines typically correspond to small, secondary streets, that most likely require frequent acceleration and deceleration.

To conclude, the case study allowed to collect interesting insights about consumption distribution, and at the same time provided an indirect validation of the output quality, since the obvious expected patterns (e.g. high consumption on steep roads) were clearly found in the estimates provided by the tool.

2.4.3 Description of EV Transaction Data Forecasting service

The forecasting tool proposes a method for estimating parking duration and the total amount of energy charged during an EV charging session, utilising historical data from previous transactions. The approach depends on historical EV charging transaction data, specific to each EV owner, which can be sourced from the database of a Charging Station Management System (CSMS) overseeing multiple charging points, or from an individual EV charger’s database.

The methodology provides estimates of a client’s total parking duration and expected total energy consumption, crucial for predictive management and planning in CSMS tools. By integrating this data, a CSMS equipped with intelligent EV charging management tools can take more informed decisions about allocating charging resources among EVs connected to a grid or charging station. The diagram for the duration/energy forecasting is presented in the figure below.

Figure 2.27: Framework of EV Transaction Data Forecasting

The following is a concise description of the key stages in this methodology:

1. Arrival and Data Collection: When a client arrives and plugs their EV to the charging station, the system automatically begins collecting data about the transaction and retrieves historical data of previous transactions. This data includes the time of day, client identifier, and historical charging patterns (i.e., total energy charged and parking duration).
2. Statistical Analysis: This stage involves analysing the historical charging patterns of the EV owner to assess the number of historical transactions for model training (e.g., perform Extract-Transfer-Load on EV

owner's datasets), and understand charging behaviour (e.g., frequent charging on specific days and times).

3. **Forecasting Process:** The statistical analysis supports a forecasting approach that includes naive methods and ML models to predict the parking duration of the EV at the station and the expected energy consumption.

It is important to note that these models provide one forecast value (continuous variable) per transaction operation, the total energy charged and/or total duration time. These operations do not directly affect the charging transaction of the EV owner (e.g., not direct control EV charging current); decisions are made on a later stage by other tools that use the forecasts for predictive management. Smart charging tools will later be responsible for effect resource allocation, for instance adjusting the initial charging time of a connected EV to a later period, to optimise the use of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and maintain the quality of service for the end-user.

The framework comprises of 5 steps and components illustrated above and described below:

- 1) **CSMS:** This is the central system that manages the EV charging station. It stores data on both current and past charging transactions, which includes information on energy transferred, parking duration, and transaction metadata (time of arrival/departure, client identification, transaction identification, etc.). A system providing this historical data should be available to be used by the developed tools.
- 2) **EV charging Transaction:** When an EV owner arrives at the charging station, it connects to the EV charger and begins a charging transaction which terminates when the EV is unplugged from the charger.
- 3) **Statistical Analysis:** Historical transaction data from the specific EV owner is analysed to identify behavioural patterns on previous transactions and allocate the client within a given category (e.g., clients with varying degrees of number of transactions and client assiduity).
- 4) **Data Processing and Forecasting:**
 - The system uses two types of models to process the data and make forecasts.
 - **Models:** ML regression models combining feature engineering techniques with the Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) algorithm are used to forecast the EV parking duration and total energy charged during a single transaction.
 - **Naive Models:** Simpler approach using historical of recent EV transactions, used to forecast the EV parking duration and energy charged for EV owners with a small number of transactions and / or very consistent charging habits (to reduce computational overhead and avoid the complexity of training / optimising new ML models).
 - The system provides two separate forecasts:
 - **Parking Duration Forecast:** This is an estimate of the number of minutes an EV will be parked and connected to the charging station for the current charging transaction.
 - **Charged Energy Forecast:** This is an estimate of how much energy the EV will consume from the charging station, during the current transaction.

The combined forecast can be used by the EV charging optimisation tools, which may adjust the charging rate or schedule charging sessions to maximise efficiency, minimise costs, or balance the load on power grid.

2.4.4 Evaluation of EV Transaction Data Forecasting service

The forecasting models were evaluated using charging transactions data from semi-public charging stations in Portugal.

Table 2.6: Overview of charging transactions data from semi-public charging stations in Portugal.

client	category	Mean Duration	Max Duration	Median Duration	Duration Std	STD Day of Week	Transaction count
T3C1	T3	77.7	131.0	79.5	21.7	2.0	124.0
T3C2		30.9	54.0	30.0	7.8	2.1	94.0
T3C3		61.0	105.0	65.5	18.9	1.9	92.0
T3C4		62.5	102.0	60.0	14.1	2.0	80.0
T3C5		64.3	121.0	62.0	16.9	2.0	70.0
T3C6		27.5	55.0	25.0	12.6	2.0	68.0
T3C7		29.8	32.0	30.0	1.8	2.0	53.0
T3C8		69.9	111.0	69.0	18.0	2.0	52.0
T3C9		51.2	77.0	49.0	11.2	2.0	52.0
T3C10		49.1	146.0	45.0	22.9	2.0	51.0
T5C1	T5	222.4	292.0	252.0	67.7	2.0	113.0
T5C2		174.4	330.0	190.0	76.6	2.0	109.0
T5C3		122.4	421.0	72.5	110.3	1.9	92.0
T5C4		103.1	223.0	109.5	60.2	2.0	90.0
T5C5		186.6	300.0	218.0	73.0	2.0	71.0
T5C6		218.2	335.0	220.0	62.5	2.0	65.0
T5C7		307.8	598.0	307.0	187.0	2.0	52.0
T5C8		127.1	286.0	84.0	78.3	1.9	50.0
T5C9		222.7	599.0	139.0	179.8	2.0	49.0
T5C10		120.2	209.0	138.0	60.1	2.0	46.0

To improve ML capacity of identifying user behaviour, EV clients were categorised into seven groups based on their historical charging sessions. This section presents the results for two categories:

1. EV owners with small variability on charging session duration (group T3)
2. EV owners with high variability on charging session duration (group T5)

Each category contains 10 different clients. For example, T5C3 means the third client of the fifth category. For clarification, variability is defined based on the standard deviation of historical charging sessions, which ranges 1.8 to 22.9 minutes for group T3 and 60 to 186.9 minutes for group T5.

Figure 2.28: Comparison of MAE (duration) for T3 (low variability) achieved by proposed method (xgb) and reference naïve models.

Figure 2.28 and Figure 2.29 illustrate a comparison between the MAE calculated between the observed and forecasted duration by the proposed regression model (denoted as xgb) and other seven naïve approaches.

For T3 clients, the proposed model presents a MAE of 3.5 minutes compared to an average of 13 minutes for the remaining naïve approaches. In this scenario, clients have a steady behaviour through each charging session, with relatively low MAE values for naïve approaches. The proposed method consistently outperformed the reference models with an overall improvement of approximately 66%.

Figure 2.29: Comparison of MAE (duration) for T5 (low variability) achieved by proposed method (xgb) and reference naïve models.

For T5 clients, the proposed model presents a mean MAE of 22.6 minutes compared to an average of 84.8 minutes for the remaining naïve approaches. The proposed method consistently outperformed the reference models with an overall improvement of approximately 69.3%. Note that these group of clients have a significantly higher variability in transaction (parking) times, thus the increase in difficulty to generate accurate forecasts. The proposed method for charging session duration presented to be robust even when the forecasting scenario is more challenging (for instance, T5 group of EV owners). The proposed ML model could capture information on historical data that allowed the model to consistently perform better than the reference models.

Figure 2.30: Comparison of MAE (Charged Energy) for T3 (low variability) achieved by proposed method (xgb) and reference naïve models.

Figure 2.30 and Figure 2.31 present the comparison between forecasted charged energy MAE of the proposed model (denoted as xgb) and other seven naïve approaches. It is important to note that groups T3 and T5 are the same as before, still defined based on the variability of transaction duration times. For T3 clients, the proposed model presents a mean MAE of 1.8 kWh compared to an average of 3.9 kWh for the remaining naïve approaches. The proposed method consistently outperformed the reference models with an overall improvement of approximately 45.3%. For T5 clients, the proposed model presents a mean MAE of 1.68 kWh compared to an average of 5.7 kWh for the remaining naïve approaches. The proposed method consistently outperformed the reference models with overall improvement of approximately 62.4%.

Figure 2.31: Comparison of MAE (Charged Energy) for T5 (high variability) achieved by proposed method (xgb) and reference naïve models.

For both transaction durations (Figure 2.28 and Figure 2.29) and total energy consumption (Figure 2.30 and Figure 2.31) forecasting, the ML models appear to significantly outperform the naïve approaches, particularly when the forecasting scenario (i.e., group of clients in analysis) presents a higher variability in transaction duration times.

2.4.5 Next steps

The trajectory-based battery consumption estimation tool (ThunderFlow) will be used in the context of UC#2, and will be subject to at least the following activities:

- Adapting the tool to specific requirements emerging from first usages. Particularly, data quality and sampling rate might be different from the case studies treated so far, potentially necessitating refinements to the tool. For instance, it might be the case that the sampling rate is higher than strictly needed, and thus an adaptive subsampling might be beneficial to improve performances and reduce energy requirements. Similarly, if additional variables (e.g. acceleration) are directly available from the dataset, consideration will be given to their use as a replacement for some of the computed variables in the tool.
- Integrating and testing the tool within the platform, and more specifically making it usable for UC#2. Currently, the tool manages input and output data through simple CSV files. Next versions will include a more integrated data exchange following the communication channels provided by the project infrastructure.

Regarding the ‘EV Transaction Data Forecasting’ service, the proposed framework was implemented with the dataset from 70 individual clients with varying charging behaviour. In the current state the model can predict

the parking duration and the amount of charged energy for the current session. This is relevant information for smart charging strategies but has the limitation of not knowing when the next session will be started. To address this, a model for predicting the plug-in time or period between current and next transaction is currently under development. With this implementation, the desired output is a single model or a combination of models capable of predicting three components of a charging session, namely the **plug-in time**, the **parking duration of the session**, and the **amount of energy charged during this session**. Based on the first two, it is foreseen to obtain an estimate of the charger’s demand and occupancy for up to 24 hours ahead. Additionally, the current framework will be implemented and validated with INESC TEC’s EV charging structures. To summarise the next steps are the following:

- Completing the development of plug-in time forecast models.
- Implementing a final model / set of models capable of combining information from all forecasting tools, providing a timeseries of charging sessions for up to 24 hours ahead.
- Implementing and validating the framework for INESC TEC’s charging stations, expecting lower variability of charging session duration / energy / plug-times compared to the one observed in the group T3.
- Creating and deploying a prototype in Python programming language, for INESC TEC charging station databases.

2.5 Federated & Auto ML at the edge/fog

This section focuses on the services developed under the context of Subtask 3.2.2, which aim to perform time series forecasting in a FL scenario while ensuring data privacy, as well as provide AutoML functionalities for both algorithm selection and hyperparameter tuning.

2.5.1 Description of Privacy-preserving FL service

This service develops a set of algorithms that allows to combine and predict multiple time series, owned by multiple owners, with a unique model. To merge data from diverse owners, various statistical methods have emerged, such as the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model, whereas a novel solution has been put forth to encrypt the data in such a way that data owners can solve the Least Absolute Shrinkage (LASSO)-VAR model [10] (refer to Appendix I for more details). This service ensures data privacy without affecting the accuracy of the collaborative model.

2.5.1.1 Forecasting model formulation

Let $\mathbf{y}_t = (y_{1,t}, y_{2,t}, \dots, y_{N,t})$ be an N -dimensional multivariate time series, where N is the number of data owners, and $y_{i,t}$ denote the time series from the i -th data owner at time t . The simplest model tackled by this service is the VAR model, illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 2.32: VAR model representation (1 timestamp ahead, using p lags on power time series)

This illustration makes clear the natural division of data and coefficients by data owners. The main issue is how to estimate the coefficients without sharing sensible information. Usually, when considering potentially correlated data, the coefficients are estimated by solving the minimisation problem, called LASSO-VAR:

$$\hat{\mathbf{B}}_{\text{LASSO}} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{B}} \|\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{ZB}\|_2^2 + \lambda \|\mathbf{B}\|_1,$$

where $\|\cdot\|_r$, represents both vector and matrix L_r , norms, and $\lambda > 0$ is a scalar penalty parameter to be tuned. To solve this optimisation problem without compromising data privacy, a critical literature review has been made showing that existing privacy-preserving techniques are unsatisfactory [2]. As a result, a novel solution has been put forth in H2020 Smart4RES project to encrypt the data in such a way that data owners can solve the LASSO-VAR model [10]. In summary:

1. Collaboration among data owners is established to encrypt their respective data using a collectively unknown key \mathbf{M} ($\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{M}_1\mathbf{M}_2\dots\mathbf{M}_N$, where only \mathbf{M}_i is known by i -th data owner). Additionally, covariates (\mathbf{Z}_i) are locally transformed using a secret key ($\mathbf{Z}_i\mathbf{Q}_i$), crucial for safeguarding the coefficient values. An overview of the data encryption protocol is provided by Algorithm 1. Both covariates ($\mathbf{Z}_i\mathbf{Q}_i$) and target (\mathbf{Y}_i) are encrypted using the protocol depicted in Algorithm 1 [10], the encrypted data is therefore $\mathbf{MZ}_i\mathbf{Q}_i$ and \mathbf{MY}_i .
2. Data owners estimate the coefficients by sharing the encrypted version of their local models, as depicted in Algorithm 2 [10]. A main advantage of this algorithm is that global model's coefficients are not affected or deteriorated as is the case with differential privacy techniques.

Algorithm 1 Data Encryption.

Input from i th agent: $\mathbf{X}_{A_i} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times s}$ and $\mathbf{M}_{A_i} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times T}$

Input from j th agent ($j \neq i$): $\mathbf{M}_{A_j} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times T}$

Output: $\mathbf{MX}_{A_i} = \mathbf{M}_{A_1} \dots \mathbf{M}_{A_n} \mathbf{X}_{A_i}$

- 1: **Initialization:** Agent i generates random invertible matrices $\mathbf{C}_{A_i} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times (r-s)}$, $\mathbf{D}_{A_i} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$, and shares $\mathbf{W}_{A_i} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times r}$ with the n -th agent,

$$\mathbf{W}_{A_i} = [\mathbf{X}_{A_i}, \mathbf{C}_{A_i}] \mathbf{D}_{A_i}. \quad (10)$$

- 2: Agent n receives $\mathbf{W}_{A_i}, \forall i$.
- 3: Agent n shares $\mathbf{M}_{A_n} \mathbf{W}_{A_i}$ with the $(n-1)$ -th agent.
- 4: **for** agent $j = n-1, \dots, 1$ **do**
- 5: Agent j receives $\left(\prod_{k=j+1}^n \mathbf{M}_{A_k}\right) \mathbf{W}_{A_i}$, and
- 6: **if** $j > 1$ **then**
- 7: shares $\mathbf{M}_{A_j} \left(\prod_{k=j+1}^n \mathbf{M}_{A_k}\right) \mathbf{W}_{A_i}$ with agent $j-1$
- 8: **else**
- 9: shares $\mathbf{M}_{A_j} \left(\prod_{k=j+1}^n \mathbf{M}_{A_k}\right) \mathbf{W}_{A_i}$ with agent i
- 10: **end if**
- 11: **end for**
- 12: Agent i receives \mathbf{MW}_{A_i} from the 1-st agent and recovers \mathbf{MX}_{A_i} ,

$$[\mathbf{MX}_{A_i}, \mathbf{MC}_{A_i}] = \mathbf{MW}_{A_i} \mathbf{D}_{A_i}^{-1}. \quad (11)$$

Algorithm 2 Synchronous Privacy-preserving LASSO-VAR.

Input: Randomized data $\mathbf{MZ}_{A_i} \mathbf{Q}_{A_i}$, \mathbf{MY}_{A_i} , $\mathbf{Q}_{A_i}^\top \mathbf{Z}_{A_i}^\top \mathbf{M}^{-1}$
Output: Transformed coefficients $\mathbf{B}'_{A_i} = \mathbf{Q}_{A_i} \mathbf{B}_{A_i}$, $i=1, \dots, n$

- 1: **Initialization:** $\mathbf{B}'_{A_i}{}^0$, $\overline{\mathbf{H}}^0$, $\mathbf{U}^0 = \mathbf{0}$, $\lambda, \rho \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $k = 0$
 - 2: **for** agent $i = 1, \dots, n$ **do**
 - 3: $\mathbf{P}_{A_i} = \left((\mathbf{Z}_{A_i} \mathbf{Q}_{A_i})^\top (\mathbf{Z}_{A_i} \mathbf{Q}_{A_i}) + \rho \mathbf{Q}_{A_i}^\top \mathbf{Q}_{A_i} \right)^{-1}$
 - 4: **end for**
 - 5: **while** stopping criteria not satisfied **do**
 - 6: **for** agent $i = 1, \dots, n$ **do**
 - 7: **Initialization:** $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}_{A_i}{}^0$, $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}^0$, $\tilde{\mathbf{U}}^0 = \mathbf{0}$, $j = 0$
 - 8: $\mathbf{K}_{A_i} = \mathbf{MZ}_{A_i} \mathbf{Q}_{A_i} \mathbf{B}'_{A_i}{}^k + \overline{\mathbf{H}}^k - \overline{\mathbf{MZQB}}'^k - \mathbf{U}^k$ (3)
 - 9: **while** stopping criteria not satisfied **do**
 - 10: $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}_{A_i}{}^{j+1} = \mathbf{P}_{A_i} \left(\mathbf{Q}_{A_i}^\top \mathbf{Z}_{A_i}^\top \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{K}_{A_i} + \rho (\tilde{\mathbf{H}}^j - \tilde{\mathbf{U}}^j) \right)$
 - 11: $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}^{j+1} = S_{\lambda/\rho^2} \left(\mathbf{Q}_{A_i} \tilde{\mathbf{B}}_{A_i}{}^{j+1} + \tilde{\mathbf{U}}^j \right)$ # soft thresh. op.
 - 12: $\tilde{\mathbf{U}}^{j+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{U}}^j + \mathbf{Q}_{A_i} \tilde{\mathbf{B}}_{A_i}{}^{j+1} - \tilde{\mathbf{H}}^{j+1}$
 - 13: $j = j + 1$
 - 14: **end while**
 - 15: $\mathbf{B}'_{A_i}{}^{k+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{B}}_{A_i}{}^j$
 - 16: **end for**
 - 17: $\overline{\mathbf{MZQB}}'^k$ is shared with peers or central node, who computes (4)–(6),
 - 18:
$$\overline{\mathbf{MZQB}}'^k = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \mathbf{MZ}_{A_i} \mathbf{Q}_{A_i} \mathbf{B}'_{A_i}{}^k$$
 (4)
 - 19:
$$\overline{\mathbf{H}}^{k+1} = \frac{1}{N + \rho} \left(\mathbf{MY} + \overline{\mathbf{MZQB}}'^k + \rho \mathbf{U}^k \right)$$
 (5)
 - 20:
$$\mathbf{U}^{k+1} = \mathbf{U}^k + \overline{\mathbf{MZQB}}'^{k+1} - \overline{\mathbf{H}}^{k+1}$$
 (6)
 - 21: $k = k + 1$
 - 22: **end while**
-

In terms of the source code, given our status as a private organization with an inherent interest in exploring potential monetization avenues, it has been decided against publicly sharing the code on the project's common GitHub deployment. Nonetheless, INESC TEC is fully open to providing access to the code to reviewers or the project officer upon request. The code of the service is available online at a private repo¹² (please reach out to us for the required access credentials).

¹² <https://gitlab.inesctec.pt/cpes/european-projects/green-dat-ai/fl-wind-forecast>

2.5.1.2 Summary of the main components and interactions

In what follows, the main components are described: initialisation, data encryption, collaborative model fitting, and forecasting.

1. **Initialisation:** multiple collaborative forecasting models can be considered, and the frequency and prediction horizon of such models depend on the specific application, e.g., for the RES power forecasting, 6 models may be considered per day, aligned with the electricity market bidding sessions. An initialisation step will be orchestrated by a central node that receives metadata from interested data owners such as:
 - a. their ID for future communications with peers
 - b. their target time series and/or variables available (only historical values? predictions for the next H timesteps?)
 - c. time intervals available for training

Based on that, data owners are informed about the required historical data, the forecasting horizon, and the moments to submit information. This central node collects the agents' IP addresses, to create an address book that establishes the communication sequence among participants.

2. **Data encryption** (data owners locally): data owners cooperate to encrypt their data sequentially by doing algebraic operations with secret matrices.
 - a. Local data encryption of private data matrix (denoted **data**)
 - i. Generate private random matrices C and D
 - ii. Perform the operation $W = (\mathbf{data} \mid C) * D$, \mid is the side by side concatenation
 - iii. Create a file (e.g. JSON) with dates and corresponding W
 - iv. Transmit the file (to the first IP in the IP address book).
 - b. Global data encryption (sequential)
 - i. Generate random matrix M
 - ii. Operations with M
 - iii. Transmit JSON file to the next IP in the IP address book.
 - c. Recover final encryption (local to each data owner)
 - i. Invert matrix D
 - ii. Operations with inverse of D
 - iii. Obtain encrypted data (**Encdata**)
3. **Collaborative model fitting (P2P or Centralised):** Once the data has been encrypted, data owners can proceed with estimating their coefficients. This process involves performing local model estimation and aggregating the local models to create a global model. However, there are two important challenges that need to be tackled during the aggregation phase: asynchronous communication and the detection of malicious noise. In essence, the following functions must be considered:
 - a. Initialisation (data owners locally)
 - b. Local model update (data owners locally)
 - c. Information exchange, with two possible schemes:
 - i. P2P: all agents exchange their local contributions with peers, without relying on a centralised authority.
 - ii. Centralised: all agents involved exchange their local contributions with a central entity. This central entity acts as a coordinator or aggregator.
 - d. Convergence analysis to detect malicious noise injection
 - e. Asynchronous communication

- f. Global aggregation
4. **Forecast (P2P):** each agent performs calculations and shares its contribution with every other agent. Once all the contributions have been received, each agent can then obtain its forecast result.
 - a. Local contribution (data owners locally)
 - b. Exchange of local contributions (data owner > data owner)
 - c. Aggregation of local contributions (data owners locally)

2.5.1.3 Innovation

While VAR models are competitive in very short-term forecasting (e.g., 15min to 6h ahead), their accuracy decreases for longer forecasting horizons due to the need for incorporating weather forecasts and the nonlinear relationship between weather forecasts and power. To tackle this issue, GREEN.DAT.AI suggests improving the previous solution by investigating variable transformation through spline and potentially kernel functions.

2.5.2 Evaluation of Privacy-preserving FL service

Initial experiments with B-spline transformations have been conducted, indicating the potential of these data transformation techniques. To assess the effectiveness of individually transformed data using B-spline transformers, wind power data from the GEFCom2014 competition was used.

The objective was to predict wind power for 10 Australian zones 24 hours in advance, starting from 0:00. The dataset from the Global Energy Forecasting Competition 2014 (GEFCom2014) spans from Jan 1, 2012, to Nov 30, 2013. Hourly wind power measurements are normalised based on zone capacities. Predictors include 24-hour forecasts for zonal and meridional wind components at 10 and 100 meters above ground level, issued daily at midnight to production locations. Four models were compared:

- LASSO Regression (privacy ensured): a linear model similar to the VAR model described in Section 2.5.1.1, predicting power values for the 10 zones as a linear combination of weather forecasts.
- B-spline LASSO (privacy ensured): predicts power values for the 10 zones as a linear combination of B-spline transformed weather forecasts.
- Gradient Boosting Regressor (privacy not ensured): a SotA nonlinear model for wind power forecasting.
- Kernel Ridge Regression (privacy not ensured): a SotA nonlinear model for wind power forecasting.

Figure 2.33 illustrates the performance of the models for 3 of the 10 zones in terms of RMSE. Hyperparameters for Gradient Boosting regressor and Kernel regression are tuned using Bayesian optimisation, minimising RMSE averaged in a 12-fold cross-validation. A sliding window of a month test and a 12-month train is used, meaning each model is optimised 11 times for each zone, including hyperparameters. Collaborative models are depicted with continuous lines, and models using only local data are depicted with dashed lines. In general, collaborative models outperformed their local counterparts. However, the extent of this advantage varied across zones, underscoring the potential benefits of data sharing among zones and the need for effective incentives since the degree of such improvements varies geographically. The Gradient Bosting Regressor and Kernel Ridge regression are front-runners among the models evaluated, consistently delivering lower RMSE. Remarkably, the spline LASSO (a linear parameter model) closely matches the performance of Gradient Bosting Regressor and Kernel Ridge regression, suggesting additive linear models can be effective alternatives in RES forecasting.

Figure 2.33: Performance of the models for 3 of the 10 zones in terms of RMSE.

2.5.3 Description of Algorithm Selection & Hyperparameter Tuning/AutoML service

Automated machine learning (AutoML) [11] aims to automate the pipeline design process (data preparation, cleaning, transformation, algorithm selection, hyperparameters' optimisation etc.) throughout a project's life cycle. In this way, tools become accessible to non-experts and practitioners reduce operational work time, improve efficiency, and accelerate decision making.

Algorithm selection and hyperparameter tuning are crucial but difficult tasks for a data scientist during pipeline design (refer to Appendix I for more details). For every ML task, such as classification, regression, clustering etc., one has a plethora of model choices with not one best model for every task. Additionally, each model requires a set of parameters, such as kernel type and regularisation for Support Vector Machine (SVM) classification. The combination of algorithm selection and hyperparameter optimisation is known in the literature as Combined Algorithm Selection and Hyperparameter optimisation.

One core concept of AutoML is optimisation, aiming to minimise the objective function.

$$x^* = \operatorname{argmin}_x f(x)$$

If f is a real valued function one can use mathematical calculus, using the function's derivatives in order to obtain critical points and characterise them accordingly. If f is not a closed-form function and defined properly, there is no way to extract the function's derivatives. Such functions, with no closed form, that are characterised only by their input and their output, are called black-box functions. Model evaluation can be considered as a black-box function where the input is the model's hyperparameters and the output is a predefined evaluation metric.

Meta-Learning. In the context of AutoML, meta-learning [12] observes how a variety of algorithm configurations have historically performed for different tasks, to create meta-models capable of predicting well performing solutions for new tasks. Meta-Learning finds application in both algorithm selection and hyperparameter tuning. Regarding algorithm selection one can associate data sets with meta-feature vectors, upon which a meta-learner can be trained to predict the best algorithm. In the case of hyperparameter tuning, meta-learners can be trained to warm-start the optimisation procedure by providing

the initial configurations to search. Meta-features usually include information on the data sets, stemming from statistics, information theory etc. Novel approaches use Deep Learning techniques to extract meta-features [13]. A comprehensive list of meta-features can be found in [12].

In this service, a meta-feature model is employed for algorithm selection prior to hyperparameter tuning, enabling to narrow down the search space of optimisation, thus reducing the necessary iterations to identify the best performing model. Currently, this is available for clustering based on Poulakis et al. [14] (refer to Appendix I for more details) but future steps include expanding this concept to support timeseries forecasting as well.

Bayesian Optimisation. One of the most frequently used optimisation algorithms for hyper parameter tuning is that of Bayesian optimisation [15]. In general, Bayesian statistics are founded upon the relationship of prior and posterior distributions. With the use of the Bayes' theorem:

$$p_{prior} \sim p_{posterior} \times likelihood$$

During Bayesian Optimisation we expect to estimate the prior distribution p_{prior} which depicts our belief regarding the objective function, through an iterative process of sequentially evaluating the function. To achieve this, two basic components are used: a) an acquisition function and b) a surrogate model. The former is responsible for querying new hyperparameters' points and the latter is used to estimate hyperparameters' space importance of which new sampling points at every iteration are queried.

A challenging procedure in Bayesian optimisation is hyperparameters' sampling from the provided search space. Two key aspects of this procedure are exploration and exploitation. Exploitation refers to choosing new query points based on our current knowledge about the hyperparameters' space. On the other hand, exploration refers to investigating new subspaces of the hyperparameters' search space that were not evaluated before, in order to get better outcomes. A trade-off of these two factors is the cornerstone of the sampling procedure in current Bayesian optimisation solutions.

In the developed service Bayesian optimisation is used to tackle hyperparameter tuning, configurable in terms of whether it follows algorithm selection or is used independently, and other aspects such as the number of trials. In the case that it is used independently, algorithms are defined as high level parameters in the search space and are the first to be selected during the sampling process.

The pseudocode of the Bayesian optimisation procedure is as follows:

- 1: While iteration \leq Budget_threshold then:
- 2: Select point x_{iter} to evaluate $f(x)$ by optimising acquisition function $a \quad x_{iter} = \operatorname{argmax} a(X | D_{1:t-1})$
- 3: Evaluate $y_{iter} = f(x_{iter})$
- 4: $D_{1:t} = D_{1:t-1} \cup \{(x_{iter}, y_{iter})\}$
- 5: Update statistical model

General Approach. In Figure 2.34 the general approach that the service follows is presented. Firstly, an offline phase examines a plethora of data sets by testing different algorithm configurations upon them. Each algorithm configuration is evaluated to be compared in terms of performance so the best performing for each data set can be retrieved. Each data set is also associated with a set of meta-features, a vector of values that characterise the data sets, drawn from statistics, information theory and landmarking. Upon this information, the meta-features and the best performing algorithm are used to train predictive models, such as KNN to predict upon meta-features the best performing algorithm.

Afterwards in the online phase, this information is exploited in the meta-learning module, followed by Bayesian optimisation for hyperparameter tuning. Currently, this service supports clustering and time series forecasting. For the former, our approach is based on the methodology described by Poulakis et al. [14] including 12 algorithms. For timeseries forecasting, two predictive algorithms, ANNs and XGBoost are currently supported. The service, true to the AutoML paradigm, requires as input a data set and one of the tasks to solve. Additionally, the actor using this service can provide a number of maximum trials for the optimisation procedure, although it is not mandatory. Default values have been assigned according to our experimentation.

Figure 2.34: Service application in both offline and online phase.

2.5.4 Evaluation of Algorithm Selection & Hyperparameter Tuning/AutoML service

General approach on UC#5. This service has been tested on data from the use-case entitled ‘Energy demand response in e-bikes & infrastructure planning’. The contribution includes automated time series forecasting to predict future bike stations’ demand, which is then provided as input to the minimum cost flow optimisation to provide a bikes’ redistribution planning. The basic data that were taken into consideration include trips and stations’ information. Trips’ data refer to trips that took place from one station to another and stations’ data refer to static information regarding their id and spatial clusters to which they belong to and their geolocation (longitude and latitude).

The goal of this scenario is to optimise bikes’ redistribution among the stations to maximise bike availability based on the predicted users’ demand. The main steps of our approach are described below:

- 1) Data undergo feature engineering to extract time series data from the raw trips data. Each station is associated with a time series that depicts the bike demand values for that station across a given time interval.
- 2) The AutoML procedure is initiated to predict future stations’ demand. Specifically, the Bayesian optimiser explores a large configuration space to select the best performing model according to a predefined number of iterations.

- 3) The forecasting results are combined with enriched data provided by Task 3.1.1 ‘Data Enrichment’, which includes information on the pairwise transportation time between stations.
- 4) The given data forecasted demand values, and estimated transportation times between stations are depicted to create a graph for solving the redistribution problem for a future time-window.
- 5) Optimisation is performed with a transformed version of the Minimum Cost Flow problem, using the graph mentioned in the previous step. The optimisation result is a transportation graph indicating the number of bikes to be transported from one station to another in the most efficient way (Figure 2.35).

Figure 2.35: Example of redistribution output after minimum cost flow optimisation.

Leveraged data. Trips data contain several features for bike trips that took place among the stations. The features used to extract demand’s time series are: i) Trip Id, ii) Start Time, iii) End Time, iv) Start Station Id, v) End Station Id. Each day is divided into periods of 2 hours, ending with 12 time-intervals starting from 0:00 multiplied by the number of available days. For every distinct station, the number of bikes that used that station as a starting point within every time period are counted, creating a time series O_s for every station s . Next, for every distinct station the number of bikes that used that station as an ending point within every time period are counted, creating a time series I_s for every station s . Finally, the demand’s time series is defined for a station s as the difference of O_s minus I_s . Formally:

$$D(s) = O_s - I_s, \text{ for every station } s$$

Positive values of $D(s)$ at timestamp t , indicate that for the time interval t , station s had a need for bikes, because the number of trips that considered s as a starting point was greater than the number of trips that considered s as an ending point. On the other hand, negative values of $D(s)$ at timestamp t , indicates that for the time interval t , station s had a surplus of bikes, because the number of trips that considered s as an ending point was greater than the number of trips that considered s as a starting point. In that notion, stations’ network was considered as a network that can balance itself. Stations with negative predicted demand are used in the redistribution procedure, in order to provide bikes to those with positive predicted demand.

Results. Below preliminary results of the evaluation are presented, while running Bayesian optimiser for 200 iterations. The evaluation metric used for every time series forecasting was the Mean Absolute Error (MAE).

Figure 2.36: Results' box plots regarding MAE.

Figure 2.37: Best Trials per algorithm: x-axis: Frequency of the optimization procedures (one for each bike station) according to required iterations, y-axis : Number of iterations for the optimization algorithm to find the optimal configuration. (Upper) MLP Search and (Lower) XGBoost Search

It was observed that for both MLP and XGBoost regressors that were used during experimentation, a relatively low mean error was obtained. Particularly, a bike station can typically hold up to 32 bikes, but due to the employed problem formulation, information was compressed in 2-hour intervals. In Figure 2.36 the

box plots of the forecasting model results for every station, are provided. The appearance of outliers indicates that there are some time series that require further examination, which it is expected to be tackled with the inclusion of more forecasting models and further improvements to the optimisation procedure.

From our experiments, it was observed that more iterations are required for MLP to find a suitable set of hyperparameters compared to XGBoost regressor. Specifically, most of the timeseries require over 125 iterations, while for XGBoost the best observation was found for around 160 time series during the first 25 iterations.

2.5.5 Next steps

Future plans for the ‘Privacy-preserving FL’ service include extension of the proposal to consider also mixed effects between input data, e.g., through spline transformers that consider products between features instead of applying spline transformers individually. Investigate if the encryption protocol can be adapted to incorporate kernel-based approaches since they tend to capture more complex relations on data.

Regarding ‘Algorithm Selection & Hyperparameter Tuning/AutoML’ service, in the next months, three actions are planned to accelerate optimisation procedure, provide more accurate results and introduce a green dimension to the approach.

- 1) Inclusion of more timeseries forecasting models: Right now, our service includes 2 regressors for timeseries forecasting, namely a) multilayer perceptron and b) XGBoost regressor. The primary target is to include more models, out of which an algorithm selection such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) among others, can be conducted.
- 2) Meta-Knowledge Repository (MKR): One of the future goals is to leverage historic data provided by Serveo, to enhance our approach on new data sets at hand. Specifically, a repository that contains results over extensive model optimisation on available time series will be created to build meta-learning models capable of model selection or warm starting the optimisation procedure. Such addition will lead to fewer iterations for the optimiser to find the best model along with hyperparameters. A similar approach is already implemented in the clustering sub-module.
- 3) Green Bayesian Optimisation: Finally, the Exploration/Exploitation strategy of the optimisation algorithm will be reconsidered to take into account the energy footprint of specific hyperparameters. The goal is to minimise how often these hyperparameters are selected for evaluation testing, thus decreasing the carbon footprint of the whole AutoML procedure.

2.6 Explainable AI/Feature Learning with Privacy Preservation

This section addresses explainability of supervised and unsupervised approaches, with the former being addressed by feature learning, and the latter is addressed by clustering.

2.6.1 Description of Explainable feature learning service

Feature learning combines a multitude of techniques that address improved data representation for increasing performance of ML models (refer to Appendix I for more details). This section describes an efficient iterative learning approach for explainable feature learning, aiming to exploit non-linear interdependencies between features and thus improves the classification efficiency of any classifier and at the same time helps

in knowledge discovery. For this purpose, it introduces two thresholds that allow for controlling output feature complexity, while each iteration consists of the following three steps:

- Feature construction, which creates a new feature space from an initial feature space by applying arithmetic operations on pairs of input numeric features and concatenation of categorical features.
- A feature evaluation that estimates the quality of a single feature by probability distributions agreement between values belonging to different classes.
- Feature selection, where high-quality uncorrelated features are selected for the next iteration using a graph cut based on two input thresholds. Graph nodes represent features with associated weights that determine their quality, while graph edge weights determine the similarities between them.

As such, the explainable feature learning approach described herein extends on the method proposed by Vlahek and Mongus [16] by considering additional feature construction operators for dealing with the categorical variables. In the following three subsections, each step is presented separately, followed by a brief overview of ongoing efforts to improve the energy efficiency of this approach.

Feature construction. In this step, a set of new features is generated from the inputted ones by recombining them using traditional mathematical operators (i.e. +, -, *, /), while concatenation is applied when considering categorical features. As division and subtraction are not commutative, but are dependent on the order of the operands, the number of new features they produce is equal to $2N(N - 1)$, where N is the number of input features. On the other hand, multiplication and addition generate $N(N - 1)$ features, as $N(N-1)/2$ features are generated by each. The number of all new features during each iteration with arithmetic operators is, thus, equal to $3N(N - 1)$. In addition to these, given K categorical features, an additional $K(N+K-1)$ concatenated features are constructed, adding up to a total number of $3N^2 - N + KN + K^2 - K$ new features being constructed in each iteration.

Feature evaluation. Each newly constructed feature requires evaluation of its quality. For this purpose, the probability distribution agreement between values belonging to different classes is being used. This is defined as the common area between two probability density functions [17], where a low probability distribution agreement corresponds to a high discriminability between classes and improves the trade-off between between-class and within-class variance. The area of agreement also directly corresponds to the expected classification error rate. In discrete space, the matching of probability distributions can be easily and directly assessed by masking between histograms of feature classes. Thus, in order to estimate feature quality, a histogram of feature values of each individual class is estimated and the proportion of overlapping values is estimated, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 2.38: Probability distributions agreement of classes c_0 and c_1 in case of an arbitrary feature with the range $[0,12]$.

Feature selection. The key objective of feature selection is to extract a subset of high-quality uncorrelated features from a set of inputs and newly created features at each iteration. For this purpose, a weighted fully connected graph is constructed with nodes defined by the individual features. While node-weights are given by the quality assessments of features, edge-weights are defined by the correlation between the features a given edge is linking. Two thresholds are applied during the construction, removing all features that are not of sufficient quality and all edges weighted with low correlations from the initial graph. Accordingly, graph cut is then applied by selecting first the feature with the highest quality and cutting (removing) from the graph all of its neighbours. As shown in Figure 2.39 below, this is repeated until all nodes are disconnected.

Figure 2.39: Features selection on (a) the initial graph G , where in steps (b) – (e) features of the highest quality (red) are selected and their neighbours (blue) are removed.

2.6.2 Description of Interpretable Clustering (ParTree Clustering Algorithm) service

The problem of understanding and explaining a clustering result has been tackled mainly using two strategies: a) create balanced trees and reduce the average distance between points in the same partition as much as possible (thus aiming at cluster compactness in a way similar to centre-based methods like k-Means [18]), and b) determine the partitioning features by optimising some metric, either locally or globally (refer to Appendix I for more details).

The objective is to enhance the interpretability of unsupervised learning algorithms, focusing on the interpretability of clustering algorithms in two key aspects: understanding the insights gained from the record-to-cluster assignment, and understanding the logic used by the algorithm to partition the data.

2.6.2.1 Partition-Tree Clustering

Given a set of n records $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$, where each observation is a d -dimensional vector, the clustering problem consists in partitioning X into $k < n$ disjoint sets (or clusters) $C = \{C_1, \dots, C_k\}$, such that C is optimal in terms of homogeneity and simplicity, i.e., similar records belong to the same clusters and the number of clusters is small. The goal is to define an algorithm that, given the dataset X , not only returns the clustering C , but also offers a way to humanly understand the logic used by the algorithm to obtain the clustering.

With this aim, the Partitioning Tree (ParTree) is introduced as an interpretable tree-based clustering method that, besides the record to cluster assignments, returns an unsupervised binary tree describing the partitioning logic adopted. ParTree is based on hierarchical top-down iterative bisections to find the best feature to partition the data. Unlike bisecting k-Means [18], the crucial point of ParTree is that the data partitioning at every tree level is done by selecting a unique feature-value to separate the data to guarantee

cohesion among the records in the same partition. Indeed, ParTree aims at guaranteeing interpretability without sacrificing the clustering quality.

Figure 2.40: ParTree application on the iris dataset. Partitioning logic as rules (1st plot, number within parenthesis are absolute and relative number of records in a cluster); partitioning logic as scatter plot (2nd), iris classes (3rd)

The above Figure 2.40 shows the clustering of ParTree on the iris dataset. On the left is reported the partitioning logic learned by ParTree. The central plot shows the effect of the axis-parallel partitioning w.r.t. the features in the rules. By comparing this plot with the right one reporting the iris classes it can be revealed how ParTree, without any knowledge of the class, retrieved that setosa flowers can be recognized by the smallest petal lengths (cl. 0), while the remaining flowers are partitioned into versicolor (cl. 2) and ‘normal’-virginica (cl. 1), still w.r.t. petal length. The ‘anomalous’-virginica, in cluster 3, are separated w.r.t. petal width from the rest. In the following, we describe the overall algorithm.

2.6.2.2 ParTree Algorithm

In line with Guidotti et al. [19], and Pelleg and Moore [20], ParTree adopts a top-down, divide-and-conquer strategy. It starts from a set containing a single cluster, then, iteratively tries to partition a cluster in two sub-clusters. The general schema of ParTree is illustrated in Algorithm 3 [21]. It starts by initialising an empty set of sets C containing the clustering result (line 1) and by building the root of the tree R containing the whole dataset X (line 2). Then, it pushes both C and R into a priority queue Q that keeps track of the set of candidate clusters to be considered for partitioning (line 3). The priority of the objects in the queue is given by a $qs(\bullet)$ function that can be implemented in different ways. In our experiments, we considered the size of the cluster.

At each iteration, a candidate cluster C and the tree node N modelling C are extracted from Q (line 5). If C is too small (min_sample) to be partitioned or the tree node N is too deep (max_depth), then C is added to the clustering result C , N is turned into a leaf L , and the control passes to the next iteration (lines 6–8). On the other hand, the partitioning of C is performed by $make_split(\bullet)$ (line 9) that returns a binary partitioning function f , as well as the partitioning obtained by f on C , i.e., C_1, C_2 , such that $C = C_1 \cup C_2$. Alternative ways to implement $make_split(\bullet)$ are illustrated in the remainder of this section. After that, ParTree calculates the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) [20] on C and on the two sub-clusters C_1, C_2 (lines 10–11). If the data partitioning of C into C_1 and C_2 is not advantageous enough than keeping C united w.r.t. the BIC score, then C is added to the clustering result C , N is turned into a leaf L , and the control passes to the next iteration (lines 10–12). Otherwise, if the data partitioning is advantageous, the tree nodes N_l and N_r are created for sub-clusters C_1 and C_2 (line 13) and linked to the parent node together with the partitioning function f (line 14). After that, the novel candidate clusters C_1, C_2 with N_l, N_r are pushed into (line 15). The $\epsilon \in [0, 1]$ parameter controls to which extent the BIC of the children must be lower than the BIC of the parent w.r.t. the absolute BIC of the parent. If $\epsilon > 0$ the condition to stop the partitioning is relaxed which allows to obtain more clusters.

Algorithm 3: PARTREE($X, \text{max_clusters}, \text{max_depth}, \text{min_sample}, \varepsilon$)

Input : X - dataset, max_clusters - max number of clusters, max_depth - max tree depth, min_sample - min cluster size, ε - percentage of BIC parent discount
Param : qs - queue score function
Output: C - clustering, R - clustering tree

```

1  $C \leftarrow \emptyset$ ; // init. clustering result
2  $\mathcal{R} \leftarrow \text{make\_node}(X)$ ; // init. tree root
3  $\mathcal{Q} \leftarrow \text{push}(\mathcal{Q}, qs(X), \langle X, \mathcal{R} \rangle)$ ; // init. priority queue
4 while  $|\mathcal{Q}| > 0 \wedge |C| + |\mathcal{Q}| < \text{max\_clusters}$  do
5    $\langle C, \mathcal{N} \rangle \leftarrow \text{pop}(\mathcal{Q})$ ; // extract tree node from queue
6   if  $|C| < \text{min\_sample} \vee \text{depth}(\mathcal{N}) > \text{max\_depth}$  then
7      $C \leftarrow C \cup \{C\}$ ;  $\mathcal{L} \leftarrow \text{make\_leaf}(\mathcal{N})$ ; // add cluster and make leaf
8     continue; // go next iteration
9    $f, C_1, C_2 \leftarrow \text{make\_split}(C)$  // make split
10  if  $\text{bic}(C) < \text{bic}([C_1, C_2]) - \varepsilon |\text{bic}(C)|$  then
11     $C \leftarrow C \cup \{C\}$ ;  $\mathcal{L} \leftarrow \text{make\_leaf}(\mathcal{N})$ ; // add cluster and make leaf
12    continue; // go next iteration
13   $\mathcal{N}_l \leftarrow \text{make\_node}(C_1)$ ;  $\mathcal{N}_r \leftarrow \text{make\_node}(C_2)$ ; // make left and right node
14   $\mathcal{N} \leftarrow \text{update\_node}(f, \mathcal{N}_l, \mathcal{N}_r)$  // update tree
15   $\mathcal{Q} \leftarrow \text{push}(\mathcal{Q}, qs(C_1), \langle C_1, \mathcal{N}_l \rangle)$ ;  $\mathcal{Q} \leftarrow \text{push}(\mathcal{Q}, qs(C_2), \langle C_2, \mathcal{N}_r \rangle)$ ; // update queue
16 while  $|\mathcal{Q}| > 0$  do
17    $\langle C, \mathcal{N} \rangle \leftarrow \text{pop}(\mathcal{Q})$ ; // extract tree node from queue
18    $C \leftarrow C \cup \{C\}$ ;  $\mathcal{L} \leftarrow \text{make\_leaf}(\mathcal{N})$ ; // add cluster and make leaf
19 return  $C, \mathcal{R}$ ;
  
```

ParTree termination is controlled by three conditions: (i) the maximum number of admissible clusters (max_clusters), (ii) the maximum admissible tree depth (max_depth), (iii) if it is worth to split the clusters obtained so far w.r.t. the BIC criterion. The while-loop (lines 4–15) ends either when \mathcal{Q} is empty or when the number of candidate clusters and the clusters contained in the clustering result exceeds max_clusters . If the queue is not empty after the first while-loop, a further loop completes the clustering and the tree construction (lines 16–18). Finally, it returns the clustering and the unsupervised binary partitioning tree. We highlight that the selection of the best splitting attribute ($\text{make_split}(\cdot)$) can be done in parallel since the search is made independently among the various attributes. The computational complexity of ParTree is $O(\text{It} \cdot n \cdot d \cdot s)$, where It is the number of iterations required to stop the algorithm, and s is the cost of the splitting strategy adopted. This leads to a theoretical worst case of $O(d^3 n^3 \log n)$, which yet in normal situations is expected to boil down to $O(d^2 n \log^2 n)$, thus almost linear in the number of records and quadratic in the number of initial features. In the following, three different implementations of ParTree $\text{make_split}(\cdot)$ are defined, fulfilling different partitioning principles.

2.6.2.2.1 Centre-based Split

Inspired by bisecting k-Means [18], Centre-based ParTree (CPT) employs a centre-based strategy. The pseudocode of CPT is reported in Algorithm 4 [21]. CPT tests each feature j and value t (lines 2–3) to find the best axis-parallel split (lines 4–5) to partition X based on the centres μ_a, μ_b of the two partitions (line 8). The goal is to optimise local compactness using a single axis-parallel split. The partitioning leading to the smallest weighted average Mean Squared Error (MSE) is selected as best split (lines 9–11). The CPT split can be parameterized w.r.t. (i) the distance function $\text{dist}(\cdot)$ used to calculate the distance between the records and its centre contributing for the MSE, and (ii) the function $\text{get_centroids}(\cdot)$ used to calculate the centroids. These functions can be adapted to different types of data, by using appropriate distance measures and feature aggregators. For continuous features the Euclidean distance is used for dist and of the mean values for every feature for get_centroids (like in k-Means), while for categorical features Jaccard distance can be used for dist and the mode values for get_centroids (like in k-Modes). Thus, CPT can be used on any data type, also mixed, if the appropriate functions are provided. Without loss of generality, the values of each feature are normalised.

Algorithm 4: CPT_split(X)

```

Input :  $X$  - dataset
Param :  $dist$  - distance function,  $get\_centroids$  - calculate centroids,
Output:  $f$  - binary partitioning function,  $C_1, C_2$  - cluster partitions
1  $j^* \leftarrow \infty; t^* \leftarrow \infty; MSE^* \leftarrow \infty;$  // init. split feature, threshold, best MSE
2 for  $j \in [1, d]$  do // for every feature
3   for  $t \in values(X^{(j)})$  do // for every value
4      $f \leftarrow make\_partitioner(cond(X^{(j)}, t));$  // build data partitioner
5      $X_a, X_b \leftarrow split\_data(f, X);$  // make binary partitions
6     if  $|X_a| = 0 \vee |X_b| = 0$  then
7       continue; // go next iteration
8      $\mu_a, \mu_b \leftarrow get\_centroids(X_a, X_b);$  // make centroid
9      $MSE \leftarrow \frac{1}{|X|} (\sum_{x \in X_a} dist^2(\mu_a, x) + \sum_{x \in X_b} dist^2(\mu_b, x));$  // calculate MSE
10    if  $MSE < MSE^*$  then // if better partitioning
11       $j^* \leftarrow j; t^* \leftarrow t; MSE^* \leftarrow MSE;$  // update split feature, thr, MSE
12   $f \leftarrow make\_partitioner(cond(X^{(j^*)}, t^*));$  // build data partitioner
13   $C_1, C_2 \leftarrow split\_data(f, X);$  // make binary partitions
14  return  $f, C_1, C_2;$ 

```

2.6.2.2.2 Impurity-based Split

Inspired by Decision Tree models for classification and regression [18], Impurity-based ParTree (IPT) adopts an impurity-based strategy. The pseudo-code of IPT is reported in Algorithm 5 [21]. The objective of IPT is to use impurity measures, such as Gini Index and Entropy for classification and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and R2 score for regression, to optimise the impurity w.r.t. the various features for an axis-parallel split. Since the problem is unsupervised and there is no target variable, the impurity measures cannot be directly adopted. Instead, given a partitioning of X into X_a and X_b w.r.t. an axis-parallel split on feature j value t , the impurity is estimated by first computing the impurity values taking each remaining feature l ($l \neq j$) as target, and then aggregating the results (lines 8–13). IPT solves the problem of requiring a notion of (i) distance, (ii) centroids. IPT split is parameterized w.r.t. (i) the impurity function(s), and (ii) $agg_fun(\cdot)$ used to aggregate the list of impurities H (line 13). If l is a continuous feature MAPE or non-negative R2 are used, i.e., R2 where values smaller than zero are considered zero, while if l is a categorical feature the Gini Index or the normalized Entropy are used, as they all take values between 0 and 1. As aggregation function $agg_fun(\cdot)$, similarly to Complete-Linkage, experimentation was made by using minimum, maximum and average values. IPT does not require to normalise the data as the features are all analysed independently from each other.

Algorithm 5: IPT_split(X)

```

Input :  $X$  - dataset
Param : impurity - impurity function,  $agg\_fun$  - impurity aggregation function
Output:  $f$  - binary partitioning function,  $C_1, C_2$  - cluster partitions
1  $j^* \leftarrow \infty; t^* \leftarrow \infty; h^* \leftarrow \infty;$  // init. split feature, threshold, best impurity
2 for  $j \in [1, d]$  do // for every feature
3   for  $t \in values(X^{(j)})$  do // for every value
4      $f \leftarrow make\_partitioner(cond(X^{(j)}, t));$  // build data partitioner
5      $X_a, X_b \leftarrow split\_data(f, X);$  // make binary partitions
6     if  $|X_a| = 0 \vee |X_b| = 0$  then
7       continue; // go next iteration
8      $H \leftarrow \emptyset;$  // init. impurity list
9     for  $l \in [1, d] \wedge l \neq j$  do // for every target feature
10       $h_a \leftarrow impurity(X_a^{(l)}); h_b \leftarrow impurity(X_b^{(l)});$  // calculate impurities
11       $h \leftarrow \frac{|X_a|}{|X|} h_a + \frac{|X_b|}{|X|} h_b;$  // calculate total impurity
12       $H \leftarrow H \cup \{h\};$  // update impurity list
13       $h' \leftarrow agg\_fun(H);$  // aggregate impurities
14      if  $h' < h^*$  then // if better partitioning
15         $j^* \leftarrow j; t^* \leftarrow t; h^* \leftarrow h';$  // update split feature, thr, MSE
16   $f \leftarrow make\_partitioner(cond(X^{(j^*)}, t^*));$  // build data partitioner
17   $C_1, C_2 \leftarrow split\_data(f, X);$  // make binary partitions
18  return  $f, C_1, C_2;$ 

```

2.6.2.2.3 Principal Component-based Split

Principal-based ParTree (PPT), with pseudo-code in Algorithm 6, is inspired by [22], [23], [24], [25], by Oblique Decision Trees [26] and Householder reflection [27]. The intuition is that principal components are capturing as much variance as possible, and they are orthogonal each other. PPT first runs a dimensionality reduction algorithm on X to obtain a reduced version A . For a continuous dataset, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) can be used, for a categorical dataset Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA) [28], and for a mixed dataset Factor Analysis of Mixed Data [29]. After that, the principal components $A(j)$ are used as target variables of a decision tree regressor f with a single split (line 4) that is used to identify the axis-parallel split that better predicts the principal component values of the data. Depending on data partition X , one of the first nbr_components principal components is used to separate X w.r.t. one of X features. Finally, the goodness of each partitioning is measured using the BIC (lines 8–10). The PPT split can be parameterized w.r.t. the number of components nbr_components and, like CPT, it requires to normalize the dataset before usage.

Algorithm 6: PPT_split(X)

```

Input :  $X$  - dataset
Param :  $\text{nbr\_components}$  - number of components
Output:  $f$  - binary partitioning function,  $C_1, C_2$  - cluster partitions
1  $j^* \leftarrow \infty; t^* \leftarrow \infty; bs^* \leftarrow \infty;$  // init. split feature, threshold, best BIC
2  $A \leftarrow \text{get\_PCA}(X, \text{nbr\_components});$  // calculate PCA
3 for  $j \in [1, \text{nbr\_components}]$  do // for every principal component
4 |  $f \leftarrow \text{train\_tree\_regressor}(X, A^{(j)});$  // build data partitioner
5 |  $X_a, X_b \leftarrow \text{split\_data}(f, X);$  // make binary partitions
6 | if  $|X_a| = 0 \vee |X_b| = 0$  then
7 | | continue; // go next iteration
8 | |  $bs \leftarrow \text{bic}(X_a, X_b);$  // calculate BIC partitions
9 | | if  $bs < bs^*$  then // if better partitioning
10 | | |  $j^* \leftarrow j; t^* \leftarrow t; bs^* \leftarrow bs;$  // update split feature, thr, BIC
11  $f \leftarrow \text{train\_tree\_regressor}(X, A^{(j^*)});$  // build data partitioner
12  $C_1, C_2 \leftarrow \text{split\_data}(f, X);$  // make binary partitions
13 return  $f, C_1, C_2;$ 

```

2.6.3 Evaluation of Interpretable Clustering (ParTree Clustering Algorithm) service

In this section, the performance evaluation of ParTree, implemented in Python, is conducted across different datasets, and compared against a wide array of (non-interpretable) competitors.

2.6.3.1 Datasets and Competitors

The evaluation encompasses 18 synthetic datasets and 15 real datasets taken by UCI and Kaggle. The synthetic datasets are all continuous and typically bi-dimensional, while real datasets are composed also by categorical attributes. The datasets are grouped as follows: $DS1$ continuous synthetic datasets, $DS2$ continuous real datasets, i.e., real datasets with one-hot encoded categorical attributes, $DS3$ categorical real datasets, i.e., real datasets with continuous attributes turned into categorical ones through equal-width binning with 20 bins, $DS4$ mixed real datasets, i.e., the datasets remain as they are. After that, categorical attributes in $DS3$ and $DS4$ are turned into labels for processing by the clustering methods, and all the datasets are normalised using z-score normalisation.

ParTree is compared with traditional clustering algorithms and with tree-based competitors. Competitors include k-Means, bisecting k-Means, Balanced Iterative Reducing and Clustering using Hierarchies (BIRCH), Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN), Ordering Points To Identify the Clustering Structure (OPTICS) and the Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering (AHC) single/complete/ward linkage approaches as implemented by scikit-learn, x-Means [20] as implemented by pyclustering, and k-Modes. Tree-based competitors consist of Clustering Through Decision Tree (CLTree) [30] that provides a

usable Python implementation. Furthermore, we implemented k-Means-Tree [31] by combining the scikit-learn k-Means and Decision Tree classifier, and inspired by [32], a variant of ParTree using the maximum variance as indicator to identify the feature-values to use for partitioning (VPT).

2.6.3.2 Experimental Setting

Table 2.7 shows the average values of the measures obtained by the 14 algorithms and their average rank for the different dataset types. In this table, for space-saving purposes, the following abbreviations were employed for the algorithms: CLTree (CLT), k-Means-Tree (kMT), k-Means (kM), bisecting k-Means (bkM), x-Means (xM), k-Modes (kMd), BIRCH (BIR), DBSCAN (DBS), and OPTICS (OPT).

k-Means is the best performer overall, while the second-best performer is the AHC, especially w.r.t. FMS that is meant to adequately judge the performance of hierarchical clustering algorithm. The best tree-based clustering algorithm is often a ParTree method. Among the synthetic datasets *DS1*, CPT is the best algorithm for NMI, ARI, and FMS. On the other hand, among the real datasets *DS2*, *DS3*, and *DS2*, independently from the data type representation, PPT is the best method for NMI and ARI, and is on par with IPT for FMS. Besides the quality measures, also w.r.t. runtime, PPT is competitive with the traditional clustering algorithms and better or on par with k-Means-Tree, i.e., k-Means followed by a Decision Tree. Notably, ParTree methods are considerably better than the unique tree-based method with a usable implementation, i.e., CLTree.

Table 2.7: Experimental results. For each algorithm and dataset, we report the performance of the best parameter configuration w.r.t. SIL. The overall highest value per measure is in bold while the highest among tree-based methods is in italic and blue.

	DS1					DS2				
	NMI ↑ avg rnk	ARI ↑ avg rnk	FMS ↑ avg rnk	SIL ↑ avg rnk	Time ↓ avg rnk	NMI ↑ avg rnk	ARI ↑ avg rnk	FMS ↑ avg rnk	SIL ↑ avg rnk	Time ↓ avg rnk
CPT	.80 5.5	.72 5.1	.81 5.4	.59 5.1	1.2 11.0	.54 1.7	.56 1.7	.83 4.0	.32 6.2	16.8 10.5
IPT	.48 10.8	.39 10.3	.65 9.3	.42 11.0	1.9 10.4	.30 5.0	.26 6.0	.71 6.5	.32 6.7	14.7 9.5
PPT	.77 6.6	.69 6.3	.78 6.6	.57 6.9	<i>0.1</i> 5.3	.69 2.0	.70 2.0	.85 2.0	.35 5.0	0.2 3.3
VPT	.66 8.3	.50 8.5	.66 8.7	.51 8.6	0.9 10.8	.01 6.0	.02 8.0	.65 7.6	.24 5.6	1.2 8.0
CLT	.10 13.2	.03 13.1	.46 12.5	.02 13.2	25.4 13.9	.01 3.5	<0 6.5	.69 3.0	<0 11.0	>100 11.0
kMT	.72 8.0	.58 7.1	.71 7.5	.54 7.6	0.1 5.6	.23 4.7	.24 3.1	.70 5.1	.37 5.0	0.4 5.0
kM	.83 4.2	.71 4.7	.79 5.0	.61 2.1	0.1 5.7	.23 2.7	.24 2.1	.71 4.7	.38 3.0	0.5 5.8
bkM	.79 6.2	.71 5.6	.79 5.9	.59 4.8	0.1 7.8	.23 2.7	.24 2.1	.71 4.7	.38 3.0	0.5 5.7
xM	.85 3.6	.76 4.3	.83 4.6	.63 1.6	0.0 2.4	.22 4.8	.21 4.8	.73 3.2	.51 2.2	0.1 1.8
kMd	.00 13.5	<0 13.3	.47 12.6	<0 13.7	0.1 7.7	.10 8.4	.11 6.7	.65 7.1	.05 10.8	5.9 8.1
BIR	.80 5.1	.68 5.8	.77 5.8	.58 5.6	0.1 4.5	.21 5.4	.21 6.7	.69 6.2	.32 5.8	1.0 5.2
AHC	.85 2.8	.74 3.3	.82 3.6	.60 3.4	0.1 4.2	.13 6.1	.10 6.4	.77 2.7	.64 1.0	1.6 4.2
DBS	.81 3.8	.75 3.6	.82 3.7	.54 7.2	0.0 2.2	.12 8.1	.10 7.5	.73 6.2	.33 7.7	1.2 3.4
OPT	.51 10.0	.36 10.1	.58 10.2	.38 10.9	4.7 12.8	.15 5.2	.10 6.7	.57 5.5	.26 7.5	90.7 10.8

	DS3					DS4				
	NMI ↑ avg rnk	ARI ↑ avg rnk	FMS ↑ avg rnk	SIL ↑ avg rnk	Time ↓ avg rnk	NMI ↑ avg rnk	ARI ↑ avg rnk	FMS ↑ avg rnk	SIL ↑ avg rnk	Time ↓ avg rnk
CPT	.13 5.4	.10 6.8	.59 7.3	.12 11.0	22.7 10.7	.13 5.3	.10 6.5	.59 7.0	.12 10.8	21.9 9.7
IPT	.11 6.0	.10 6.5	.66 4.5	.17 9.7	1.1 7.5	.11 6.2	.10 6.7	.66 4.7	.17 10.5	1.1 7.0
PPT	.25 3.5	.26 3.1	.66 6.3	.28 7.8	0.9 6.2	.25 3.7	.26 3.2	.66 6.6	.28 8.2	0.9 5.8
VPT	.10 6.4	.09 7.7	.64 5.8	.34 8.2	1.4 6.6	.13 5.5	.14 5.6	.64 6.5	.44 6.5	3.9 10.0
CLT	.11 5.1	.08 8.1	.59 7.1	<0 13.5	>100 14.0	.11 5.2	.08 8.2	.59 7.8	<0 13.7	>100 14.0
kMT	.13 6.6	.13 5.2	.63 5.5	.48 4.2	0.6 6.3	.14 6.5	.14 5.4	.63 6.1	.48 4.5	0.6 6.1
kM	.17 5.4	.17 3.0	.62 5.6	.46 2.6	0.6 8.3	.18 4.9	.17 3.1	.62 6.1	.46 3.2	0.5 6.9
bkM	.18 5.0	.17 2.9	.63 5.2	.46 2.9	1.0 8.0	.18 5.2	.17 3.0	.63 5.7	.46 3.6	0.9 7.6
xM	.18 4.9	.17 3.9	.61 6.6	.45 2.9	0.1 1.7	.17 6.1	.15 4.5	.64 5.2	.49 2.6	0.1 2.3
kMd	.08 6.7	.06 6.2	.57 8.3	.08 11.6	2.2 8.7	.09 6.5	.09 6.2	.60 6.8	.10 11.5	1.6 8.3
BIR	.16 6.3	.15 6.1	.63 6.4	.40 5.3	1.9 5.3	.16 6.3	.15 6.4	.63 6.0	.42 5.2	1.7 5.3
AHC	.07 7.6	.06 8.6	.68 3.3	.60 1.6	4.3 3.3	.07 8.0	.06 8.6	.68 3.2	.61 1.6	3.7 3.3
DBS	.09 8.4	.06 9.0	.67 5.2	.35 7.3	1.6 3.8	.09 7.7	.06 9.3	.67 5.2	.35 7.7	1.6 3.7
OPT	.15 5.1	.08 7.3	.52 7.0	.20 8.6	65.2 12.8	.16 4.8	.08 7.3	.53 7.0	.23 8.5	62.9 12.6

The comparison of the ranks of all methods against each other considering all datasets and types is visually represented in Figure 2.41 below with Critical Difference diagrams [33]. Two methods are tied if the null hypothesis that their performance is the same cannot be rejected using the Nemenyi test at $\alpha=0.05$. It can be noticed that for NMI and ARI, the methods are compactly tied to each other but having PPT and CPT in the top-5 together with the centroids-based methods k-Means, bisecting k-Means and x-Means. For FMS, the top-7 should be considered to find PPT and CPT, which are overtaken by AHC and DBS besides k-Means, bisecting k-Means and x-Means. Finally, for SIL, the performances of ParTree methods are slightly worse. However, PPT performance is not statistically worse than k-Means-Tree, the best tree-based clustering method w.r.t. SIL, as they are tied in the Critical Difference plot. Furthermore, k-Means-Tree first applies k-Means and then a Decision Tree that uses as target variable the cluster labels. Similarly to CUBT [34], this causes an inconsistency in the tree-based logic of the clustering structure, as two different records satisfying different conditions in the tree can be assigned to the same cluster. On the other hand, for ParTree methods, this cannot happen by construction, making ParTree the best interpretable-by-design tree-based clustering method. Moreover, the SIL measure, and other internal evaluation measures, are influenced by the distance function used to estimate it. In contrast, the external validation measures NMI, ARI, and FMS are more objective as they report the agreement between the returned and expected clustering assignments. Therefore, the good performance of ParTree methods is even more remarkable, considering that the best parameter configuration has been selected w.r.t. SIL. Thus, SIL can be used for an unsupervised parameter tuning of ParTree.

Figure 2.41: Critical Difference plots with Nemenyi at 95% confidence among all datasets.

2.6.3.3 User study

In this section, the user study carried out to evaluate the interpretability of various clustering algorithms is described. Firstly, the aim is to investigate whether users, when assigning a record to a cluster, i.e., trying to repeat the same logic followed by a clustering algorithm, make fewer mistakes using a tree rather than other clustering visualisations like centroids or dendrograms. Secondly, the objective is to determine if the tree resulting from ParTree has a lower cognitive effort and offers higher usability than other clustering summarisations. As competitors, (i) the centroids returned by k-Means represented with a parallel plot, and (ii) the dendrogram returned by AHC were selected. k-Means and AHC were chosen based on their effectiveness in the benchmarking in the previous section and their widespread adoption. ParTree is not compared against other tree-based clustering algorithms, as in the previous section, ParTree has been assessed as the best tree-based clustering algorithm. Additionally, since all methods in this family return a tree, there is small interest in comparing different trees, while on the contrary it is interesting to check if a tree is more interpretable than the visualisations available from traditional non-tree-based clustering algorithms.

The experiment consists in providing a user with a record x and a clustering visualisation in terms of tree, centroids, or dendrogram and ask to the user to insert x into the right cluster. For all the visualisations, distances between x and the clusters are not provided to avoid biasing the user towards a number that might be unable to understand and to entirely judge how much a user can really exploit the different clustering representations provided. Thus, the hypotheses are as follows. By comparing the correctness of the assignments, i.e., correspondence of matches between users' assignments and real cluster assignments, i.e., the Success Rate, the clustering interpretability and usability can be evaluated. HP1: ParTree visualisation makes users perform better in terms of Success Rate than the competitors. Cognitive Effort is assessed by means of the NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) questionnaire [35], and the clustering visualisation Usability with the System Causability Scale (SCS) [36]. It is expected that the tree-based visualisation of ParTree illustrates the clustering logic in a clearer way than the competitors because, at the cognitive level, following precise partitioning steps on a tree is easier than simultaneously comparing a set of features on centroids or on a dendrogram. HP2: ParTree visualisation requires a lower cognitive effort than the competitors as NASA-TLK. HP3: ParTree visualisation provides better usability than the competitors as SCS.

2.6.3.3.1 Experimental Setting

The experiment was conducted using data from home and diabetes datasets, from which three records were randomly selected. For ParTree, the CPT version was adopted. Parameters of CPT, k-Means, and AHC were set to obtain 5 clusters for home and 10 clusters for diabetes, respectively.

Figure 2.42: Clustering visualisations for home. Top: ParTree; bottom, from left to right: k-Means, AHC.

Figure 2.42 above shows the visualisations for home. More details are available in the repository, including the clustering logics provided to user study participants. The online experiment was conducted using the Qualtrics platform with data collected from 40 participants with a background in Computer Science and Data Science with an average age of 26 ranging from 22 to 37 years old. Participants were asked to assign a record to a cluster using CPT, k-Means and AHC for home ('easy' task, with 7 features and 5 clusters) and diabetes ('difficult' task, with 8 features and 10 clusters). Subsequently, they were asked to express their confidence

in the accomplishment of the task. To prevent any learning effect, each participant used different yet analogous records for each algorithm. Then, to prevent any order effect, participants were presented with randomized orders for the complexity and for the algorithms.

2.6.3.3.2 Results

Figure 2.43 below (left) illustrates the Success Rate in the record to cluster assignment. It is clear that users find it easier to correctly assign a record to a cluster by following the tree logic by reasoning on one feature after the other, instead of considering all the features simultaneously with parallel plots and dendrograms. A one-way ANOVA test on the ST revealed that there is a statistically significant difference in performance between at least two methods. The methods were identified through the Tukey’s Honestly Significant Difference (THSD) [37] for multiple comparisons. It showed that the mean value of Success Rate is significantly different for CPT and k-Means ($p > 0.01$, 95% Confidence Interval (CI)=[0.47,0.92]) and for CPT and AHC ($p > 0.01$, 95% CI=[0.4,0.8]). This result confirms HP1. Also, the THSD found that the mean value of Success Rate is not significantly different between the easy and complex conditions ($p = 0.213$, 95% CI=[-14.6,3.3]). This lack of statistical significance holds also for the Cognitive Effort and Usability. Figure 2.43 below (centre) shows the Cognitive Effort as NASA-TLX boxplots (the lower, the better): CPT has the lowest and more compact boxplots. The THSD found that the mean value of NASA-TLX is significantly different between CPT and k-Means ($p > 0.001$, 95% CI=[-48.6,-30.6]), and between CPT and AHC ($p > 0.001$, 95% CI=[-41.9,-24.0]), while this does not happen between AHC and k-Means. Similarly, Figure 2.43 below (right) shows the Usability as SCS boxplots (the higher, the better): CPT has the highest and more compact boxplots. Also, in this case the THSD found that the mean value of SCS is significantly different between CPT and k-Means ($p > 0.001$, 95% CI=[0.18,0.11]), and between CPT and AHC ($p > 0.001$, 95% CI=[-0.04,0.09]), while again this does not happen between AHC and k-Means. These results confirm HP2 and HP3.

Figure 2.43: User study results. (left) success rate, (center) cognitive effort, (right) usability.

2.6.4 Next steps

With the first version of the service completed, future efforts will focus on performance monitoring for detection of possible service reliability issues and other improvements. Core developments will focus on service integration into pilot environments. Furthermore, due to obvious energy inefficiency of existing service implementation, as discussed in section 3, particular focus will be paid in reducing the computations used by the service itself.

The immediate next steps for developing the ‘Interpretable Clustering (ParTree Clustering Algorithm)’ service include the following actions:

- Adoption of ParTree in a real-world scenario, in particular UC#6 in the banking context. This is likely to have some specificities of the application emerge as refinements or tuning of the algorithm, which was so far tested on standard, open data sets only.
- While runtimes of ParTree have been shown to be among the best of the pool of algorithms compared, its impact in terms of energy demand have not been explored and are far from obvious. Next steps will include an evaluation of these aspects, exploiting the results of T2.5, and a tuning of

the algorithm aimed to find the best trade-off between performances (runtimes and output quality) and energy consumption.

- More on the research side, but with important implications concerning ethical aspects of real applications, fair-clustering approaches will be considered (e.g. Chierichetti et al. [38]) based on our ParTree tool, modifying its partitioning procedure in order to guarantee fair partitions, i.e., groups of records not separated w.r.t. a sensitive attribute such as sex or race.
- From a more engineering point of view, better integration of the tool in the GREEN.DAT.AI platform is foreseen. Currently, ParTree reads input/write output through files, which fits well the development phase and early testing with the UC, yet in the long term it will be required to integrate its data flows in the project infrastructure exploiting the communication channels provided.

2.7 Federated & Automatic Transfer Learning

FL involves advancements in privacy-preserving collaborative learning, allowing multiple parties to train a shared model without sharing raw data, while Automatic Transfer Learning focuses on developing algorithms capable of transferring knowledge from a pre-trained source domain to a target domain automatically, enabling efficient adaptation to new tasks or environments with minimal human intervention (refer to Appendix I for more details). This section reports the advances in the FL and Transfer Learning services, which emerged as very significant for the UCs needs. Specifically, a service of FL for time series forecasting is described in this deliverable, mainly motivated by energy demand prediction applications within the project. Transfer Learning services are currently under development, mainly addressing the needs of UC#1 and UC#5, and will be described in deliverable D3.2, due on M24.

2.7.1 Description of weighted FL (FL for timeseries forecasting) service

The service called ‘FL for timeseries forecasting’, falls under the general service named ‘(weighted)FL’ and is under development by UPRC within the context of Task 3.3, ‘Federated & Automatic Transfer Learning’. Its purpose is to predict the energy demand of EV charging points using cross-device FL [39], [40]. The prediction model aims to provide accurate forecasts of energy/power consumption, enabling better planning and optimisation of EVs charging schedule.

UC#2.1 scenario focuses on FL-enabled smart charging for EVs. The goal is to manage connected EVs’ charging under technical constraints (e.g., maximum capacity, power limit) while also maximising renewable energy utilisation. To achieve this, FedEDF is introduced, as a FEDerated learning approach for Energy/power Demand Forecasting of EVs. More specifically, the target is to train a centralised data-driven model over the decentralised datasets across edge devices (i.e., EV charging points), to estimate their corresponding power load (i.e., energy demand) in short-term. This information enables utility providers to anticipate energy/power demand and improve grid reliability in terms of power violations within the charging points’ power grid. FedEDF forecasts the future power consumption of EV points up to a set prediction horizon based on the temporal sequence of their power (W), providing insight into future demand. Each EV connection to the point results in fluctuations in terms of voltage. Grid stability is assessed by the voltage, which has to be within $\pm 10\%$ of the nominal value (e.g., 230V)

The first (prototype) version of the architecture of FedEDF is illustrated by Figure 2.44 below. Exploiting VLF-LSTM [41], our model consists of the following layers: a) an input layer of three neurons, one for each input variable, b) a single LSTM [42] hidden layer composed of 350 neurons, c) an embedding layer with one dimension for vectorising the location of the EV charger, d) a Dropout layer with probability for model

regularisation, e) a fully-connected hidden layer composed of 150 neurons, and f) an output layer of one neuron, for the output variable.

Figure 2.44 - FedEDF Architecture Overview

The input variables consist of the differences (i.e., deltas) of voltage (ΔV), current (ΔI), and power (ΔP). On the other hand, the output variables consist of the difference in power ΔP_{next} of the predicted value with respect to the current one.

2.7.2 Evaluation of weighted FL service

The training and evaluation of FedEDF use the dataset provided by INESC TEC for research purposes, within GREEN.DAT.AI. Figure 2.45 below provides a snapshot of (a part of) this dataset, consisting of 107,074 records from 8 EV charging stations distributed across 2 charging points over a temporal span of three months (Jan. 10, 2023 – Mar. 20, 2023).

Figure 2.45 - Snapshot of INESC TEC dataset; Illustrating EV chargers' demand in terms of power (W)

All conducted experiments were implemented in Python. More specifically, the aforementioned models were implemented using PyTorch¹³ and trained using Flower¹⁴ for FL, via a GPU cluster equipped with 8 Nvidia A100 GPUs, 128 CPUs, and 1TB of RAM.

¹³ PyTorch: An Imperative Style, High-Performance Deep Learning Library. <https://pytorch.org>

¹⁴ Flower: A Friendly Federated Learning Framework. <https://flower.dev>

2.7.3 Next steps

Section 2.7 presented the problem formulation of ‘FL for timeseries forecasting’, a service developed by UPRC geared towards UC2 and demonstrated the prototype architecture and FL training workflow. In the near future, the goal is to improve the architecture of the FedEDF model to increase the accuracy of the model. In a parallel line of research, in order to account for heterogeneity among EV chargers, the FL workflow of FedEDF will be improved by either fine-tuning the existing training process, or implementing newer aggregation schemes, such as work by Fallah et al. [45].

2.8 Adaptive FL for Digital Twin Applications

As follows from the definition of Task 3.4, this task builds on GemMA Fusion Suite (GFS)¹⁵ with the objective to deliver (near) real-time map generation, aiming to fulfil key functional requirements for building Digital Twins. While service architecture follows the JDL/DFIG reference data-fusion model (refer to Appendix I for more details), management of subscribed data sources (e.g. satellites, UAVs, and IoT Hubs) and internal communication protocols are developed here, thus, enabling utilisation of GREEN.DAT.AI algorithms and design new dedicated ones. This allows for rendering the behaviour of observed geospatial entities (e.g. farmlands, water bodies, or localised sensory systems), i.e. developing their digital twins. Following is an overview of service architecture.

Figure 2.48: Overall service architecture for derivation digital twin applications.

¹⁵ <https://apps.gemma.feri.um.si/gemmafusion/>

In accordance with JDL/DFIG reference model, key service layers include:

- **Level 0 services** aim at source pre-processing, ensuring all data sources are aligned in time and space, are appropriately cleaned and of sufficient quality. More specifically, map re-projections into a common coordinate system, data re-sampling into a common spatio-temporal resolution, data filtering (like detection of clouds on satellite images), and data cleaning (e.g. smoothing, morphological operations, and data implantations with interpolations), to name a few, are performed here. GemmaFusion SDK, as depicted in Figure 2.48 above with purple colour, is responsible for delivering these functionalities.
- **Level 1 services** are focused on recognising and attributing observed geospatial entities with relevant attributes extracted from multiple spatio-temporally aligned and pre-processed data sources. For this purpose, data enrichment and aggregation functionalities are implemented using geospatial querying and other geometric operations (e.g. polygon intersections, nearest neighbours, and range queries) using data-specific libraries like Geometric Tools and Wild Magic (WM5), depicted in Figure 2.48 above with purple colour. Examples of this include assigning different spectral indices extracted from satellite images (e.g. normalize vegetation difference, moisture stress, or normalised difference mud indices) to observed agricultural fields and water bodies or assigning air temperature and moisture from the closest weather station to provide complete definitions of their states.
- **Level 2 services** provide situation assessment features. For this purpose, attribute schemas are utilised to interlink observed geospatial entities with holistic representations of their contexts. As for example, the irrigation system used in UC#4 is connected here with water quality measurements and vegetation status measurements, while agricultural areas observed in UC#3 are interlinked here with past crop development observations to extract timeseries related features. As this level is obviously highly dependent on the actual use-case, its implementation is achieved in separate workspaces, as depicted in Figure 2.48 above with green colour.
- **Level 3 services:** provide impact assessment features, usually implemented by applying predictions on any of the attributes/features extracted at one of the lower levels. Accordingly, its implementation is also use-case dependant and, similarly to Level 2, implemented in separate workspaces, as depicted in Figure 2.48 above with green colour.
- **Level 4 and 5 services** ensure the rendering of the behaviour of the observed spatial entities. On one hand, this includes orchestration and management over behaviour modelling pipelines and management of intermediate data products, while also ensuring rendering and distribution of the final results (i.e. results of prediction models) on the other. The server components, as depicted in Figure 2.48 above with orange colour, are responsible to deliver this.

For the purposes of GREEN.DAT.AI, the services' architecture described above is implemented in a form of the runtime extension built on top of the Gemma Fusion SDK, which exposes APIs for building geospatial services in the C++ programming language without requiring the complex development environment setup. Each service is implemented by following a predefined common interface for data processing where all the inputs and outputs must be defined by the service itself using data structure interfaces instead of data formats. Code is then compiled into a native cross platform binary which can then be loaded into a deployed Gemma Fusion Runtime that handles the necessary input and output data conversions into the interfaces defined by the implemented service.

Accordingly, the following architecture provides a concrete instantiation for three GREEN.DAT.AI services being implemented for the purposes of adaptive FL-based digital twin applications within Task 3.4, namely

(i) orchestration framework for derivation geospatial data products, (ii) behaviour modelling pipelines, and (iii) event detection on fused datasets. In continuation of this section, each of them is discussed further.

Figure 2.49: Architecture of GREEN.DAT.AI services for Digital Twin applications.

2.8.1 Description of Orchestration Framework for Derivation Geospatial Data Products service

This service provides a basic instantiation of the developed data fusion architecture, applied on raster data. It implements data pre-processing (i.e. Level 0), definition of observed geospatial entity and its assessment (i.e. Level 1) and its visualisation in an automated manner (i.e. Levels 4 and 5), while Levels 2 and 3 are implemented as straightforward data transformations. Following are key indexes computed:

Table 2.8: List of implemented earth observation indices on top of the Sentinel 2 data products.

Index	Description	Monitoring type
NDVI	Normalised Difference Vegetation Index	Vegetation
NDMI1	Normalised Difference Moisture Index (B11)	Vegetation moisture
NDMI2	Normalised Difference Moisture Index (B12)	Vegetation moisture
GNDVI	Green Normalised Difference Vegetation Index	Vegetation
EVI	Enhanced Vegetation Index	Vegetation with reduced soil noise
AVI	Advanced Vegetation Index	Vegetation
SAVI	Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index	Vegetation with reduced soil noise
MSI	Moisture Stress Index	Vegetation moisture
GCI	Green Coverage Index	Vegetation
NBRI	Normalised Burned Ratio Index	Natural hazard
NDWI	Normalised Difference Water Index	Inland water
NDSI	Normalised Difference Snow Index	Ice, snow, glacier cover
NDGI	Normalised Difference Glacier Index	Ice, snow, glacier cover
NDBSI	Normalised Difference Bare Soil Index	Soil cover
ARVI	Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index	Vegetation
SIPI1	Structure Insensitive Pigment Index (B01)	Vegetation health
SIPI3	Structure Insensitive Pigment Index (B02)	Vegetation health
BSI	Bare Soil Index	Soil cover
SI	Shadow Index	Vegetation shadow casting
NPCRI	Normalised Pigment Chlorophyll Ratio Index	Vegetation health

MSAVI2	Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (Simplified)	Vegetation with reduced soil noise
OSAVI	Agriculture Optimised Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index	Vegetation with reduced soil noise
EVI2	Enhanced Vegetation Index (B09, B05)	Vegetation with reduced soil noise
SATVI	Soil-Adjusted Total Vegetation Index	Vegetation with reduced soil noise

As such, it provides core functionalities for assessment of the state of the agricultural fields and water bodies with spectral indices derived from the satellite images. Following are key services specifications:

- Input datasets: Sentinel 2 and cadastre data.
- Output dataset: Maps of a given spectral indices of observed geospatial entities.
- Parameters: date, observed entity id.

Figure 2.50 below demonstrates the obtained results.

Figure 2.50: Data processing flow loading two different geospatial products and producing derived spatial map.

2.8.2 Description of Behaviour Modelling Pipelines service

Behaviour modelling pipelines address predictions of various attributes related to the observed geospatial entities. At a generic level, these can be either of raster or sensory type. Accordingly, two generic pipelines were designed to be applied to different UC domains. When considering raster data, spectral indices (defined in the previous section) are of the core interest as they encapsulate the behaviour of agriculture lands as well as the observed water bodies. Here, the service is used to aggregate time series of past values of spectral index in question, while convolutional Long short-term memory (ConvLSTM) with the following architecture is utilised for predicting the next image in the series:

Figure 2.51: ConvLSTM architecture for predicting spectral indices of raster type.

Accordingly, the following are the key service specifications:

- Input datasets: A time series of spectral indices and cadastre data.
- Output dataset: Prediction maps for given spectral indices of observed geospatial entities.
- Parameters: Date, ID of the observed geospatial entity.

Figure 2.52 below is an example of the obtained results.

Figure 2.52: Prediction of crop behaviour on raster data using NDVI.

On the other hand, prediction of sensory type parameters of spatial entities is achieved using various types of regressions, depending on the actual application domain. As for example, water quality is determined by six parameters: Potential of Hydrogen, Oxidation-Reduction Potential, Conductivity, Dissolved Oxygen, Temperature, and Total Dissolved Solids. To forecast the future values of these parameters, contextual weather data obtained from the Slovenian Environment Agency were incorporated. The data consists of Minimum Temperature, Maximum Temperature, Mean Temperature, Humidity, Precipitation, Pressure, and Wind Speed. After initial temporal data alignment at 10 min. and application of feature learning services, XGBoost regressor using a 70/30 split with shuffling. In the initial tests, following results were achieved.

Table 2.9: Results of predictions of water quality behaviour parameters.

Water quality parameter	RMSE value
Potential of Hydrogen	0.1885865028587167
Oxidation - Reduction Potential	0.0020060000000000
Conductivity	2.6091955951489587
Dissolved Oxygen	0.4922223911409806
Temperature	0.1787829542309974
Total Dissolved Solids	0.4903688572365372

2.8.3 Description of Event Detection on Fused Datasets service

At a generic level, this service is implemented as abnormality detection raster or sensory data. In both cases, predictions made by behaviour modelling pipelines are compared to the actual monitored state of the observed spatial entity for this purpose and appropriate actions are specified accordingly. When considering sensory data, this is straightforwardly implemented using a predefined set of threshold values, nevertheless, detection of events on raster data is not so trivial, as this is the case for pest and disease detection. Due to the relatively low resolution of satellite images, detection here is achieved indirectly by observing the state

of crop development. However, as crops are subjected to complex environmental conditions, not all deviation from normal crop development can be attributed to the pest attacks or disease, while not all areas within the observed agricultural field may be affected equally. Thus, while general analysis of crop development may determine the level at which fertilisation or spraying can be applied, it is actual spatial distribution that needs to be further specified by the definition of the so-called spraying map, i.e. a map that is uploaded to the actual spraying equipment and determines precise amounts of fertiliser or pesticide to be applied to each particular meter of land. While anomaly detection map is in our case extended with the segmentation for precise definition of the spraying zones. In this case, image segmentation is based on a max-tree based implementation of connected operators [46] that allow for straightforward definition of local maxima (i.e. regions, where crop is well developed and spraying should be reduced), minima (i.e. regions where crops are less developed and spraying should be increased) and regions of normal crop development where reference amount of saying should be applied. The following figure shows predicted and actual crop development and the accordingly generated spraying map.

Figure 2.53: Predicted crop development map (left), actually observed crop development (centre), and accordingly generated spraying map.

Following key service specifications:

- Input datasets: Predicted and actual crop development parameter and cadastre data.
- Output dataset: Spraying map.
- Parameters: ID of the observed geospatial entity.

2.8.4 Next steps

With *Orchestration framework for derivation geospatial data products* already implemented and deployed, further activities regarding this service will include ongoing performance monitoring for detection and timely correction of all possible defaults in service execution. On the other hand, *Behaviour modelling pipelines* and *Event detection on fused datasets* are still under development. While these are being both applied to different use-case domains, the main focus will be on gradual improvements of their accuracies in each of them by the means of (i) enriching the feature space with supplementary dataset and (ii) extending the training sets, while also (iii) examining different model architectures.

Also note that in both latter cases, these services also provide a base line for addressing their energy efficiency as discussed in Section 3.

2.9 Automated IoT event-based change detection/ forecasting

Automated IoT event-based change detection and forecasting showcases algorithms tailored for real-time analysis of IoT data streams. These methods leverage event-driven architectures (for detecting anomalies,

changes, and patterns in IoT data, enabling proactive decision-making) and ML/statistical techniques (for accurate forecasting of future events/trends maintenance, etc) (refer to Appendix I for more details).

The functionality described in Task 3.5 is split into two services:

- a fully configurable data ingestion service, event-based change detection, summary statistics, and forecasting, developed by KNT and supported by INLE, henceforth referred to as the *Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox*, and
- the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’, where the core operation is pattern matching and its implementation is inspired by the Aho-Corasick algorithm [47].

In the following sections, the current as well as the prospected functionality of each service (Sections 2.9.1 and 2.9.3), the application and evaluation of each service within the scope of the project (Sections 2.9.2 and 2.9.4), and finally the workplan to achieve this (Section 2.9.5), are outlined.

2.9.1 Description of Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox

2.9.1.1 Functionality Overview

The Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox is a component planned to offer a comprehensive range of functionalities.

It will be engineered to seamlessly ingest data from various sources, including APIs, FTPs, and Data Storage systems such as different flavours of SQL and MongoDB. The ingestion process will be scheduled and fully configurable, allowing users to tailor it to their needs. The resulting data will then be stored in one of many Data Storages (sinks) supported, such as HDFS, MongoDB, or Kafka. The storage ‘folder’ structure will be organised following a structured hierarchy, ensuring easy access and management of the ingested data.

Furthermore, the component will record the output structure, whether it's in JSON, CSV, or XML; as this information is vital for understanding the data's layout and will facilitate the retrieval of statistical metrics, event triggers, and forecasts. For example, users will be able to retrieve the minimum or maximum of a particular value over a specified timeframe, or values surpassing a predefined threshold. These metrics and events can then trigger user-configurable messages sent to a fitting data sink (e.g., Kafka) to be picked up by downstream components for further processing.

To manage and orchestrate these functionalities an API as well as a user interface, providing users with an easy to use and intuitive way to orchestrate the entire process will be included. The user interface will serve as a proof of concept for the project's needs.

The driving force behind the above will be an ontology-backed GraphQL server, serving as the central hub for managing metadata, using a Neo4j deployment for its storage needs, e.g., the JSON-formatted structure of an ingestion process. This graph-stored metadata will serve two critical functions that aid different components of the service in: (i) retrieving and understanding their input and (ii) recording metadata related with their output. The service's prospective high-level architecture, illustrated in Figure 2.54 below, showcases the interconnected nature of its various components and highlights the flow of data throughout the system.

Currently, the status of the service is as follows:

In terms of offered functionality, the service supports RESTful APIs as Data Sources and HDFS as Data Sinks, with the output structure of JSON-formatted input being recorded as metadata, all of which can be easily orchestrated by users through the Python-based user interface. The current high-level architecture,

illustrated in Figure 2.55 below, presents the existing functionality with the planned final features distinguished by faded colours.

Of significant note is the ontology employed by the GraphQL server backing the entire process via Neo4j. It is in an advanced stage and supports the ‘general’ concepts of Data Sources and Data Sinks, as well as the abstract notion of output structure, regardless of it being in JSON, XML, or CSV format. The current version of this ontology is outlined in Figure 2.56 below.

Figure 2.54. Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox, high-level architecture (final)

Figure 2.55. Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox, high-level architecture (current)

Figure 2.56. Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox, GraphQL ontology (current)

2.9.1.2 Technical Specifications

The service is deployed as a Docker Compose consisting of 8 separate containers. As previously discussed, the backbone of the service is an ontology-backed GraphQL server. Specifically, the ontology illustrated in Figure 2.56 above has been translated into a GraphQL schema. This schema is then utilised by an Apollo Server, an open-source spec-compliant GraphQL server, deployed through a Node.js 18 Docker container, incorporating the Neo4j GraphQL Library. Both the user interface and the backend API have been developed in Python 3.12, with the UI making use of Python’s pywebio library. Currently, these components are packaged together in a single container, however, due to the codebase’s modularity, the potential for a future separation into multiple containers and languages exists. Furthermore, a ‘vanilla’ Neo4j-5.13 container is used for storing the knowledge graph. Finally, for testing and demonstrating the data sink capabilities of the service, an HDFS datastore is also deployed using the same Docker Compose configuration, spread over 5 containers (namenode, datanode, resource manager, node manager, and history server).

Concerning the source code, being a private organisation and naturally being inclined to explore possible monetisation opportunities for it, it has been decided not to share the code openly at the common GitHub deployment of the project, but instead store it on our private GitLab deployment¹⁶. However, access to our code will be provided to any reviewers or the project officer upon request (please contact to provide you with the necessary access credentials).

¹⁶ <http://greendatai.konnecta.io:3000/>

2.9.2 Evaluation of Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox

The tool is capable of performing GET calls to any RESTful endpoint that does not require authentication, irrespective of the number of query/url/header parameters involved. Additionally, users can schedule and repeat these calls at their discretion using a suitable cron schedule, with the flexibility to terminate the process as needed. All the received REST responses, along with pertinent metadata, can be systematically stored in any HDFS deployment. For the demonstration, the ‘public holidays’ RESTful API was used, returning details on public holidays for a specific year and country (e.g., <https://date.nager.at/api/v2/publicolidays/2020/US> returns the US public holidays of 2020). The resulting data was stored in a local HDFS deployment.

Concerning the green aspects of the service, these have not been demonstrated yet. However, it is anticipated that these will be demonstrated in the future both in a ‘direct’ and an ‘indirect’ manner through the channels discussed in Section 3.

2.9.3 Description of Accelerated Event Processing Engine

The ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ core operation is pattern matching and its implementation is inspired by the Aho-Corasick algorithm [47]. The tool receives two files as input, (i) the pattern file, which includes several fixed string patterns, and (ii) the text-based input file, which contains the text in which we search for any occurrence of patterns. The patterns are compiled into Deterministic Finite Automaton (DFA) automata, which enables the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ component to search multiple patterns against the input within one pass. Figure 2.57 presents a high-level overview of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ component. Particularly, the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ builds DFA automata using the pattern/keywords provided as input. In parallel, the text-based input is copied to data buffers. Then, the pattern matching process is performed and any matches found are reported as output of the tool.

Figure 2.57: High-level overview of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ in GREEN.DAT.AI

The compilation of the patterns into DFA automata is a process performed once before the main execution of the pattern matching core procedure. This offline compilation offers the advantage of no additional runtime overheads to the pattern matching procedure. Specifically, the patterns are compiled into DFA automata and state transition tables. Then, the state table is copied to the corresponding device memory space. For instance, if the accelerator used is a discrete GPU, then the state table is copied to the device memory. If the device to be used is an integrated GPU and thus, the memory space of the device is shared with the CPU, then the state table is mapped to the corresponding shared memory space. This procedure eliminates redundant memory copies, which add significant overhead in the processing performance.

The ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ has been developed using Open Computing Language (OpenCL). OpenCL is designed to support heterogeneous computing platforms, including CPUs, GPUs, and other hardware accelerators. When executing on platforms that support SIMD instructions, OpenCL use these instructions to enhance performance by parallelising computations across multiple data elements. The current version of the implementation of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ enables the execution on OpenCL-enabled CPUs, integrated and discrete GPUs.

An example of the execution of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ is presented in Figure 2.58. Figure 2.59 and Figure 2.60 show the input file contents and the patterns that were used for this execution example.

```

epapado@adam:~/accelerated_event_processing_engine$ ./bin/accelerated_event_processing_engine -p patterns.dat -i input_text.dat -d 1 -v
max state: 41
max states: 42
tree: 42
Command line execution command
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
Vel turpis nunc eget lorem dolor sed viverra ipsum nunc.
Tincidunt augue interdum velit euismod in.
Pellentesque diam volutpat commodo sed egestas.
Nec nam aliquam sem et. Pellentesque dignissim enim sit amet venenatis.
Venenatis cras sed felis eget velit aliquet sagittis id.
Consectetur purus ut faucibus pulvinar.
Iaculis nunc sed augue lacus viverra vitae congue.
Volutpat est velit egestas dui id ornare arcu odio ut.
Results: Input that was matched against the patterns
total matches: 9
Execution time (usecs): 121 Processing performance statistics

```

Figure 2.58: Example execution of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’.

In the context of GREEN.DAT.AI, the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ will be used in UCs that can offer data in a suitable format (i.e., text-based). Specifically, the component will be used by UC#5, to accelerate the processing of annual user surveys that SERVEO receives as feedback. This procedure will help SERVEO to extract meaningful insights for their services, grouped by a topic. For instance, topics could be the following ‘negative reviews’, ‘recommendations’, ‘positive reviews’, ‘malfunction reports’, ‘accidents caused by malfunctions’, ‘customer service reviews’. An example of the utilisation of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ in UC#5 follows.

```

epapado@adam:~/accelerated_event_processing_engine$ cat input_text.dat
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
Mauris a diam maecenas sed enim.
Eu feugiat pretium nibh ipsum consequat nisl vel pretium.
Dictumst vestibulum rhoncus est pellentesque elit ullamcorper.
Vel turpis nunc eget lorem dolor sed viverra ipsum nunc.
Tincidunt augue interdum velit euismod in.
Pellentesque diam volutpat commodo sed egestas.
Nec nam aliquam sem et. Pellentesque dignissim enim sit amet venenatis.
Venenatis cras sed felis eget velit aliquet sagittis id.
Egestas maecenas pharetra convallis posuere morbi leo urna.
Gravida rutrum quisque non tellus orci ac.
Tincidunt tortor aliquam nulla facilisi cras fermentum.
Consectetur purus ut faucibus pulvinar.
Eget dolor morbi non arcu risus quis varius quam.
Iaculis nunc sed augue lacus viverra vitae congue.
Amet mattis vulputate enim nulla aliquet porttitor lacus.
Volutpat est velit egestas dui id ornare arcu odio ut.
Eu non diam phasellus vestibulum lorem sed.

```

Figure 2.59: Input used for the execution of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’.

```

epapado@adam:~/accelerated_event_processing_engine$ cat patterns.dat
Lorem
viverra
patternX
velit
patternY
purus
egestas
Pellentesque
patternZ

```

Figure 2.60: Pattern file used for the execution of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’.

A test pattern file was constructed containing patterns that could signify negative reviews (e.g., broken, unresponsive, accident). As input, a sample of randomly selected responses from 50 users was utilised. Figure 2.61 shows the output of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ with the input provided by SERVEO. Since the user input is in Spanish and Catalan, the patterns were translated from English to Spanish. The pattern used are presented in Figure 2.62.

```

epapado@adam:~/accelerated_event_processing_engine$ ./bin/accelerated_event_processing_engine
-p GREENDATAI_UC5/test_patterns_negativerreviews -i GREENDATAI_UC5/test_input -d 1 -v
max state: 24
max states: 25
trc: 25
Hacerles buen mantenimiento a las bicicletas porque luego tienen sorpresa, porque para lo que
paga uno al año y por uso deberían estar en mejor estado, frenos rotos, timbres, timon de bici
roto, las electricas a veces no les va el motor y no arrancan, las mecanicas super duras. Y s
olucionar el QR porque hay gente borrándolos y no puedes desbloquear las bicis. Gracias
Cal cuidar l'estat de les bicicletes i no permetre que els remolcs que les transporten aparqui
n malament per anar al bar
Arregla los problemas con los QRs! Y tienes que añadir una forma para dar feedback en la app s
obre el estado de la bicicleta. No siempre esta rota entero pero puede falls un freno por ejem
plo. Estará bien poder valorar cada bici después del uso del 1-10 así bicing sabe cual arregla
r con prioridad
Que la tarifa sea más económica y las bicis sean revisadas a menudo. Se encuentran muchas defec
tuosas
Sigue siendo muy malo el servicio. Reservas y no salen. Siempre hay muchisimas en rojo. Las me
canicas son imposibles de llevar por lo pesadas.
Las bicis mecánicas pesan mucho, hay bicis eléctricas Que se quedan sin batería, hay muchas bi
cis con el código QR tachado por lo que no se pueden usar, muchas bicis rotas en las estacione
s. Poca disponibilidad de bicis eléctricas.
Total matches: 6
Execution time (usecs): 135

```

Figure 2.61: Output of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ using as input the annual user surveys that SERVEO receives from their customers.

```

epapado@adam:~/accelerated_event_processing_engine$ cat GREENDATAI_UC5/test_patterns_negativerreviews
malo
mala
roto
rota
defectuoso
defectuosa
accidente

```

Figure 2.62: Patterns used to extract negative reviews from the annual user survey.

Finally, the source code for the "Accelerated Event Processing Engine" tool will not be publicly available since it is planned to be commercialized. However, access to the code will be provided to reviewers or the project officer upon request. The code of the service is available online at a private repo¹⁷ (please contact to provide you with the necessary access credentials). Also, a docker image with the tool executable is uploaded to the GREEN.DAT.AI docker registry¹⁸ and it is available for testing purposes.

2.9.4 Evaluation of Accelerated Event Processing Engine

Due to the specific requirements of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ (i.e., OpenCL-enabled hardware devices and root privileges OpenCL drivers' installation), the deployment of the tool is performed at the premises of TUC. The system setup of the testing environment for the execution of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ follows. The CPU is an Intel(R) Core (TM) i7-4770 CPU operating at 3.40GHz packed with an Intel(R) HD Graphics GPU. The HD Graphics uses OpenCL version 1.2 with driver version r5.0.63503, while the Intel i7 CPU uses OpenCL version 1.2 (build 475) with driver version 1.2.0.475. The system memory is 16GB. The OpenCL devices are shown in Figure 2.63.

¹⁷ <https://github.com/greendatai-eu/T3.5-accelerated-event-processing-engine>

¹⁸ <https://harbor.greendatai.rid-intrasoft.eu/harbor/projects/44/repositories/accelerated-event-processing-engine>

```

epapado@adam:~/accelerated_event_processing_engine$ clinfo -l
Platform #0: Intel(R) OpenCL
+-- Device #0: Intel(R) HD Graphics
`-- Device #1: Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-4770 CPU @ 3.40GHz
  
```

Figure 2.63: OpenCL devices present in the testing environment.

For the evaluation of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ performance, several micro-benchmarks were performed on the Intel i7 CPU. For these micro-benchmarks, pattern files with different number of patterns were used (i.e., 300, 700 and 1000 patterns with varying length). In addition, synthetic input files with varying sizes were generated. The input files were constructed accordingly to cause different workload conditions. The processing performance of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ is measured based on the execution time and it is presented in Table 2.10. The value presented is the median value calculated after 20 runs. It can be observed that the number of patterns used does not affect the performance achieved by the tool, while larger input sizes result in higher processing throughput (data/execution time). Similarly, Table 2.11 presents the performance achieved by the SotA tool GNU grep using the `-f` option to force the utilisation of the Aho-Corasick algorithm. The execution of the GNU grep tool is performed on the CPU, as well. The processing performance speedup of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ when compared to the SotA GNU grep tool is achieved due to the acceleration caused by OpenCL and the SIMD instruction-set used.

Table 2.10: Performance achieved by the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ under different processing conditions (i.e., number of patterns, input size, and workload).

Number of patterns	Input size	Execution time (without matches)	Execution time (with matches)
300	5.5MB (100,000 lines)	106 µs	95 µs
300	11MB (200,000 lines)	125 µs	126 µs
300	22MB (400,000 lines)	185 µs	185 µs
300	44MB (800,000 lines)	168 µs	154 µs
700	5.5MB (100,000 lines)	110 µs	94 µs
700	11MB (200,000 lines)	127 µs	134 µs
700	22MB (400,000 lines)	188 µs	194 µs
700	44MB (800,000 lines)	169 µs	168 µs
1000	5.5MB (100,000 lines)	103 µs	102 µs
1000	11MB (200,000 lines)	126 µs	119 µs
1000	22MB (400,000 lines)	189 µs	181 µs
1000	44MB (800,000 lines)	168 µs	166 µs

Table 2.11: Performance achieved by the GNU grep tool under different processing conditions (i.e., number of patterns and workload).

Number of patterns	Input size	Execution time (without matches)	Execution time (with matches)
300	44MB (800,000 lines)	3,000 µs	3,000 µs
700	44MB (800,000 lines)	3,000 µs	3,000 µs
1000	44MB (800,000 lines)	3,000 µs	4,000 µs

2.9.5 Next steps

In line with the discussion in Section 2.9.1, the ontology forms the backbone of the Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox, driving the metadata graph stored in Neo4j which in turn powers all functionalities of the service. Therefore, the pivotal next step that will drive all other developments is the expansion of the ontology in a way that adequately supports all functionalities we wish to develop discussed below.

1. Enhance Data Source Integration: Building upon the existing RESTful API ingestion functionality, further developments are needed to support authentication methods (e.g., basic authentication, API keys, JSON Web Tokens) that might potentially include choreography (i.e., receiving the token from one endpoint before using it in a different endpoint). Simultaneously, expand the scope to include additional data sources as required in the project (e.g., FTP servers, SQL databases, MongoDB).
2. Extend support of the cataloguing of the response structure from JSON to also include XML and CSV and allow for the selective storage of the response (i.e., only ingesting part of the response).
3. Extend the support of data sinks to Kafka as this will be central messaging component of the project and will allow the service to message other downstream components.
4. Augment response data with statistical metadata like the minimum, maximum, and average values of certain metrics over user-defined timeframes while allowing for checks for specific threshold-based events to be performed both in the ingested data as well as in the statistical metadata.

By achieving these key developments, the service will be fortified, and its functionality, scalability, and adaptability will be enhanced to meet the requirements of the project.

Concerning the integration of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ into the GREEN.DAT.AI system, it is envisaged to integrate it with the Visualisation Workbench component of AEGIS. This integration will enable the visualisation of the output of the tool based on the UC#5 requirements. The tool will be also integrated with the Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox of KNT, which will provide the input through a user-friendly environment. Finally, the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ will be executed and evaluated on discrete GPUs, as well.

3 Discussion of the Green Dimension of the WP3 Services

As the energy demand of AI systems, especially with the increasing utilisation of deep learning and other resource-intensive algorithms, continues to rise, there is a growing imperative to address concerns regarding sustainability. As already discussed, this deliverable underscores the development of the first version of the energy-efficient large-scale data analytics services, tailored to meet the requirements of the six UCs involved within the GREEN.DAT.AI project. Although, the initial versions of these services have been deployed, there is an ongoing commitment to refine and optimise them further to decrease their energy consumption and contribute to the overall project's overarching goal of achieving energy efficiency. To this end, this section aims to highlight the initial 'green' attributes of the developed services and outline strategies for further optimisation. Specifically, WP3 will explore solutions to enhance energy efficiency, leveraging analytical tools for energy demand measurement developed within WP2, as outlined in D1.1. The final iteration of the services will be detailed in D3.2 and aim to showcase a minimum 10% improvement in energy efficiency compared to baseline scenarios and metrics identified in D1.1. Below, the energy-efficient footprint for each service is described and strategies for optimisation are outlined:

Data enrichment. This service is based on the scalable tool RDF-Gen, which enables data transformation to RDF triples and data enrichment with contextual information. RDF-Gen processes data in a 'record-by-record' manner, inherently supporting parallel processing, which underscores its design for overall performance enhancement. Although energy efficiency has not been directly evaluated, preliminary assessments suggest potential gains by deploying some tasks on the edge. Consequently, future efforts will concentrate on exploring a more energy-efficient approach by tuning the service for improved performance at the edge.

Incentive mechanisms for Data Anonymisation and Sharing. These services hold promise for enhancing sustainability indexes, such as the improved utilisation of renewable energy sources. Despite the environmental benefits associated with the services' goals, there's a recognition of the significance of energy efficiency concerning the computational processes involved in data analysis and algorithm execution. Thus, future evaluations will utilise the energy profiling tools from WP2 to optimise energy consumption.

Mobility trajectory data generation (IMN-cloning Car Trajectory Synthesis) service. Data generation is a one-time computation, the energy costs of which are typically easily amortised by subsequent processes. Its outcome has the potential to be utilised by numerous tasks, including trajectory-based energy consumption services and prediction algorithms during the learning phase of models (which may involve several iterations). This service has the potential to be energy-efficient through the implementation of specific strategies. Therefore, future iterations of the service will explore optimisations with energy efficiency as an evaluation metric, in addition to considering runtimes and the quality of results. Common optimisation strategies will be explored in particular: pre-computing useful aggregates (e.g. one-to-many shortest paths in place of the one-to-one adopted so far), removing redundant computations (e.g. caching results of partial computations) and replacing random searches with faster heuristics (e.g. in searching locations mapping).

Trajectory-based battery consumption estimation. This service is tailored for efficiently processing large trajectory datasets while reducing computational load. Future efforts will prioritise optimising energy efficiency in terms of seeking the optimal balance between runtimes, result accuracy, and energy demand. This will be achieved by leveraging tools for energy demand measurement from WP2 and exploring solutions to improve energy efficiency. Key areas of focus include identifying the best sampling rate of data, since a higher than necessary rate increases the computation load with no benefit, and possibly simplifying some parts of the model that do not impact significantly on the output estimates.

EV Transaction Data Forecasting. This service employs a set of modelling approaches that can be used as an alternative aiming towards energy efficiency. Although the initial emphasis of model and feature selection was on forecasting accuracy, upcoming steps will explore alternative methods to balance precision, robustness, and energy consumption. Key strategies include employing clustering techniques to group clients, considerably reducing the number of datasets for modelling, thereby reducing computational time and energy consumption. Additionally, another tactic involves testing smaller sets of features beyond the optimal ones to assess how model accuracy reacts to this alternative scenario.

Privacy-preserving FL. The utilisation of FL offers significant contributions to global sustainability indexes by incentivising stakeholders in the energy sector to share their data through privacy-preserving mechanisms, thus facilitating better optimisation of renewable resources. Subsequently, a comprehensive analysis is planned to uncover potential energy-saving opportunities in the algorithms used for forecasting wind power generation. Regarding the integration of FL and edge computing, energy efficiency can be proved through a thorough evaluation of computational efficiency and data transmission reduction. The decentralised nature of FL allows for local model training on individual EV chargers, diminishing the need for centralised server computations. This decentralised approach is anticipated to yield lower electricity consumption, given the potential exponential relationship between processing use and energy consumption. In this sense, a comparative analysis between energy consumption from edge devices and centralised computations will be conducted to validate the environmental advantages of FL.

Algorithm Selection & Hyperparameter Tuning/AutoML. Goal of AutoML is to minimise the number of trials of different algorithm configurations to select the best performing one. Inherently, this procedure, among other benefits, is more efficient than exhaustive search solutions such as grid search or random search in terms of carbon footprint. During the first period of the project, focus has been on improving technical aspects of the provided service and improving the quality of results. Improvements over the energy efficiency of the AutoML procedure have been part of the design process and are expected to be developed and functioning in the upcoming period. Examples include optimisation according to an objective function that takes into account the algorithm energy consumption and parameter exploration strategies for Bayesian search to focus its search on parameters that are inversely correlated with cost.

Explainable feature learning. Straightforward implementation of the described approach generates a massive number of new features in each iteration that require evaluation and are, providing they are of sufficient quality, included in the feature selection step. Currently, this approach demonstrates efficiency in terms of accuracy. During the next steps of project developments, efforts will be directed towards reducing the input features for the construction of new ones. For this purpose, histograms of input features (estimated during their evaluations during the previous iteration) will be analysed for pre-filtering features and their pairs that do not have the potential to result in an improved feature. In this way, we are planning to at least half the number of features and their pairs and, thus, significantly reduce the number of computation and the related energy consumed by the implemented approach.

Interpretable Clustering (Partitioning-Tree Clustering). As discussed in the service description, ParTree has already proven to be among the most efficient algorithms of the large pool of comparable competitors considered in empirical evaluation. Next steps will include an evaluation of the energy demand related aspects, based on the functionalities for energy demand measurement that will be provided by WP2 in the following period of the project, and a tuning of the algorithm aimed to find the best trade-off between performances (runtimes), output quality and energy consumption. The strategies that will be explored for

improving energy efficiency will mainly focus on simplifying some of the exhaustive searches that the algorithm is currently performing, targeting the steps that have a minor impact on the final output.

(weighted) FL. By distributing the training workload to multiple edge devices / silos, FL allows for potentially ‘smarter’ models, lower inference latency, less overall power consumption, and thus lighter environmental impact [48]. To minimise the carbon footprint of FL, reduce training time, and achieve high model quality, FL developers must focus on lowering the training time, e.g., through the right choice of the optimiser, learning rates, and batch sizes, while keeping the concurrency small [49]. As stated in Section 2.7.3, this will be investigated further during the next stage of the project, with a particular focus on exploring solutions towards balancing FL model performance and energy efficiency.

Adaptive FL for Digital Twin Applications. In terms of energy efficiency, the developed services at this stage provide the baseline on which several optimisations will be researched. Due to the complex interactions between different components of data fusion model for the implementation of digital twin applications there are obviously several possible ways in which improvements can be achieved. At the source pre-processing level (i.e. Level 0), we have already examined computational efficiency of morphological operators in [50]. As this also directly impacts energy efficiency, significant optimisations are expected to be achieved by utilising the same principles also on other data filtering and pre-processing operators. In addition, at object assessment (i.e. Level 1) levels we plan to utilise geospatial database procedures in order to reduce data transfer, while remote procedure calls will be studied for evoking Level 2 and 3 Services. Finally, several orchestration pipelines and other possible system optimisation will be addressed and levels 4 and 5.

Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox. The nature of the service, that of a ‘box-mover’, does not make use of any AI algorithms that are based on heavily energy-reliant ANNs. Nevertheless, this service could potentially yield direct and indirect energy efficiency benefits. The direct efficiency gain of the service comes from the (planned) implementation of a simple timeseries forecasting tool based on ARIMA methods [51], a forecasting tool first suggested in the 60s, that is multiple orders of magnitude lighter on computational resources than current ANN developments. Although our intention to implement this model arises from being able to run the service on any device irrespective of its processing power, ARIMA-based models’ performance has been shown to be relatively comparable with much newer methods under certain scenarios [52], [53]. Although, the primary focus is on direct efficiency improvements, there are additional indirect efficiency gains of this service including the usage of summary statistics by downstream components, and filtering and selectively storing metrics for potential use by other components.

Accelerated Event Processing Engine. SIMD-enabled processors offer significant advantages in terms of energy efficiency. By allowing multiple data to be processed simultaneously with a single instruction, SIMD architectures reduce the number of instructions required to perform a given task, reducing the energy consumption that is normally required. When compared to the SotA, the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ can process the same amount of data in significantly less time, as presented in Table 2.10 and Table 2.11. Consequently, it exhibits remarkable energy efficiency.

In conclusion, while initial assessments reveal areas for improvement, WP3 is committed to enhancing the energy efficiency of its services to align with the project's broader goals of environmental sustainability.

4 WP3 Toolbox in GREEN.DAT.AI & UC Workflows

This section provides six distinct workflows, each tailored to meet the requirements of the GREEN.DAT.AI UCs. These workflows demonstrate the seamless collaboration among WP3 services to address the different needs of each UC. They serve as examples showcasing how WP3 services can be interconnected to effectively tackle the unique challenges and objectives outlined within each UC.

It is important to note that in the following workflows, WP3 services are distinguished using two different colours: Services highlighted in dark pink have already been developed for the specific UC and are detailed in this deliverable, while services highlighted in pale pink indicate those that are currently under development or possibly aimed to be developed for the respective UC.

4.1 UC#1 Workflow

UC#1 overall objective is to facilitate knowledge sharing among stakeholders in the renewable energy sector. As a result, this UC encourages the exchange of expertise, enhances model accuracy through diverse data sources, and fosters innovation in the field. A central focus of UC#1 is to meet the critical requirement for accurate forecasting of energy production, especially vital for wind-farm owners, enabling them to effectively plan energy sales strategies.

UC#1 comprises two distinct systems interconnected through an API, facilitated by Python tooling called Predico. Predico also facilitates the management of cryptocurrency wallets for each participant. The first system caters to energy traders, providing analytics on their trades, enabling manual adjustments to trading patterns, and facilitating the transmission of trading data to the market system via a Web User Interface. The second system, known as the market system, consists of a market engine responsible for executing models for market prediction, and a database that stores historical data, recent predictions, and client data.

The following services are utilised to address the needs of UC#1:

- **Data marketplaces using blockchain [ST3.1.2]:** This service provides collaborative forecasting strategies for time series data through a data market platform prototype that integrates a set of mathematical algorithms to ensure fair data exchange and compensations. Interactions between data owners are made through a data market platform (implemented in a distributed ledger technology, IOTA) that orchestrates all the processes. Data owners have a REST Client API that allows for an easy interaction with the data market platform.
- **Data monetization mechanisms for data sharing [ST3.1.2]:** This service aims at creating a set of mechanisms for data sharing with the main goals of attracting data consumers and benefit data providers. In this sense, data owners share their data because they are monetarily compensated if their data is relevant for solving analytics/optimisation tasks.
- **Privacy-preserving FL [ST3.2.2]:** This service involves predicting multiple time series by combining time series data from diverse companies. In specific, provide renewable energy time series forecasting of geographically distributed renewable power plants. To facilitate collaborative forecasting among agents, it is imperative that the models include data privacy protocols throughout the collaboration process.
- **Geographical Transfer Learning [T3.3]:** The effectiveness of forecasting models for energy production strongly depends on rich historical data associated to the power plant under examination.

The GTL service (currently under development and not presented in this deliverable) will provide approaches to produce forecasts of reasonable quality also for newer plants where data are insufficient to build models from scratch, exploiting the data and models built over consolidated plants, as well as their geospatial relations.

Figure 4.1: UC#1 workflow utilising WP3 services.

4.2 UC#2 Workflow

UC#2 focus lies on implementing FL-enabled smart charging for EVs while leveraging edge computing to deploy an intelligent charging management system that tackles the challenges of simultaneous EV charging under varied technical constraints. A core technical emphasis is on utilising FL as the primary mechanism for training AI models while safeguarding data privacy. This involves orchestrating a decentralised learning process where AI models are collaboratively trained across multiple local nodes (EV chargers), eliminating the need for raw data exchange. The overarching technical objective is to achieve efficient and secure model training, enabling the EV charging infrastructure to dynamically adapt to real-time grid conditions, with a specific emphasis on maximising the utilisation of RES.

Furthermore, another technical objective pertains to establishing crowdsensing-enabled data-driven services for EV charging management. This entails integrating data collected from EV users' smartphones, which is securely transmitted to a central server. The technical challenge lies in harnessing this crowd-sensed data, including GPS coordinates, acceleration, and altitude, to enhance the optimisation processes initiated in the previous context, for example, to estimate the State of Charge of a given user's EV. Additionally, the presence of a dedicated interface in the users' mobile devices enables the creation of additional features to engage the user and potentially promote revenue generation.

The following services are utilised to address the needs of UC#2:

- **Data enrichment [ST3.1.1]:** This service will be applied on the mobility data (real or synthetic), to enrich the data with contextual information and interlink with third party data sources (e.g. such as OpenStreetMap, wikiData, etc).
- **Mobility trajectory data generation (IMN-cloning Car Trajectory Synthesis) [ST3.1.3]:** This service will provide synthetic, yet realistic mobility data associated to users of the EV recharge facilities involved in the UC. The purpose will be two-fold: in a first phase, synthetic data will be used to test and tune algorithms that will exploit crowdsourced mobility data of users to better forecast energy demand; in a second phase, it will be explored the possibility to align the generated data to the real recharge facilities' usage data, and thus use the synthetic trajectories as a tentative reconstruction of the (real) users' recent mobility history. Combined with the trajectory-based consumption estimation service, that might provide a useful input to forecasting algorithms.
- **Energy (demand/consumption) forecasting of charging stations/EVs [ST3.2.1]:** This service (still under exploration) is designed to address the problem of forecasting energy consumption/demand for charging stations/EVs. Specifically, it leverages recent historical EV charging consumption data, weather data, and time-of-day data as inputs to an ANN model, enabling the generation of daily and monthly consumption forecasts.
- **Trajectory-based Battery Consumption Estimation [ST3.2.1]:** This service will be applied to the mobility history (real or simulated) of users that recharge at INESC TEC facilities. Estimating the battery consumed during the recent history of the user provides useful information about the energy that their vehicle will need when connecting to the rechargers, and thus about how long the vehicle will remain connected, which are two of the central challenges of this UC.
- **Charging station occupancy forecast [ST3.2.1]:** This service (still under development) aims to develop a methodology for forecasting the start time of the next EV charging transactions, ranging from hours to day-ahead. The forecasting methodology operates through scheduled tasks, such as hourly updates, utilising historical data from previous charging transactions to predict the start time of the subsequent transaction. The resulting output from this service will be integrated into smart EV charging tools, contributing to the optimisation of the charging schedule for vehicles connected to the same grid. By merging the predicted start times with transaction durations, a comprehensive EV charging station occupancy timeseries is generated, providing insights into both transaction initiation times and expected durations.
- **EV transactions data forecasts [ST3.2.1]:** This service is dedicated to forecasting various components of an EV charging transaction, specifically the total parking duration at the EV charging station and the total energy charged to the vehicle. The forecasting process takes place in real-time, triggered when an EV owner plugs their vehicle into the charger. The resultant output serves as input for smart EV charging tools, facilitating the optimisation of charging schedules for multiple vehicles interconnected within the same grid.
- **Distributed optimization at the edge [ST3.2.2]:** This service (still under development) aims to implement intelligent charging strategies by leveraging the computational capacities of EV chargers, promoting the use of edge computing. With the objective of optimizing the utilization of RES for charging EVs, chargers collaboratively compute charging setpoints for the next few hours. The optimization problem encompasses maximizing the use of renewables while addressing technical grid constraints and adhering to EV owners' satisfaction criteria (e.g., minimum State of Charge (SoC)).
- **Privacy-preserving FL [ST3.2.2]:** To ensure data privacy, an algebraic protocol is applied during the computation of sensitivity factors – express the impact of power variations in voltages. These

sensitivity factors act as a data-driven digital twin of the grid, derived from historical data collected by grid-connected devices, eliminating the need for an exhaustive topological or electrical characterisation of the grid.

- **Algorithm Selection & Hyperparameter Tuning/AutoML [ST3.2.2]:** AutoML methods will be applied on data gathered from the developed mobile application to provide well performing models for a given task such as drivers’ behaviour clustering or energy consumption forecasting.
- **(weighted) FL [T3.3]:** The purpose of this service is to train a data-driven model using Federated Learning across edge devices (i.e., EV charging points) in order to estimate their corresponding demand, in terms of power consumption.

Figure 4.2: UC#2 workflow utilising WP3 services.

4.3 UC#3 Workflow

UC#3 aims to enhance an existing Farm Manager platform by leveraging AI and digital twin solutions to optimize farming practices. The UC#3 key objective is to empower farmers counselling services with: a) optimisation of fertilisation by (near) real-time generation of fertilisation maps, fitted to the soil and crop need, b) monitoring services for early detection of plant pests and disease using (near) real-time object assessment on the fusion of satellite images and UAV inspections, and c) prognostics on the soil-health status and optimal harvesting times.

The following services are utilised to address the needs of UC#3:

- **Data generation based on images [ST3.1.3]:** This service (still under exploration) aims to provide a data augmentation functionality that should expand the real training data for predictive models (basically, satellite maps about vegetation, associated to the soil/vegetation status and the domain expert’s prescriptions) with new elements that reproduce the information contained in the real data

from different perspectives. That is expected to facilitate the task of prediction learning algorithms, compensating the current size limitations of real data available.

- **Explainable feature learning [ST3.2.3]:** This service addresses the construction of feature spaces for improved performances of classifiers and prediction models applied on it. Accordingly, this service will provide necessary feature transformation for crop development predictions, pest & disease detection, as well as generation of fertilisation and spraying maps.
- **(weighted) FL [T3.3]:** The purpose of this service (currently under development) is to train a data-driven model using FL across edge devices (i.e., farming areas) in order to estimate the amount of fertiliser required during the current fertilisation phase.
- **Orchestration framework for derivation geospatial data products [T3.4]:** This service provides a systematic feature extraction over the whole data fusion pipeline. More specifically, spatio-temporal alignment of satellite images is achieved here, following by derivation of soil health and crop development indices that are feed into crop predictions. Finally, this service also provides derivation of their timeseries for anomaly detection (i.e. detection of pest and diseases) to be used for final generation of fertilisation and spraying maps.
- **Behaviour modelling pipelines [T3.4]:** This service combines a series of prediction models for forecasting crop development. It acts on raster data and includes predictions of different vegetation, soil, and moisture indices. This behaviour models are later used by orchestration framework for anomaly detection.
- **Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox [T3.5]:** The Smart farming optimisation through Digital Twins UC will possibly involve the monitoring of weather forecasts provided by weather providers' APIs to produce relevant weather forecasts and insights on the soil quality. The service appears suitable to support the following actions:
 - Ingest required metrics from weather providers' APIs.
 - Produce basic forecasts and/or statistical measurements for key metrics of interest.

Figure 4.3: UC#3 workflow utilising WP3 services.

4.4 UC#4 Workflow

UC#4 objective is to empower farmers with irrigation water quality prediction, offering a prognostic system for water quality management in agriculture to meet the increasingly vital needs of farmers, plantation owners, and vegetable growers. The UC#4 aims to furnish farm managers with significant benefits, particularly heightened awareness of current and future irrigation water quality. Armed with this information, farm managers can make necessary adjustments to ensure optimal water conditions for crops, ultimately enhancing productivity and overall farm performance.

The envisioned system of UC#4 will offer: a) enhanced coverage of remote real-time data intake from various water sources, b) integration of received data with open-source data for micro-location, such as weather and temperature, c) identification of suitable water types for different agricultural uses and treatment methods to maximise water usage and value, d) optimisation of water intake at various locations based on AI-driven analysis of all input data, e) provision of a graphical and visual real-time map displaying different water sources and quality elements.

The following services are utilised to address the needs of UC#4:

- **Data enrichment [ST3.1.1]:** The data enrichment service in this UC, will provide the means for integrating recordings from different sensors. This service enables the semantic enrichment of data reported by different sensors under a common schema. Also, this service will enrich the data with contextual information (e.g. interlink sensors with parcels), to improve the performance of frequently used queries.
- **Explainable feature learning [ST3.2.3]:** This service builds a new feature space from the input explanatory variables for improved performances of prediction of water quality prediction parameters. Accordingly, it acts on satellite data in order to provide necessary data transformation for water quality maps and combines these with raw IoT data provided by Wabooost monitoring system to be fed into water quality predictions. Finally, this service also provides the necessary data transformations for water irrigation optimisations (i.e. selection of optimal water irrigation regime according to the current and predicted water quality and soil moisture parameters).
- **Orchestration framework for derivation geospatial data products [T3.4]:** Feature extractions over data fusion pipeline will be provided here, including pre-processing and spatio-temporal alignment of satellite images and IoT data, to be fed into water quality assessments, together with generation of time series data for quality predictions using feature space provided by feature learning. Finally, this service uses water behaviour models to search for optimal irrigation regime, i.e. a map, specifying the water parameters (e.g. oxygen level, acidity etc.) to be applied on a particular area.
- **Event detection on fused datasets [T3.4]:** This service provides straightforward detection of drought or, more general, vegetation deterioration from satellite images. This is achieved by simple classification applied on vegetation indices extracted from satellite data, namely Sentinel 2.
- **Behaviour modelling pipelines [T3.4]:** This service combines a series of water quality prediction models in order to provide holistic water behaviour model to be used by orchestration framework for deriving optimal irrigation scenario.
- **Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox [T3.5]:** The Smart Water Management UC will involve the monitoring of weather forecasts provided by weather providers' APIs, as well as water quality metrics gathered by IoT devices installed as part of the UC. The service appears suitable to support the following actions:

- Ingest required metrics from all relevant sources, including weather providers' APIs and IoT devices.
- Monitoring metrics for user-defined thresholds and generate notifications when these are triggered.
- Produce basic forecasts for key metrics of interest.

Figure 4.4: UC#4 workflow utilising WP3 services.

4.5 UC#5 Workflow

UC#5 focuses on enhancing energy demand response in e-bikes and infrastructure planning. The primary objective of this UC is to optimise energy demand, stabilize the network, and enhance user satisfaction through the development of a dedicated application. The aim is to ensure that fully charged e-bikes are strategically positioned at stations where demand is anticipated, while charging occurs in a distributed manner. This approach aims to minimise peak energy consumption, ensure network stability, and reduce the need for extensive bike redistributions.

The following services are utilised to address the needs of UC#5:

- **Data enrichment [ST3.1.1]:** This service semantically enriches the data and detects relations between entities described in the data. In this UC, the data enrichment service is expected to provide an improved view of the data to help other subtasks improve their results.
- **Mobility trajectory data generation (IMN-cloning Car Trajectory Synthesis) [ST3.1.3]:** This service (still under exploration) aims to provide functionalities similar to the synthetic trajectory data in UC2, namely for simulating the mobility history of users that pick-up and return e-bikes from the available stations. The objective is to exploit such information to help the predictive tasks to infer the battery status of returned e-bikes, and thus their energy demand during the recharges and the required recharge times.
- **Energy (demand/consumption) forecasting of charging stations/EVs [ST3.2.1]:** This service (currently under development and not presented in this deliverable) aims to address the problem of

forecasting energy consumption/demand for charging stations/e-bikes. Specifically, it leverages recent historical charging consumption data, weather data, and time-of-day data as inputs to an ANN model, enabling the generation of daily and monthly consumption forecasts.

- **Algorithm Selection & Hyperparameter Tuning/AutoML [ST3.2.2]:** The goal of this service is to optimise bikes’ redistribution among the stations, in order to maximise bike availability based on the predicted users’ demand for bikes.
- **Geographical Transfer Learning [T3.3]:** This service (currently under exploration and not presented in this deliverable) addresses the forecast of some key indicators for e-bike stations (stalls availability, energy demand, etc.) focused on stations with too little historical data to build a ‘local’ predictive model, e.g. the stations in a new area recently opened to e-bikes. The basic approach will consist of exploiting the data/models available in other areas of the city and the geospatial relations among the stations/areas to build a local forecast model of acceptable performances.
- **(weighted) FL [T3.3]:** The goal of this service (currently under development) is to estimate demand in terms of the volume of incoming/outgoing traffic flow within each corresponding e-bike charging point.
- **Event detection on fused datasets [T3.4]:** This service will utilise eBike demand prediction and eBike status monitoring for timely detection possible deficits in their availability. Accordingly, eBike redistribution planning will be addressed by multicriteria optimisation, taking additionally into account distribution of energy consumption due to eBike charging.
- **Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox [T3.5]:** The Energy demand response in e-bikes and infrastructure planning will involve some ‘free-text’ user feedback on the quality of the service. The service will ingest the ‘free-text’ user feedback and allow the end-user to be notified when certain kinds of feedback is received (e.g., negative feedback). It will then be calling on the Accelerated Event Processing Engine.
- **Accelerated Event Processing Engine [T3.5]:** A UC scenario for the utilisation of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ is the processing of annual user surveys that SERVEO receives as feedback to extract meaningful insights about their services and user satisfaction.

Figure 4.5: UC#5 workflow utilising WP3 services.

4.6 UC#6 Workflow

UC#6 focuses on enhancing the efficiency of Fraud Detection systems, recognizing the escalating significance of digital security in light of the proliferation of fraud technologies in recent years. Within WP3, the primary objective is to develop tools aimed at reducing the operational costs of day-to-day operations at CXB by improving efficiency of Fraud Detection Systems, while also striving to improve customer satisfaction by leveraging eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) to avoid discrimination. This UC encompasses four main sub-UCs, namely: 1) XAI for secure ecommerce fraud detection, 2) XAI for online multi-factor authentication (MFA) fraudulent enrolment detection, 3) XAI models for customer claims on potential frauds, and 4) eXplainable clustering and anomaly detection in customers behaviour.

The following services are utilised to address the needs of UC#6:

- **Interpretable Clustering [ST3.2.3]:** This service will be used to provide an unsupervised classification of customers in UC6, to complement the supervised classification models already available and those under development in the project for identifying bank frauds. The aim is to explore the clustering structure of the data and possibly identify those groups that have characteristic features deemed interesting for the application, i.e. suspicious and potentially fraudulent. A special requirement for this task is the interpretability of the clustering, since understanding what each cluster represents is fundamental, and thus our ParTree tool will be adopted, which provides a compact and easy-to-read tree-structured representation of clusters.
- **Knowledge discovery tools on learned features [ST3.2.3]:** This service provides analytics of already trained models for examining their decision-making processes using SHAP and LIME methodologies in order to ensure their compliance with certain ethical standards. Service accepts already trained AI model, together with a set of testing data, as an input, while its output is a figure explaining relations between the model’s inputs and its outputs.
- **Explainable feature learning [ST3.2.3]:** This service provides a new feature space from the input explanatory variables for improved e-Commerce fraud detection. Accordingly, it will process customers fraud claims and extract relevant features from their recent behaviour (i.e. ATM money withdraws, online transactions, etc.).

Figure 4.6: UC#6 workflow utilising WP3 services.

5 Conclusion

The current document, D3.1 – First Version of Energy-Efficient Large-Scale Data Analytics Services, represents a pivotal achievement within WP3 of the GREEN.DAT.AI project. It signifies the culmination of endeavours aimed at crafting innovative solutions for large-scale data analytics. This deliverable serves as the initial iteration of D3.2, delineating a path towards achieving MS2. D3.1 underscores the importance of MS2 within the GREEN.DAT.AI project, marking the initial integration of technical elements and addressing GREEN.DAT.AI objective 3 (O3), which aims to develop pioneering Energy-Efficient Large-Scale Data Analytics Services, including FLS, and tools to facilitate the deployment of operational solutions using the infrastructure developed in Objective 2 (O2). Aligned closely with WP2, O2 furnishes the BDA infrastructure and tools to support dynamic data sharing in industrial ecosystems through service federation and the execution of distributed large-scale data pipelines. Furthermore, D3.1 represents the inaugural endeavour to incorporate environmentally sustainable dimensions into the developed services, highlighting the project's dedication to sustainability and environmental stewardship. By providing a comprehensive overview of the preliminary solutions devised within WP3, this deliverable establishes the foundation for further progress and enhancements in the subsequent iteration, ultimately contributing to the overarching goals of the GREEN.DAT.AI project.

In detail, this release encompasses a comprehensive software package and accompanying documentation that encapsulates the development of services and findings from technical efforts in WP3 (Tasks T3.1 – T3.5). Through the development of sixteen distinct services tailored to six UCs across four sectors, D3.1 marks the first phase of work towards providing energy-efficient large-scale data analytics solutions. These services cover critical domains such as AI-driven data enhancement, Incentive models for Data Sharing, and Federated & Automated Transfer Learning, among others.

Moreover, the inclusion of both software components and an exhaustive report in D3.1 reflects a multifaceted strategy towards solution development, informed by UC requirements outlined in T1.1 and WP4. The software package, accessible via the GREEN.DAT.AI GitHub Repository, serves as a tangible demonstration of the project's advancement in developing cutting-edge data analytics solutions.

In conclusion, the developed services contribute to reducing the energy footprint while remaining adaptable to various user needs. Moving forward, a subsequent version of this deliverable is anticipated, which will incorporate updates and the finalized rendition of the energy-efficient large-scale data analytics services realising fully the envisioned UCs workflows. This final iteration is expected to demonstrate enhanced energy efficiency by at least 10% compared to baseline scenarios, further emphasising the project's dedication to sustainable innovation. Thus, we will actively seek intensive orchestration and collaboration with partners involved in WP2 and WP4 activities to ensure continuous improvement and refinement.

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Appendix I – AI-based Tools Background

In this section, we provide a brief overview of the SotA in Energy-Efficient AI-based algorithms and Large-Scale Data Analytics related to the services developed within WP3 and outlined in this deliverable.

A. SotA in AI-enabled data enrichment

The semantic enrichment of data requires the use of a semantic model that provides the conceptualization of the domain. This semantic model is typically defined as an RDFS/OWL ontology that may also reuse existing, well-established, higher-level ontologies. Subsequently, the process of data enrichment is performed by means of data transformation from diverse data sources and formats into Resource Description Framework (RDF) triples. As such, the data transformed under the vocabulary of an RDFS/OWL ontology, become semantically enriched, and interlinked with other resources described in data originating from various data sources. Data interlinking often requires custom functions tailored to the specific data input and relations between resources that need to be discovered. In this section, we briefly present the SotA approaches related to data transformation into a common semantic representation (RDF).

Before delving into these approaches, it is essential to outline the desired properties for data transformation to RDF:

- Support for a wide range of input formats and data sources.
- Support of streaming data.
- Capability to incorporate custom functions for use-case specific conversion/transformation, ensuring applicability across different applications.
- High efficiency in terms of processing time.
- Scalability through data-parallel processing.

DataLift [r1] is a data transformation framework providing an integrated platform for publishing datasets on the Linked Data Cloud. A wide range of data formats are supported such as Comma-Separated Values (CSV), eXtensible Markup Language (XML) and Environmental Systems Research Institute (ESRI) shapefiles. A two-step approach is followed, where in the first step input data is transformed to raw RDF, whereas in the second step SPARQL Construct queries are used to generate 'well-formed' RDF based on selected vocabularies. However, DataLift lacks support for streaming data sources and the integration of custom data processing functions, limiting its broader applicability.

RML [r2] introduced a more flexible approach, providing a mapping language for expressing mappings between multiple heterogeneous sources and ontology terms. RML can process large datasets, as it does not heavily depend on in-memory processing and supports custom data processing functions using a script language, namely FnO [r3]. However, the custom functions require re-definition in every mapping's specification, leading to increased time for overall RDF generation process. Experimental results [r4] have shown that RML (such as D2RML [r5], KR2RML [r6], GeoTriples [r7]) based approaches have performance limitations.

RMLStreamer, introduced by Haesendonck et al. [r8], builds upon Apache Flink to parallelise and distribute the ingestion tasks over multiple nodes, aiming to scale with data volume. However, it relies on Flink's memory management for processing large data sets. An input operator that consumes CSV, JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) and XML data formats is used for the data ingestion phase. Parallel processing is limited on CSV data, where a parallel input operator can be used to parallelise the process over multiple nodes, while

in case of JSON and XML formats, a sequential input generator is used. In addition to that, no other data formats are supported, such as binary grib or Environmental Systems Research Institute (ESRI) shapefiles and there is no support for custom functions on data transformation and conversion.

SPARQL-Generate [r9] offers a different approach by enabling data transformation from various formats, designed as an extension of SPARQL 1.1, so it can be implemented on top on any existing SPARQL engine. Although, the latest version of SPARQL-Generate can process Websocket streams and HTTP GET requests, it can only be used on top of a triple store and lacks support for parallel processing. Additionally, the definition of custom functions is not straightforward in the general case since it requires the SPARQL engine to be re-compiled. Similar approaches that depend on (specific) triple stores, such as OntoRefine tool of GraphDB, Sponger tool of Virtuoso, are not considered as general solutions since they are dependent on specific triple-stores, and they cannot be evaluated in a standalone mode. Although the majority of the above methods support a wide variety of data formats, only a few supports custom functions for data filtering, conversion and interlinking. Moreover, scalability and parallel data processing are important criteria to be considered, especially on big data processing or on a low power consumption-oriented approach, where resources have to be efficiently used.

Prior work developed in UPRC, RDF-Gen [r10], is introduced to bridge this gap, since it supports data transformation from various data formats, including streaming and archival sources. RDF-Gen can operate as a server, transforming data via HTTP POST requests and responding with the generated output, which can be automatically uploaded to a triple store (local or remote), or simply stored in local Turtle (TTL) files. RDF-Gen enables the description of custom functions by implementing Java methods that can be invoked at runtime, while it provides built-in functionality for data interlinking. Experimental results [r10] have demonstrated RDF-Gen's scalability and performance compared to the SotA approaches.

B. SotA in Incentive mechanisms for Data Anonymisation and Sharing

Incentive Mechanisms for Data Anonymisation and Sharing revolves around designing effective strategies to motivate individuals and organisations to anonymise and share their data. These mechanisms strike a balance between the need for data privacy and the benefits of data sharing, leveraging incentives such as financial rewards, access to proprietary algorithms or insights, and enhanced reputation. Interactions between data owners are made through a data market platform (implemented in a distributed ledger technology, specifically Internet Of Things Application (IOTA)) that orchestrates all processes, integrating a set of mathematical algorithms to ensure fair data exchange and compensations.

B.1. Incentive mechanisms for data sharing

Collaboration among various data owners or agents has the potential to enhance the forecasting accuracy of statistical learning methods due to spatio-temporal dependencies in geographically dispersed time series data. This collaborative approach has been supported in various domains: (a) wind energy forecasting has benefited from combining geographically distributed power measurements from aggregated wind power plants [r11] and individual turbine-level data [r12]; (b) solar energy forecasting has improved by using measurements from distributed small-scale photovoltaic systems [r13] and sensors like pyranometers and satellites [r14]; (c) other Renewable Energy Sources (RES) technologies, such as wave energy [r15] and load forecasting [r16] can also gain from data exchange among different owners and sources; and (d) non-energy-related fields, such as supply chains forecasting and control [r17], traffic flow forecasting [r18], and retail prices forecasting [r19] have also proven to benefit from spatio-temporal data sharing.

Despite the potential advantages of data sharing, reluctance among data owners to cooperate persists. Two key requirements for engaging data owners in data-sharing platforms are data privacy and compensation, whether monetary or non-monetary. While recent developments in FL propose privacy-preserving protocols for combining and forecasting time series data from different owners, companies competing in the same markets or individuals resistant to data sharing often lack incentives to share data such as power measurements. One possible incentive mechanism is data monetisation, wherein data sellers receive a share of the monetary gain from forecast skill improvement in a specific UC, which can be reinforced by integrating data privacy protocols.

The current landscape of data markets and sharing incentive mechanisms can be categorised as follows:

- 1) Game theory approaches, such as cooperative no-regret mechanisms utilising Shapley fairness [r20], or two-stage Stackelberg games for joint profit maximisation of data broker and consumer [r21], or combinations of differential privacy with game theoretic negotiation mechanisms [r22].
- 2) Social welfare maximisation methods, like iterative auction mechanisms where selfish bidders submit offers to maximise their utility functions [r22], and probabilistic choice models exploring data owners' risk-aversion and incentivising unbiased data sharing through certainty-equivalent games based on utility theory [r23].
- 3) Multi-armed bandit strategies where data consumers sequentially interact with multiple data owners, integrating privacy protection in dynamic pricing [r24].
- 4) Bidirectional data sharing, where agents exchange data without monetary transactions, formulated as a graph formation game [r25].

GREEN.DAT.AI aims to design and test a set of incentive mechanisms for data sharing, focusing on attracting data consumers and increasing revenue from data sellers. Two main types of mechanisms will be considered in GREEN.DAT.AI: (a) data monetisation departing from data auction solutions of past projects such as H2020 Smart4RES, namely game theory and social welfare maximisation; (b) barter trading, in particular data-by-data (processed as raw material) exchange schemes leveraged by distributed ledger technology (IOTA).

B.2. Data marketplaces using blockchain

Data marketplaces built with blockchain technology are at the forefront of a transformative shift in global data assets exchange [r26]. These marketplaces, functioning as ecosystems and not only as transactional hubs, stimulate collaboration, innovation, and significant value creation across multiple industries.

By harnessing blockchain's inherent characteristics, these marketplaces ensure data integrity, authenticity, and accessibility, thus transforming the dynamics of data exchange. The essence of these data marketplaces lies in their capacity to democratise access to valuable data, dismantling traditional barriers to entry and eliminating central points of control. This democratisation fosters a more equitable data economy, enabling participation of individuals and organizations, regardless of size or geographic location. Furthermore, the transparency provided by blockchain technology instils a higher degree of trust among participants, a crucial factor in an ecosystem where data is a critical asset [r26]. Until now, blockchain technologies in data markets have been primarily employed for generic IoT applications [r21], [r27] rather than being specifically tailored for forecasting use cases as within GREEN.DAT.AI. An exception exists [r28], which implements a blockchain-based data transmission market for both centralised and decentralised energy imbalance markets, albeit without a market clearing mechanism for data sellers and buyers. In [r29], a 3-tier decentralised data marketplace architectural design with smart contracts is presented, eliminating the need for intermediaries in managing agreement terms, though it raises concerns about potential malicious behaviour. Unlike other approaches, [r30] integrates with a publish/subscribe system to deliver real-time data streams to interested

consumers while continuously monitoring information flow for monetisation purposes. The rationale for adopting blockchain is presented in [r31], emphasising users' need to purchase and monitor certified and trusted data streams from a smart city without intermediaries, utilising IOTA technology. This decentralised marketplace allows for truly peer-to-peer transactions without centralised authorities levying fees. Apart from IOTA, which will be further described below, EOS is another blockchain project aiming to create scalable, decentralised applications on top of an existing blockchain architecture [r32]. The EOS project addresses crucial aspects such as creating peer-to-peer terms of service agreements and separating authentication from application, essential elements for establishing a decentralised peer-to-peer data marketplace. The EOS Whitepaper [r32] emphasises that, in blockchain, a pointer to relevant data should be stored instead of the content itself, highlighting the importance of relevance rather than bulk IoT data storage.

The next sub-sections explore the components and functionalities that define such marketplaces, emphasising the suitability of IOTA's unique technology in this context.

Blockchain Infrastructure. A blockchain infrastructure offers a distributed ledger technology to record and verify all transactions in a decentralised fashion [r29]. This foundational layer enhances the trustworthiness of data exchanges by ensuring the integrity and immutability of transactions. IOTA's Tangle technology [r33], a highly scalable and robust blockchain alternative, exemplifies this infrastructure by providing a feeless and scalable solution that supports a vast number of transactions, thus overcoming the limitations commonly associated with traditional blockchain systems.

Smart Contracts. Smart contracts can be revolutionary in the operation of data marketplaces, automating transactions execution and ensuring that agreements between data providers and consumers are enforced with transparency and security. The terms of these agreements are embedded directly into code, eliminating the need for intermediaries. IOTA supports the implementation of smart contracts [r34], thereby enabling automated transactional processes within the marketplace.

Data Providers and Consumers. The ecosystem of blockchain-based data marketplaces thrives on the dynamic interaction between data providers and data consumers, each playing pivotal roles in the value exchange process. Data providers, ranging from individual creators to large-scale corporations, are integral in contributing their valuable data assets to the marketplace. Consumers are the end users that are interested in buying the raw data or a value-added service. They can be private or government organizations or individual users. A consumer queries the system defining the required data and other aspects. Instead of storing the data directly on the blockchain, which is impractical due to size and scalability concerns, blockchain technology is used to manage the metadata, ownership, and transactions related to these data assets [r29]. This approach ensures the integrity and confidentiality of the data transfer process, without the need to store the actual data on the blockchain. By recording transactions and encrypting data access permissions on the blockchain, the technology acts as an intermediary that ensures secure, transparent, and verifiable exchanges between parties. This security measure is crucial; it not only protects the transaction records from unauthorised access but also builds trust among participants in the marketplace.

Tokenisation and Decentralised Governance. Tokenisation serves as a feature of blockchain-based data marketplaces, where tokens serve as the medium of exchange, allowing transactions across borders, reducing the need for traditional financial intermediaries and minimising transaction costs. IOTA's tokenisation features support feeless transactions, enhancing the efficiency of data exchanges within the ecosystem. Decentralised governance mechanisms may enable marketplace participants to influence platform policies, standards, and development roadmaps through a democratic voting process, ensuring that the marketplace evolves in a manner reflecting collective interests and inputs of its participants. IOTA's

governance model embodies this principle, ensuring a collaborative and transparent decision-making process.

The Case for IOTA. The choice of IOTA as the underlying technology for a data marketplace is compelling for several reasons. Beyond the mentioned blockchain features, IOTA's infrastructure is also distinguished by its feeless transactions and highly scalable nature, courtesy of the Tangle's graph-based structure. This enables the handling of a vast volume of transactions without the bottlenecks associated with traditional blockchain technologies. Additionally, IOTA aims for full decentralisation [r35], aligning with the ethos of blockchain to remove central points of control or failure, thus enhancing the robustness and reliability of the data marketplace. IOTA ability to support a high throughput of transactions, coupled with its already mentioned feeless model, ensures that IOTA-based marketplaces can operate at very large scales (which the IoT industry often demands). The technology's emphasis on full decentralisation not only secures the marketplace against potential vulnerabilities but also fosters a more equitable and participatory ecosystem.

C. SotA in Synthetic Data Generators

In this section, a brief overview of the SotA in mobility data generation is provided, which has been the focus of the WP3 activities related to synthetic data generation. Mobility data generation is typically addressed from three different perspectives, depending on the mobility component of interest: flows, namely the number of trips that move from a location to another one; trajectories, thus reproducing paths of single trips; individual mobility, concerned with the generation of a consistent sequence of trips for a single user.

C.1. Flow Generation

Generating realistic mobility flows is a challenging task that aims to create flows of people among a set of geographic locations based on demographic and geographic characteristics (e.g., population and distance). Traditionally, flow generation is addressed through the Gravity model [r36], the Radiation model [r37], and their variants [r38]. The Gravity model assumes that the number of travellers between two locations (flow) increases with the locations' populations while decreasing with the distance between them. The model has a few parameters to be fit over real data, expressing the weight that population and distance have in the computation. The Radiation model is a parameter-free model that only requires information about geographic locations (e.g., population), which considers the intervening opportunities among them (typically proportional to the population). The choice of the destination involves computing a fitness value for each location opportunity that represents the quality of the opportunity for each travel, and then ranking the opportunities according to their distance from the origin location to choose the nearest location with a fitness higher than a minimum threshold. More recently, some approaches have been proposed, that apply Deep Learning techniques to learn from historical flow data to recreate new flows, for instance MoGAN [r39], which utilises a Generative Adversarial schema on top of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), where flows between locations are represented as an image.

C.2. Trajectory Generation

The goal of a trajectory generation model is to create a set of trajectories (and not just the mobility demand) whose mobility patterns are statistically indistinguishable from those of real trips. In literature, three main types of approaches are common: mechanistic ones, based on Deep Learning, and, finally, combinations of both these approaches.

Diary-based TRAjectory Simulator [r40] is a framework to generate synthetic trajectories based on a data-driven algorithm (diary generator) that creates a mobility diary, and a trajectory generator based on

preferential return and exploration mechanism (d-EPR). Global Positioning System (GPS) data and Call Detail Records (CDRs) are used to train the diary generator and fit the parameters of d-EPR. The diary generator is based on a Markov Model and trained on trajectories data, which describes the probability that an individual follows or breaks the typical routine. The trajectory generator transforms the mobility diary into a sampled mobility trajectory, adding geographical positions to abstract locations. An individual force that makes an agent more prone to come back to previously visited locations (preferential return) coexists with a collective force that pushes an agent to visit new places collectively relevant (preferential exploration).

The model presented in [r41] is based on a combination of Variational Autoencoders (VAE) and Seq2Seq network and leads to the creation of a Sequential VAE. This model can combine the VAE's ability to construct a latent space that captures salient features of the training data with the ability regarding the processing of sequence-to-sequence models. Sequential VAE has an Encoding Layer, based on Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) that learns a vector representation from an input sequence of fixed dimensionality; a Variational Layer, that takes in input the intermediate vector from the encoder and learns the hidden space using multivariate Gaussian distribution to approximate the real posterior distribution of human mobility; and a Decoding Layer, also based on LSTM, that resamples from the learned distribution to reconstruct human trajectories.

The solution proposed in [r42] is a two-step model made by an Input-Output Hidden Markov Model (IO-HMM), that creates a chain of labelled activities; and an LSTM network to learn from trajectory sequences. The main advantage of IO-HMM is that the transition probabilities depend on contextual variables, such as the time of the day or day of the week.

C.3. Individual Mobility Generation

The challenge of defining an individual user's mobility model is commonly addressed in literature using three approaches: Markov chains, mixture of general laws and pattern discovery. An example belonging to the first category is [r43] which characterises and classifies user's Point of Interests (POIs) according to their relevance for the user: mostly visited POIs, occasionally visited POIs, exceptionally visited POIs, and build a Markov chain using the movements and the stops duration to weight the chain. In [r44] the authors use Markov chains and a mixture of data-driven mobility laws to generalise the user's behaviour from the geography, and to describe them in terms of their preferential exploration or return tendencies [r45]. Then they use the models to generate synthetic trajectories maintaining some properties of original data, e.g. number of locations per user, radius of gyration, mobility entropy.

In [r46] a non-parametric Bayesian method for modelling collections of timestamped events is proposed. The authors use a Dirichlet process for learning a set of intensity functions which form a basis set for representing individual time-periods which are exploited for 'unusual' events detection. A general law approach is also followed by [r47] where the authors state that human trajectories show a high degree of spatio-temporal regularity, with each individual being characterised by a time-independent characteristic travel distance and a significant probability to return to a few highly frequented locations.

The work in [r48] presents a data-driven approach which uses mobility patterns to predict the future positions of a user when it matches the pattern premises. Other approaches related to pattern discovery consider external factors such as social relationship. In [r49] a locations recommender is presented, based on past user behaviour, the locations' venues, the social relationships, and the similarity among users. In [r50] it is empirically observed that the movements of a user can be classified as short and long: short-distance travels and long-distance travels, where the former is based on periodic behaviours, while the latter is more likely to happen due to social influence. Besides the type of model, another crucial aspect is the

strategy adopted for managing the spatial and temporal dimensions. Most of the existing approaches discretise them using grids computed over the whole data. Anagnostopoulos et al. [r51] map the real position of the users in a hexagonal grid. Zheng et al. [r52] make use of a grid-based technique to extract interesting locations. This generalisation of the locations simplifies the problem and makes it more manageable, with only a minimal impact on the output quality. Finally, the model presented by Guidotti et al. [r53] extracts a user's personal mobility model and uses it to reproduce their personal mobility agenda, representing the predicted positions where the user accomplishes their activities during the whole day. The approach is completely unsupervised, adaptive to different users and mobility scenarios. The method exploits some existing SotA mobility models, such as mobility profiles and routines [r54], and Individual Mobility Networks (IMNs) [r55].

D. SotA in Large-scale time series analytics

In this section, we delve into the domain of Large-scale time series analytics, a critical component of modern data analytics frameworks. Time series data, characterised by sequential observations recorded over time, presents unique challenges in analysis and interpretation, especially at scale. Specifically, SotA methodologies and advancements in large-scale time series analytics are explored, focusing on two specific directions: trajectory-based battery consumption estimation and EV transaction data forecasting, representing significant areas of interest within the domain of EV charging time series analytics. Recent mathematical models and open-source tools are exploited, enabling battery consumption estimation and analysis, along with complex mobility application software. Furthermore, literature on predicting EV parking duration and charged energy, including ensemble approaches and models trained on features like calendar, weather, electricity prices, and traffic data, is reviewed, while various ML techniques are assessed against their effectiveness in forecasting EV charging demand.

D.1. Trajectory-based battery consumption estimation

Estimating battery consumption is fundamental for assessing impact or limitations of EV mobility compared to traditional internal combustion engines (ICEs). Recent literature has proposed several mathematical models to infer consumption from vehicles characteristics and movement dynamics. Most of them (e.g. [r56], [r57], [r58], [r59]) are based on the same basic elements: consider air and rolling resistances, the efficiency of the engine internal attrition, road slope, energy-consuming devices onboard (e.g. air conditioning), etc., where the physical parameters of the vehicle are estimated from sample car models, and some constants in the formulas are empirically determined. In terms of actual implementations, several open-source libraries and solutions have been proposed, that integrate battery consumption estimates at some level.

EmobPy is an open source, python-based tool that can create battery EV time series. It can create four different time series: vehicle mobility, driving electricity consumption, grid availability, and grid electricity demand time series. It also includes energy needs for accessories and heating/cooling, as well as the charging and discharging losses of the battery. The time series of grid availability provides information whether a vehicle is connected to the electricity grid in a time step and if so, with what power rating for charging or discharging. The time series of grid electricity demand provides information on how much electricity a vehicle demands from the electricity grid in a time step. The tool is based on the model in [r56].

VencoPy [r60] is designed to simulate and analyse the energy consumption profiles associated with EV usage by accessing comprehensive travel survey datasets, which enable the determination of both minimum and maximum battery constraints for EVs. It can simulate scenarios based on different EV battery sizes, specific energy consumption rates, home charging availability, and maximum charging powers. Through these

simulations, VencoPy can predict how changes in user behaviour or charging infrastructure might impact overall energy consumption and efficiency of EV.

DataFev [r61] is a Python package that serves as a framework for the development, testing, and assessment of management algorithms for EV charging scenarios. It facilitates the creation of scenario-oriented management strategies, which are crucial for addressing the complex interactions between multiple intelligent agents, such as EV drivers and charging station operators, within the EV charging ecosystem. DataFev's capabilities are geared towards optimising these interactions through dynamic simulations and the optimisation of charging processes, which are essential for improving the efficiency and reliability of EV charging management concepts.

The EV Path and Range Estimator (EVPRE) [r62] software is essentially a routing algorithm aimed at optimising the energy management of EVs. By leveraging a complex set of vehicular parameters and environmental data, EVPRE computes routes that are calibrated to conserve energy, thereby extending the effective range of EVs and diminishing the frequency of recharging intervals required. EVPRE's algorithmic sophistication lies in its integration of vehicular data analytics with real-time environmental sensing.

In addition to the tools mentioned above, some complex mobility application software have been developed and commercialised, also providing energy consumption information. The most popular include FASTSimTM [r63], that provides a simple way to compare powertrains and estimate the impact of technology improvements on light-, medium-, and heavy-duty vehicle efficiency, performance, cost, and battery life; SUMO, which is an open-source, highly portable, microscopic and continuous road traffic simulation package designed to handle large road networks. It is widely used for traffic management and transportation planning, and it also provides an energy estimation model for EVs; finally, many EV manufacturers have their proprietary software solutions integrated into their vehicles, such as Tesla, Nissan, and Chevrolet, who have onboard systems that estimate range and consumption based on real-time conditions.

D.2. EV Transaction Data Forecasting

As the adoption of EVs accelerates, it is essential to address the challenges associated with power demand management without a significant burden on the grid, as well as the need for investment on charging infrastructure. ML forecasting services can provide an accurate prediction of charging duration and energy requirements, enabling an optimal deployment of charging stations, efficient energy distribution, and to unlock flexibility as a service to the grid. Most part of the available literature relies on predicting EV parking duration and charged energy. Some authors employ an ensemble approach combining both duration and energy forecasts to achieve an improved accuracy.

EV charging modelling can be implemented for individual vehicles [r64], university campuses [r65], single charging stations [r66] and several charging stations [r67], [r68]. In terms of model training features, calendar [r69], [r70], [r71] and weather [r72] data are commonly used. Electricity prices [r66] and traffic [r73] data is also used, but to a lesser extent. For instance, an approach to predict EV user behaviour using several ML and Deep learning tools has been presented [r71]. Particularly, users were categorized into regular and irregular users. The proposed method predicted both charged energy and session duration. Observed model Mean Absolute Error (MAE) was significantly lower for category specific models compared to general ones. Furthermore, the parking duration forecasting has been approached from the idle time perspective [r74]. That is, how much time the EV is expected to be parked after full charge. The methods employed were Random Forest, Gradient Boosting and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), with XGBoost slightly outperforming the other methods.

Additionally, there are works employing LSTM ANNs, such as an LSTM model developed to predict the EV energy demand at the station level up to 5 hours ahead [r68]. The proposed model outperformed the reference ANN and AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) models. Different settings of data structure and forecasting horizon were also tested. However, the authors concluded that data structure did not impact model accuracy as much as forecasting horizon, with 1-hour ahead being the best-case scenario. Also, LSTM models have been used to forecast day-ahead charging demand to a hospital's charging station [r75]. By incorporating calendar and weather features, the proposed model achieved a reduction in MAE by 28.8%. Moreover, an LSTM model has been proposed for 24h-ahead forecasting of EV charging information of an individual vehicle [r76]. The proposed method provides prediction on charging duration and how many charging sessions are expected to be conducted over the period.

Forecasting EV charging sessions is complex due to the unpredictable nature of demand, which is influenced by various factors such as charging station infrastructure, location, weather conditions, and other relevant elements. Additionally, the behaviour of individual users plays a significant role in the models' accuracy, making it difficult to capture using traditional statistical tools. Nonetheless, by carefully selecting models, refining features, and conducting well-organised case studies, ML becomes a powerful tool for optimising smart charging strategies by offering precise and reliable forecasts.

E. SotA in Federated & Auto ML at the edge/fog

FL and AutoML at the edge/fog involves cutting-edge advancements in deploying ML models directly on edge and fog computing devices, enabling efficient processing of data close to its source, thereby reducing latency and bandwidth requirements. FL techniques allow collaborative model training across distributed edge devices while preserving data privacy. AutoML algorithms tailored for edge/fog environments automate the process of model selection, optimisation, and deployment, empowering edge devices with intelligent capabilities without extensive human intervention.

E.1. Vertical Federated Learning

To merge data from diverse owners, various statistical methods have emerged. One such method is the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model, which is commonly used in collaborative forecasting of time series data owned by different parties. In sectors like energy, the VAR model helps in refining short-term forecasts (e.g. 15min to 6h ahead) using real-time data from sensors and power generation sources like wind turbines and solar inverters.

Additionally, the involvement of multiple data owners favours the use of distributed optimisation algorithms to estimate the coefficients of the model, like the Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM). Collaborative forecasting with VAR models has applications across various domains such as supply chain management [r77], traffic flow prediction [r18], and retail price forecasting [r19]. However, concerns about data privacy remain a significant barrier. To address these concerns, it is essential to develop privacy-preserving algorithms for estimating the coefficients of the model, ensuring the security of personal and sensitive data.

To solve this optimisation problem without compromising data privacy, a critical literature review has been made in [r78] showing that existing privacy-preserving techniques are unsatisfactory. For example, collaborative learning focuses on data split by observations, where agents estimate a local model and then only share the features coefficients to build the final model. However, spatial data is distributed by features, therefore features from other agents are unknown and coefficients cannot be assigned.

As a result of such analysis, a novel solution has been put forth to encrypt the data in such a way that data owners can solve the Least Absolute Shrinkage (LASSO)-VAR model [r79] without disclosing their private data. A key property of this encryption protocol is that model accuracy is not affected as happens with differential privacy, where random noise is added to sensible data and a trade-off exists between privacy and model accuracy. Additionally, there are no third parties to generate encryption keys to avoid trust in third parties.

While the VAR model is commonly used, it was designed to capture linear relationships between time series, which is a strong assumption in many UCs. For example, to predict wind power for 24h-ahead, the use of wind speed forecasts is crucial and the relation between wind speed and power is known to be non-linear.

Extensions of the VAR model allow for the inclusion of additional information and modelling of non-linear relationships with past data. Extending with additive model structures have been explored, and recent work has shown that non-linear extensions of linear models, e.g., by transforming input variables using polynomial transformations, can be similar to complex ANNs when modelling dynamical systems [r80]. However, none of these extensions have considered the data privacy issues.

E.2. AutoML in Classification

One of the most prominent frameworks in the field is AutoSklearn [r81] written in python as a wrapper of the popular ML library scikit-learn. It employs Bayesian optimisation and model ensembles to provide the final pipeline. Auto-Sklearn 2.0 [r82] further extends this work by better budget allocation and a different meta-feature space. AutoWeka [r83] uses SMAC for optimisation and is based upon the WEKA analysis framework. The same problem is also tackled through genetic optimisation by TPOT [r84] and TPOT 2 [r85] which improves over its predecessor on pipeline representation and genetic algorithm specification. Finally, Google Vizier [r86] covers dynamic optimisation algorithm selection and various early stopping criteria to reduce unnecessary costs.

E.3. AutoML in Clustering

In this section we list the most recent advancements in the field. We classify each work according to the taxonomy presented in Poulakis, et al. [r87].

Algorithm Selection. Some of the earliest works in the field target solely algorithm selection but rely on datasets that hold information on ground truth, i.e. the cluster in which each data set instance belongs. The work of Souto et al. [r88] is the first of such efforts. In this study, for a set of 24 gene expression datasets several algorithms are tested to identify the best performing one and a set of meta-features that rely on ground truth are extracted, which combined are provided as input to train a meta-learner classifier. Nascimento et al. [r89] extend this work by including a set of five additional meta-features and by employing the MLRules algorithm to address which meta-features mostly impact the meta-learner decision. In [r90] the meta-learning task of interest is to predict the actual performance of each algorithm instead of predicting the best performing one.

More recent works explore algorithm selection for data sets without ground truth. Ferrari et al [r91] introduce algorithm scoring systems based on a set of multiple internal cluster validity indices. Additionally, they propose a novel set of meta-features that is extracted from the distance distribution of the instances. The same meta-features are also extracted from the pairwise correlation distribution of data set instances [r92]. Finally, in Marco-Ge [r93] algorithm selection is tackled with meta-features that are extracted through a graph ANN trained to predict the best performing algorithm.

Hyperparameter Tuning. Several approaches also consider optimisation for hyperparameter tuning. The main differentiating factor among works is which objective function they aim to optimise. In AutoClust [r94] internal cluster validity indices are used to train regressors that predict external validity indices which in turn are used as the objective for optimisation. Additionally, a set of landmarking based meta-features is proposed based on the evaluation of the MeanShift algorithm. AutoML4Clust [r95] tests Bayesian optimisation with different internal validity measures as objectives. In CsmartML [r96] the framework learns to associate three internal to one external validity index by measuring their correlation and performing meta-learning, which are then provided to a genetic optimisation algorithm. Csmart Glassbox [r97] provides a graphical interface for AutoML and meta-learners that predict the necessary budget for the optimisation procedure. Autocluster [r98] employs an ensemble of models built over grid search results and includes landmarking based meta-features for initial model selection. Finally, TPE-AutoClust [r99] also uses an ensemble of clustering models that are selected through multi-objective genetic optimisation.

E.4. AutoML in Time Series Forecasting

AutoML in time series forecasting is the least explored of the tasks presented in this section. Auto-Pytorch-TS [r100] is an Automated Deep Learning framework that aims to provide an efficient approach for the joint Neural Architecture Search problem and optimisation of the hyperparameters of the entire data processing pipeline for time series forecasting. According to a given budget, the framework's optimiser searches among different neural architectures and hyperparameters from the configuration space, selecting firstly the most promising algorithms and then tuning them. To achieve this, it uses a Bayesian Optimisation approach. AutoGluon [r101] is an AutoML framework for probabilistic time series forecasting. Using a variety of forecasting models (both local and global ones) it is taking advantage of both classical statistical and Machine/Deep Learning models, fits the models and then extracts an ensemble using a convex combination of the predicted values.

F. SotA in Explainable AI/Feature Learning with Privacy Preservation

Feature learning combines a multitude of techniques that address improved data representation for increasing performance of ML models [r102]. These methods are replacing traditional approaches to feature engineering in many ML applications, ranging from speech recognition and computer vision to general signal processing [r103], [r104], [r105]. Feature learning methods can be divided into unsupervised and supervised. Unsupervised approaches learn from unlabelled data, while supervised approaches learn from labelled data. The latter therefore also enable the evaluation of the created models, which can be directly measured according to the error in labelling the learning samples. As the quality of the used features can also be evaluated in this way [r106], this report focuses only on these. These can be roughly divided into:

- Traditional feature engineering,
- Feature selection approaches,
- Dimensionality reduction techniques,
- Supervised dictionary learning, and
- Deep learning.

These techniques are explored further to understand their role in encoding explainable decision-making processes for knowledge discovery. Note that despite focusing on classification, rationales discussed below are also compelling when considering regression problems. Finally, knowledge discovery is also addressed in this section through the review of Explainable AI in the context of unsupervised learning, in particular explainable clustering approaches that can enhance the capacities of all previously discussed methods. This

emerged as an important task in the project UCs as a means to explore and better understand data, in particular to identify potentially new behaviours (e.g. fraudulent-looking profiles) not known a priori in the applications.

F.1. Traditional feature engineering

Traditionally, feature engineering consists of user administered [r102]:

- feature construction,
- feature evaluation, and
- feature selection steps.

Feature construction is defined as the formation of new features by applying transformations on individual feature or combining them with mathematical operators, such as logical, arithmetic, trigonometric and aggregation operators [r107]. However, the number of features built in this way is predetermined by the user [r108]. Evolutionary algorithms allow automatic recombination of input features with little or no user interaction. The input features represent the population, and the scoring function is defined by metrics that determine the ability to separate feature samples between different classes. Traits are recombined in crossover and mutation steps. The construction of new features from the input data set using arithmetic operators has been demonstrated [r109]. The evaluation metrics of the characteristics defined in this way include information gain, Gini index, chi-square and their sum.

Feature construction is followed by their evaluation that is traditionally achieved by evaluating the classification models trained on them. The choice of classifier has a strong influence on the evaluation results, while its learning is often time-consuming. The latter is particularly evident in cases of a large number of characteristics [r110]. To avoid the use of a classifier, techniques for analysing the discriminatory power of characteristics in the form of the ratio between the distances of samples of different classes and samples of the same class have been researched. Examples of these include Fisher's criterion, the Laplacian estimator, and the maximum edge principle [r111]. An alternative possibility is to calculate the correlation coefficient (e.g., Pearson's or Spearman's) between the characteristic values and the class labels. Although the mentioned techniques only cover linear interdependencies between characteristic values and class labels, they are computationally efficient and enable the interpretability of the final model. Approaches based on the information contribution classify the features according to the ratio between the class entropy and the conditional entropy of the feature values [r112]. Similar results can also be achieved with the Gini impurity estimation technique [r113] or techniques based on the calculation of mutual information. Their main advantage is the successful capture of non-linear relationships between features and labels classes [r113]. Nevertheless, such approaches favour characteristics with a large number of different values, which can cause overfitting. Feature selection is the last step of this process. Since it is often applied separately, i.e. as separate feature learning approaches, it is described in more detail next.

F.2. Feature selection and dimensionality reduction

Feature selection methods reduce the dimensionality of the input feature space by trying to select a subset of 'important features' (i.e. features that improve classification accuracy) and remove irrelevant or redundant ones, which contributes to faster learning of ML models. Although such methods do not change the definition of the features themselves, and are therefore explainable, their efficiency in classification is limited, as they are not able to introduce new or recombine existing features. We divide them into three groups [r114], namely:

- Feature filtering is usually performed with a threshold value. Although such methods are computationally very efficient, their classification power largely depends on the feature quality assessment technique. The latter often take into account only pairwise dependencies between features and class labels, while neglecting correlations between features. As a result, the effectiveness of such classification is limited [r115].
- Envelope-based methods select a subset of features that maximises the performance of a given classifier. The latter is understood as a multi-criteria optimisation problem of maximising classification accuracy while simultaneously minimising the number of selected features. This can be addressed with several optimisation techniques, such as sequential selection algorithms or nature-inspired algorithms, such as they are evolutionary and genetic algorithm, particle swarm optimisation and bee algorithm [r116].
- Built-in methods are considered embedded methods, known for their lower execution times. They perform the selection of a subset of features in interaction with the classifier in the learning phase of the model and are thus tied to the selected classifier. For example, decision trees achieve feature selection based on mutual information evaluation, while support vector methods use LASSO regression analysis [r117].

In contrast, dimensionality reduction techniques make this possible. These are based on the assumption that high-dimensional learning patterns are often distributed near a low-dimensional linear or non-linear manifold. Accordingly, the recombination of features is achieved by mapping learning patterns onto them. As such mappings inevitably change the distances between the training samples, they often increase the presence of noise in the training data. Moreover, in the case of using non-linear combinations, there is a risk that the final classification models become unexplainable [r118]. Such approaches always reduce the dimensionality of the representation but cannot increase the input feature space.

F.3. Supervised dictionary learning

In contrast to feature selection or dimensionality reduction, supervised dictionary learning methods build a new feature space from the input data with a linear or non-linear combination of an arbitrary number of base vectors, called atoms [r118]. Accordingly, dictionary learning is considered to be an optimisation problem, the goal of which is to gradually increase the sparsity of the input representation while minimising the reconstruction error. The latter is defined as the difference between the test data and the result of the sparse representation. Most of the proposed approaches solve this optimisation problem iteratively by updating individual criteria step-by-step. As the number of classes increases, so does the number of performed iterations, which increases the computational complexity. An alternative option is to introduce classification error as an additional optimisation criterion in dictionary learning. The result in this case represents a shared dictionary that is tuned for a given classifier. Although such approaches are usually classification efficient, sparse representation may be reflected in interpretable models. This is especially evident in cases where the dictionary contains a large number of items. The computational complexity of dictionary learning is further increased by the required non-convex optimisation and tuning of many input parameters [r119].

F.4. Deep learning

Similar to dictionary learning, Deep Learning methods also undergo computationally demanding feature optimisations in the presence of a large number of local optima in high-dimensional spaces. Deep methods are based on different architectures of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), with several hidden layers of neurons, which enable the gradual multi-level structuring of features from raw input data. By increasing the depth, ANNs are able to learn complex decision logic and thus achieve high classification accuracies. Unfortunately, this also increases the number of necessary iterations to tune them. These types of methods

are also black boxes, because the learned intermediate characteristics are highly abstract and incomprehensible to humans [r120].

In general, we can therefore conclude that traditional feature learning approaches are either inexplicable or limited in their accuracy, which is a consequence of the inability to recombine input features. Approaches that allow increasing the dimensionality of the input feature space are also computationally demanding, as they require iterative non-convex optimisations and tuning of many configurations of hidden dimensions.

F.5. Interpretable clustering

In the literature, the problem of understanding and explaining a clustering result has been tackled mainly using two strategies. The idea behind the first strategy is to create balanced trees and to reduce the average distance between points in the same partition as much as possible, thus aiming at cluster compactness in a way similar to centre-based methods like k-Means [r121]. For example, k-d trees [r122], is a space-partitioning data structure for organising points in a k-dimensional space that splits a node using the median value of a feature as the threshold. The selected feature often has the largest variance in the data. Other similar approaches consist of Random Projection tree [r123] and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) trees [r124]. These methods are similar to k-d trees, except that they choose a random direction in the case of Random Projection trees and the median value along the first eigenvector of the covariance matrix in the case of PCA trees.

The second strategy consist in determine the partitioning features by optimising some metric, either locally or globally. For example, TIC [r125] uses maximum distance between prototypes as a splitting criterion and the F-test as a stopping condition. CLTree [r126] is based on a supervised decision tree construction that uses uniformly at random synthetic points to capture the natural distribution of the data. A simplified approach to CLTree is outlined in [r127], wherein k-Means is initially employed to cluster the data, and the cluster assignment labels are then utilised as classes for a decision tree classifier. The fidelity of the explanation significantly relies on the accuracy score of the trained decision tree, owing to the distinct partitioning strategies employed by k-Means and the decision tree. A method for hierarchical clustering based on trees where the selection of the splitting attribute is established with respect to four measures based on heterogeneity has been proposed [r128]. Moreover, additional split criteria and agglomeration measures have been developed [r129]. TASC [r130] partitions data space by constructing a decision tree using one attribute set and measures the degree of similarity through another one.

Recent approaches returning clustering trees focus on interpretability to address the need for eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) [r131]. Iterative Mistake Minimisation (IMM) [r132] recursively builds a binary tree to minimise mistakes in k-Means. ExKMC [r132], [r133] extends IMM to allow for more accurate but less interpretable clustering trees. Ex-Greedy [r134] additionally boosts ExKMC, while ExShallow [r135] favours the construction of shallow trees by accounting for the depth through a penalty term. K-Means Tree (kMT) [r136] extends k-Means optimising tree and centroids jointly for fast clustering. Gabidolla and Carreira-Perpinan [r137] create oblique trees on top of any clustering method defined by optimizing a cost function.

G. SotA in Federated & Automatic Transfer Learning

FL involves advancements in privacy-preserving collaborative learning, allowing multiple parties to train a shared model without sharing raw data. Automatic Transfer Learning, on the other hand, focuses on developing algorithms capable of transferring knowledge from a pre-trained source domain to a target domain automatically, enabling efficient adaptation to new tasks or environments with minimal human intervention. Both areas continue to see significant research efforts aimed at improving scalability, efficiency,

and performance across various applications. Federated transfer learning marks a transformative shift, enabling training across decentralised data sources. This pioneering paradigm is poised to revolutionise the way AI algorithms leverage geographically disparate datasets, promoting collaboration and knowledge sharing while respecting data privacy and security.

G.1. Federated Learning

FL is a branch of Distributed Machine Learning (DML) that trains centralised models using decentralised data [r138]. Compared to DML, FL algorithms are fundamentally different and are primarily concerned with data privacy. Considering the characteristics of the data owners, two main FL variants have been identified, namely, cross-silo and cross-device FL [r139]. Cross-device FL is suitable for large groups of participants with slow or unreliable internet connections, such as mobile applications, where training data comes from users' interaction [r140]. Cross-silo FL, on the other hand, is suitable for small groups of participants who share a common incentive to collaboratively train an ML model based on their data but are unable to share them directly due to cost or legal constraints (e.g., GDPR).

There are two main methodologies for creating the global model in FL. The first method, built on DML, involves averaging the gradients of all local models and performing Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) on the global model, known as Gradient Averaging [r141]. However, due to privacy issues regarding data leakage from gradients [r142], another approach is preferred called Model Averaging, where the models' weights are averaged instead of their gradients. Both methods are referred to as Federated Averaging (FedAvg) [r141]. Following the same line of research, FedAvg has been extended to accommodate the use of adaptive optimisation schemes [r143], such as Adam [r144], YOGI [r145], and AdaGrad [r146]. In their approach the clients use SGD for local model training, while the aggregation server uses any of the aforementioned optimisation schemes in order to update the parameters of the global model. By focusing on adaptive server optimisation, they enable use of adaptive learning rates without increase in client storage or communication costs, while ensuring compatibility with cross-device FL [r143].

Except network and communication efficiency and client availability [r147], another key challenge of federated optimisation is the training parties' heterogeneity with respect to their local datasets [r140]. In order to address the former two issues, FedAvg performs multiple local updates on the available clients before communicating to the server. While this approach works well when participants' data are homogeneous, it is unsuccessful with heterogeneous parties. Each step causes the parties' locally fitted ML models to converge to various local optima, introducing slow and unreliable convergence to the global model. This phenomenon is known as 'client-drift', and in order to avoid it, fewer local updates and/or lower learning rates must be used, actions that have a significant impact on the convergence stability of FedAvg.

Karimireddy et al. [r148] acknowledge the aforementioned issue and propose a new federated optimisation framework called SCAFFOLD, which uses control variates (variance reduction) in order to approximate an ideal unbiased update, thus accounting for 'client-drift' in its local updates. By experimenting on various optimisation settings, the authors demonstrate that SCAFFOLD is resilient to client sampling (i.e., independent of the amount of client heterogeneity) and consistently outperforms FedAvg on non-convex functions (i.e., deep neural networks). Further following this line of research, FedProx [r149] presents an extension to FedAvg, which adds a regularisation term in the clients' cost function to restrict local updates to be closer to the initial (global) model. In a similar fashion, the qFedAvg algorithm [r150] introduces a novel optimisation objective inspired by fair resource allocation in wireless networks that encourages a more uniform accuracy distribution across devices in federated networks.

Closest to our work, Taik et al. [r151] present the first application of FL within the context of energy demand forecasting. Using a baseline LSTM based NN, they demonstrate the soundness of FL towards the aforementioned task in terms of bandwidth gain and privacy preservation, as well as the effect of personalisation of the global model on the accuracy of the edge devices' data. Towards more recent works, Menegatti et al., [r152], propose a novel consensus-based protocol for decentralised FL, and assess its performance compared to centralised and distributed approach over a baseline LSTM NN. Their experimental study over an open energy demand dataset, demonstrates the soundness of their approach, by achieving comparable performance to the centralised setting.

G.2. Automatic Transfer Learning

Transfer learning involves leveraging knowledge gained from one data-rich task or domain (the source) to improve performance on another data-poor related task/domain (the target), usually automating the selection and adaptation of existing models for the target tasks. One key problem, investigated in the literature, is evaluating the task's similarity and transferability, namely understanding the relationship between source and target tasks, which involves the definition of metrics and algorithms for quantifying task similarity and transferability, enabling better model selection and adaptation strategies [r153], [r154]. Since the domains involved can have differences (different features and/or different distributions) domain adaptation is another key problem to address, for which techniques such as adversarial training, domain alignment, and meta-learning have been proposed to enhance the transfer of models across different domains and distributions [r155], [r156].

Transfer learning is a need that emerged clearly in GREEN.DAT.AI since the beginning of the project, in particular the transfer of knowledge between different geographical areas (e.g. new service areas which did not yet collect the significant historical data needed to build predictive models), also known as Geographical Transfer Learning. This specific topic is studied only sparsely in the literature, usually with rather narrow objectives. The most common problem considered is image recognition, typically satellite image labelling [r157], [r158] where Deep Learning classifiers are assigned to work on data-poor areas, and therefore the models learned in data-rich areas (usually CNN-based models) are adapted to the new domain. The authors of [r159] focus on crime prediction and, again, try to exploit the knowledge available in some areas to make reliable predictions on a different one having too little data to build a model. Finally, Liu et al. [r160] build shared bike demand prediction models over some cities (especially large ones, where more data is generally available) and then adapt them to other – usually smaller – ones. The work by Iddianozie and McArdle [r161] tackles the problem of labelling road networks and shows how assessing the similarity of street networks improves the transfer of a model from one city to another one. Finally, a set of geographical transfer strategies are proposed by Nanni et al. [r162] that are based on a wide range of geospatial features to characterise areas, transferring data or models through a weighing schema based on feature similarity.

H. SotA in Adaptive FL for Digital Twin Applications

Digital twins are characteristic for their ability to mimic the behaviour of real-world systems. Despite being primarily applied into Industry 4.0 settings; they are recently gaining attention for their environmental application [r163] by implementing a fusion of wide range of Earth Observations. In this context Joint Directors of Laboratories/Data Fusion Information Group (JDL/DFIG) data fusion model is considered to be a de-facto standard reference model for assessing features from heterogeneous data sources and streams, including remote sensing, IoT, and various thematic maps and attribute data.

Figure H.1: JDL/DGFI data fusion model for the implementation of digital twins.

JDL/DFIG model prescribes feature modelling over the six levels [r164], [r165] (as it can be seen in the figure above based on [r163]):

- Level 0 – Source pre-processing components have the objective to acquire and transform heterogeneous data sources into a coherent representation of overlaid data layers, aligned in space and time. Data harvesting mechanisms (capable of automatically fetching and/or federating Copernicus data, arbitrary MQTT-compliant IoT platforms, and OGC-compliant data distribution systems) are supplemented here by data source-specific denoising (e.g. convolution- and mathematical morphology-based filters), cleaning (e.g. data auditing with statistical methods and outlier detection) and transformation services (to map the data into a common format).
- Level 1 – Object assessment services address the first, low-level, generation of data products by performing arithmetic operations directly on data layers, aggregating and recombining attributes from different data layers, and structuring data product generation flows. For example, derivation of spectral indices based on physical characteristics of the observed objects (like vegetation, soil, and water quality indices from satellite data) is supported here, in addition to object recognition techniques, like land-use classification from satellite images [r166], LiDAR-based recognition of terrain, buildings or even individual trees [r167], [r168], [r169] and other objects of interest [r170], [r171].
- Level 2 – Situation assessment services focus on the extraction of spatial relationships amongst monitored objects and their characterises for recognition of situations. Thus, in addition to traditional tools used in geospatial analytics (like point pattern analysis, geostatistical analysis, spatial (auto) correlations and regressions), classifiers like decision trees, random forests and different Deep Learning approaches are applied here. For example, disease and pest detection [r172], quality drops in open water sources [r173], and climate-change related critical events like landslide [r174] have already been examined in this context.
- Level 3 – Impact assessment realises simulations and predictive analytics of socio-economic and environmental parameters. Here, tools for extraction of trends from the history of the behaviour of monitored objects or other entities are examined, combining traditional timeseries analytics (like (auto)regression and hidden Markov models) with regression based on deep and explainable learning with an orchestra of AI techniques. Such examples include a wide range of applications, from straightforward prediction of environmental parameters like air pollution [r175] to complex interconnected simulations of vegetation development [r163].
- Levels 4 and 5 focus on process (situation) refinements address actual decision support from the user perspective, addressing the efficiency of the system performances and visual analytics. For this

purpose, users are provided with dedicated tools for developing their own analytics flows and visually examining past, current, and future data layers and graphs with numerous statistic tools (including the assessment of spatial correlations with variograms and spatial autocorrelation like Moran I or G Statistics, cross correlations and dependency assessments, Granger causality estimations, and statistical dispersion) [r176].

Despite being focused on a single objective, the presented design allows performing a structured data fusion from heterogeneous data sources and streams within end-to-end applications, thus, ensuring environmental intelligence to be achieved based on digital twins. Further research into their adaptability to the changes in contextual settings of the processes they are mimicking (e.g. climate change and social trends) is, however, still to be addressed.

I. SotA in Automated IoT event-based change detection/ forecasting

Automated IoT event-based change detection and forecasting showcases algorithms tailored for real-time analysis of IoT data streams. These methods leverage event-driven architectures that can help in detecting anomalies, changes, and patterns in IoT data, enabling proactive decision-making. ML and statistical techniques facilitate accurate forecasting of future events and trends based on historical IoT data, enhancing predictive capabilities for various applications such as predictive maintenance, resource optimisation, and risk management.

I.1. Data Ingestion and Analysis

With the ever-growing volume and variety of data, the demand for efficient and flexible tools that can collect and integrate the various data-points from their sources, while able to meet the aggregation and analysis needs of downstream components is rising.

On this area there has been substantial presence in the software area of data integration tools like NiFi excel in facilitating the seamless movement of data across different sources. Nonetheless, they typically lack built-in functionality for centrally cataloguing the structure of ingested data. On the other hand, data catalogue tools (e.g., Amundsen, Datahub) function as a digital library for data assets, helping users to discover and manage different datasets scattered across different systems and formats. However, these often lack data movement capabilities and built-in analytical tools. Given the above observations, the need for a tool that can not only support the ‘box-moving’ functionality offered by data integration tools but can also catalogue the data being moved in a semantic and accessible manner is clear.

I.2. Accelerated Pattern Matching using Hardware Accelerators

Originally designed with a focus on tasks such as image, video, and signal processing, stream processors have evolved to accommodate general-purpose computing needs, particularly in computationally intensive workloads. Massively parallel processors, such as GPUs or modern Central Processing Units (CPUs), utilise SIMD instruction sets [r177], which enable the simultaneous operations on multiple data elements within a single operation.

The continuous processing of streaming data serves various purposes across different fields, such as real-time network traffic processing, AI-driven real-time predictions and continuous monitoring of real-time data resulting from sensors, even in diverse sectors (e.g., healthcare, agriculture). Accelerating computationally intensive workloads to meet the demands of continuously generated streaming data is essential, and it can be achieved by employing SIMD-enabled stream processors.

The ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ tool takes advantage of those powerful, SIMD-enabled, multi-core processors to enhance the performance of pattern matching. Pattern matching is the core operation of the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ and involves determining whether a specific keyword (referred to as a pattern) is present within a text-based phrase (referred to as input). Due to its computational nature and demands, the computations of pattern matching can be parallelised, depending on the underlying algorithm used, enabling streaming processing. The pattern matching algorithm employed in the ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ is inspired by the Aho-Corasick algorithm [r178]. The main characteristic that makes the Aho-Corasick algorithm ideal for string searching when there is need for efficiency and real-time results is the capability of simultaneous searching of multiple string patterns. In addition, as the nature of the algorithm facilitates parallelisation, using hardware accelerators significantly enhances performance efficiency.

Furthermore, pattern matching serves as the fundamental operation in numerous network packet processing applications, while it is also used for log analysis, monitoring of sensor data in sectors like healthcare, and transportation. In addition, pattern matching is used in bioinformatics tasks such as aligning RNA structures, among others [r179], [r180]. Finally, there are numerous works in the literature that examine the acceleration of network packet processing computations using GPUs [r181], [r182], [r183], [r184], [r185], while others aim for efficient load balancing between heterogeneous applications and hardware devices [r184], [r186], [r187].

The ‘Accelerated Event Processing Engine’ tool that TUC offers in the context of the GREEN.DAT.AI project enables the efficient and simultaneous search of multiple patterns against large volumes of input. As the main operation of the tool is built upon the principles of the Aho-Corasick algorithm, its execution on SIMD-enabled hardware devices, such as GPUs or modern CPUs, offers significant performance acceleration. In addition, this computational speedup, when compared to similar CPU-based SotA tools, such as the GNU grep utility¹⁹, clearly promotes energy efficiency. Particularly, in cases that the proposed pattern matching procedure leads to double processing throughput (i.e., double data size processed in the same amount of time), then, the energy efficiency achieved is paramount, since there is no need to double the resources (leading to double processing power consumption).

¹⁹ <https://man7.org/linux/man-pages/man1/grep.1.html>

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Appendix II – Ethics Checklist

Ethics Checklist and Questionnaire

THIS FORM NEEDS TO BE FILLED-IN BY THE DELIVERABLE LEADER DURING THE WORK LEADING TO THE RELEVANT DELIVERABLE. DELIVERABLE LEADERS ARE ENCOURAGED TO DISCUSS EACH ACTIVE QUESTIONNAIRE WITH THE ETHICS COMMITTEE. EACH OPEN QUESTIONNAIRE SHOULD EITHER BE STORED IN THE PROJECT MS TEAMS DIRECTORY OR A LINK MADE AVAILABLE TO THE RELEVANT SHARED DOC. COMPLETED FORMS NEED TO BE SUBMITTED AS PART OF THE DELIVERABLE Q/A PROCESS. IN THE EVENT OF COMMENTS AND/OR QUESTIONS BY THE ETHICS COMMITTEE, THE DELIVERABLE LEADER HAS TO PROVIDE RELEVANT RESPONSES AND/OR CLARIFICATIONS IN A TIMELY MANNER

A. PERSONAL DATA

1. Has **personal data** going to be processed for the completion of this deliverable?
 - If “yes”, do they refer only to individuals connected to project partners or to third parties as well?

Answer: *This deliverable does not contain any personal data.*

2. Are “**special categories of personal data**” going to be processed for this deliverable? (whereby these include personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, and trade union membership, as well as, genetic data, biometric data, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation).

Answer: *No.*

3. Has the **consent** of the individuals concerned been acquired prior to the processing of their personal data?
 - If “yes”, is it based on the Project’s Informed Consent Form, either on the provided Template or on other attached herein Template?
 - If “no”, is it based on a different legal basis?

Answer: *No, as we do not process any personal data.*

4. In the event of processing of personal data, is the processing:
 - obviously “**Fair and lawful**”, meaning executed in a fair manner and following consent of the individuals concerned or based on another - acknowledged as adequate and proportionate as per above - legal basis?

Answer: *Yes.*

- Performed for a **specific (project-related) cause** only?

Answer: *Yes.*

- Executed based on the principle of **proportionality and data minimization** (meaning that only data that are necessary for the processing purposes are being processed and such deductive reasoning is documented)?

Answer: Yes.

- Based on **high-quality, updated, and precise** personal data?

Answer: Yes.

5. Are there any provisions for a storage limitation period of the personal data-in case of storage- after which they must be erased?

Answer: No.

6. Are all **other lawful requirements** for the processing of the data (for example, **notification of the competent Data Protection Authority(s)** or undergoing a **DPIA procedure** and consulting with the competent DPA, if and where applicable) adhered to and on what legislative basis are such notifications justified as necessary or dismissed as unnecessary?

Answer: No, as there are no personal data contained in this deliverable.

7. Have individuals been **made aware of their rights** on the processing of the personal data as per the GDPR and the relevant and executive national legislation (particularly the rights to access, rectify and delete the personal data and their right to lodge a complaint with the relevant Competent Authority) and if yes, by what demonstrable means (e.g. the informed consent form as per above or as per other Templates, attached herein?)

Answer: No, as there are no individuals named within the deliverable.

8. Even if anonymized or pseudonymized or aggregated data are referred to, does the dataset contain **data** that could potentially (even via the combined use of other datasets) **be traced back to individuals**? If yes, what specific measures are taken to ensure this data (i) is anonymized or pseudonymized and (ii) cannot be used to track individuals without their consent? If no, what is the scientific methodology used to collect and gather said data?

Answer: No.

9. In the context of risk assessment, prediction, and forecasting, as foreseen in the scope of the GREEN.DAT.AI project, **is there any risk** that personal data could be inadvertently revealed in the event of an **emergency** or **unusual event**, because of the dataset usage, either on its own or combined with other openly available datasets, triggering identification or unwanted disclosure of Personal Identifiable Information (PII)? What measures are in place to protect - still identifiable if the dataset allows such extraction - **personal data** in these circumstances?

Answer: No, as there are no personal data contained in this deliverable.

10. Is there any potentially PII in the datasets, **disclosable by combination with other datasets**, either open data or proprietary? If yes, how is PII adequately anonymized or pseudonymized or how other datasets that by combination may result in unwanted or illegal disclosures or identification before any processing takes place?

Answer: No, as there are no such PII contained in this deliverable.

B. DATA SECURITY

1. Have proportionate security measures been undertaken for protection of the data, considering project requirements and the nature of the data?
- If yes, brief description of such measures (including physical-world measures, if any)
 - If yes, is there a data breach notification policy in place within your organization (including an Incident Response Plan to such a breach)?

Answer: No, as there are no datasets being produced in this deliverable.

2. Given the **large-scale nature** of some datasets, are there specific measures in place to protect **included personal data** at scale at the data source or in the possession of data processors?

Answer: No, as there are no personal data contained in this deliverable.

3. Are there specific measures in place to secure **sensitive infrastructure data**, if present?

Answer: No, as there are no datasets being produced in this deliverable.

C. DATA TRANSFERS

1. Are personal data transfers beyond project partners going to take place for this deliverable?
- If “yes”, do these include transfers to third (non-EU) countries and if what policies apply?

Answer: No.

2. Are personal data transfers to public authorities going to take place for this deliverable?

Answer: No.

3. Do any state authorities have direct or indirect access to personal data processed for this deliverable?

Answer: No.

4. Considering that the Project Coordinator is the “controller” of the processing and that all other project partners involved in this deliverable are “processors” within the same contexts, are there any other personal data processing roles further attributed to any third parties for this deliverable? And if any, are they conformed to the GDPR provisions?

Answer: No.

5. Given the geographical diversity of the datasets, are there measures in place to ensure compliance with specific personal data protection regulations **in different jurisdictions** i.e., at the place of the data source establishment as well as at the place of the establishment of a Data processor?

Answer: Not applicable.

6. Are there additional protocols for data transfers involving **sensitive infrastructure data** if present?

Answer: Not applicable.

D. ETHICS AND RELATED ISSUES

1. Are personal data of children going to be processed for this?

Answer: No.

2. Is **profiling** of identifiable individuals in any way enabled or facilitated for this deliverable?

Answer: No.

3. Are **automated decisions** for identifiable individuals made or enabled on the basis this deliverable?

Answer: No.

4. Have partners for this deliverable taken into consideration system architectures of **privacy by design** and/or **privacy by default**, as appropriate?

Answer: Yes.

5. Have partners for this deliverable taken into consideration gender equality policies or is there an explicit reasoning that dismisses such risk as unsubstantiated or such need as irrelevant as per the methodology of work and production of the deliverable?

Answer: Yes.

6. Have partners for this deliverable taken into consideration means of protecting the confidentiality of the dataset if it is not signified as open data?

Answer: Yes.

7. Are there additional considerations around the collection and processing of data **that could potentially be used to infer patterns about individuals**?

Answer: No.

8. Have partners identified any **additional ethical issues** related to the processing of sensitive infrastructure data?

Answer: No.

9. Is the Project taking into account the need for an all people-inclusive policy in the future within its overall goals and not only the “tech-savvy” (i.e., elderly people not familiar with some tech devices, poor people) and does it entail possible proposals for that?

Answer: No.